

Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation

**Theoretical Study of THz Magnon Dynamics in
Transition-Metal-Based Magnetic Insulators**

Andi Gumarilang Cakti Ahmadi

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Division of Material Science
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遷移金属系磁性絶縁体におけるテラヘルツ帯マグノンの理論的研究

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Abstract

Recent advancements in telecommunication and signal processing devices prompt the use of radio spectrum in the THz frequency, and the frequency of collective precession of magnetic moments in magnetically ordered solid, called magnons, falls within the THz regimes. The magnon frequency responses are mainly determined by the present magnetic interactions in the system, which strongly depends on the electronic states of the constituent atoms. Transition-metal (TM)-based magnetic insulators offer wide range of magnetic interaction types with varying strengths, due to varying electron occupation in the d orbitals, and different magnon frequency responses are consequently expected for one magnetic structure composed from different TM cations. If nonmagnetic ligands with strong spin-orbital coupling (SOC) effects are present in the vicinity of the TM cations, anisotropic magnetic interactions, e.g., Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs), appear, which drive magnon to propagate unidirectionally, leading to a non-trivial topological magnon phase. The understanding how the magnetic interactions in the TM-based magnetic insulators gives rise to THz magnon dynamics and other macroscopically observable physics is necessary for the utilization in the THz frequency devices.

In this work, the interplay between magnetic interactions on THz magnon dynamics in bulk (3D) antiferromagnetic insulators transition-metal monoxides, TMOs (MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO), and thin-film (2D) van der Waals (vdW) ferromagnetic insulator CrI₃/As bilayers, which hosts topological magnon, are theoretically investigated. This dissertation consists of five chapters. In Chapter one, the background and purposes of this study are presented, and the importance of exploiting magnons to carry and process THz frequency signal is addressed. In Chapter two, theoretical foundation for density functional theory (DFT) are thoroughly described, with special emphasis on the generalization of magnetic force theorem (MFT). The mathematical methods to solve the spin Hamiltonian model parameterized by the generalized spin-exchange constants are also presented based on linear spin-wave theory (LSWT) and its extension to many-body Green's function.

Chapter three is devoted to benchmarking the developed MFT and LSWT by investigating the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions and magnetic anisotropy on the Néel temperatures and the THz antiferromagnetic resonance (AFMR) frequencies in 3D bulk TMOs. The experimentally observed Néel temperature of each TMO is successfully captured by the isotropic spin-exchange interactions obtained from the developed MFT. On the other hand, only the AFMR frequencies of MnO and NiO are successfully captured by the LSWT, while those of FeO and CoO are not well captured in the present

work. Furthermore, it is found that the THz AFMR frequencies of MnO and NiO is mainly affected by the magnetic dipolar interactions, and rhombohedral lattice distortion is required to explain the experimentally observed lower AFMR frequency. In the case of the FeO and CoO, the effect of SOC is only introduced phenomenologically via magnetocrystalline anisotropy, while, in reality, the SOC also induces multiple non-degenerate spin states, which require the general LSWT, i.e., flavor-wave theory, to fully capture the effect.

In Chapter four, the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions and DMIs on THz topological magnons in 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayer are discussed, and the stacking order dependence of magnetism and magnonics properties of CrI₃ layer is addressed. Specially, having non-trivial topological magnon phase and high Curie temperature require the DMIs to be strong enough to drive the unidirectional magnon, i.e., chiral edge states, but weaker than isotropic spin-exchange interaction to keep collinear magnetic ground state. For this, the modulations of isotropic spin-exchange constants and DMIs in the CrI₃ layer, by addressing the stacking order dependence of its magnetic and magnonic properties, are demonstrated. This stems from the change of electronic states of Cr *d* orbitals under site symmetry breaking induced by the As substrate and interfacial charge transfer from the As substrate to the I sub-layer, that chemically alters the symmetry of the spin-pair. Chirality of magnon edge states, which indicates a non-trivial topological magnon phase, is modulated depending on the stacking order of CrI₃/As bilayers, where the chirality of the magnon edge states disappears under broken mirror and rotational symmetry. Although the chirality of magnon edge states is lost, the two counter-propagating magnons edge states undergo different magnon damping, which is mainly attributed to the finite second-nearest neighbor DMIs that are perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis.

This work is concluded in Chapter five with the prospect for future work.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Magnons for Terahertz Frequency Carrier

1.1.1 The Need of Terahertz Frequency Band

The pursuit of advancing human life through technological development is progressing rapidly across various fields and scales. In integrated circuits, this progress is largely driven by the push to increase transistor density on wafers, which is captured by Moore's Law [1]. In telecommunications, the focus is on raising data rates to meet ever-growing service demands, as predicted by Edholm's Law of bandwidth [2] in 1998. Over the past few years, wireless data traffic has surged at an unprecedented rate: mobile data traffic was expected to increase sevenfold between 2016 and 2021, while video traffic was projected to triple during the same period [3]. By 2030, wireless data rates are predicted to rival those of wired broadband, as illustrated in Fig. 1.1. This explosive growth in wireless usage has motivated researchers to explore new regions of the radio spectrum to meet rising global demands. Among these, the terahertz (THz) band—spanning from 0.1 to 10 THz—has gained renewed attention for its potential to deliver seamless data transfer, virtually unlimited bandwidth, microsecond-level latency, and terabit-per-second (Tbps) capacities [4–6]. Positioned in the electromagnetic spectrum between the microwave region (\sim GHz) of electronic devices and the optical region (\sim 100 THz) of photonic devices, as shown in Fig. 1.2, the THz frequency range offers unique advantages: high communication capacity from its wide bandwidth, strong resistance to interference, and compact antenna sizes enabled by shorter wavelengths than those in microwave devices. However, the challenge lies in the lack of suitable materials capable of efficiently operating at THz frequencies. The THz frequency range is too high for conventional microwave electronics yet too low for photonic devices. Consequently, identifying new materials and methods for transmitting and processing information at THz frequencies has become a critical research priority.

Figure 1.1: Data rates of wireless local area network (LAN) and cellular predicted up to the year 2035 [7].

Figure 1.2: Electromagnetic spectrum that covers a range from radiowaves to X-Rays. The ranges of microwave electronics, THz, and photonics devices are also indicated [8].

1.1.2 Joule Heating-Free Magnetic Excitation Called Magnon

Development of high energy-efficient devices to process information requires materials with low energy dissipation when the information propagates. In magnetic solids, a propagating collective precession of localized magnetic moments can be utilized to carry and process the information rather than merely conduction electrons. This propagating collective precession is called *spin-wave*, and within quantum mechanical framework, the quasiparticles that carry spin-wave is called *magnon*, as shown in Fig. 1.3. Magnon carry not only energy, but also heat and spin angular momentum in which information can be encoded in and detected. Felix Bloch first proposed the idea of magnons in 1931 [9] to explain how the spontaneous magnetization was reduced in ferromagnets at high temperature. The idea was further theoretically developed by Holstein, Primakoff, and Dyson [10, 11], which gave birth to the modern spin-wave theory and magnonics, a branch field of spintronics that deals with the excitation, propagation, control, and detection of magnons in magnetic solids.

As an information carrier, magnonics-based system offer several advantages over conduction electrons-based systems. First, the propagation of magnons does not involve moving conduction electron which implies minimized Joule heating and reduced energy consumption. Second, since magnon possesses wave-like nature, the information can be encoded in multiple forms, for instance frequency, amplitudes, and polarization [13–16]. The operation frequency of magnons typically ranges from GHz to THz ranges, which is beneficial for microwave applications. The magnon polarization refers to which direction the magnetic moment perform precession, and multiple magnon polarization might exist in magnetic solids, e.g., one polarization mode, attributed to one magnon mode, in ferromagnets and two opposite magnon polarization mode, attributed to two magnon modes, in antiferromagnets, as shown in Fig. 1.4. Experimentally, magnons can be excited by applying radio-frequency electromagnetic field with magnetic field component perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis, in which the oscillating magnetic field drives magnetic moment precession, resulting in coherent magnons being excited [12]. By measuring the magnetic susceptibility response,

Figure 1.3: A propagation of collective precession of magnetic moment, as seen from (a) positive z axis and (b) positive y axis [12].

Figure 1.4: Magnon dispersion and its polarization in (a) ferromagnets, and (b) antiferromagnets [20]. In ferromagnetic case, only one type of polarization exists with frequency of precession described by the magnon dispersion. In antiferromagnet case, one polarization has a counter-clockwise precession direction, while another polarization has a clock-wise precession direction. These two polarizations are attributed to two magnon modes.

the absorption peak correspond to the excited magnon frequency, while the width of the peak corresponds to the magnon damping, which is a dissipation channel for magnons. For THz frequency magnons, the excitation method typically consists of using ultrafast laser pulse [17–19].

In static limit, each localized magnetic moment in a magnetic solid ‘communicates’ with each other via magnetic interactions, forming magnetic order and energetically preferable magnetic moment direction, i.e., magnetic easy axis. Dynamically, the magnetic interactions present in the magnetic solids, e.g., isotropic spin-exchange interactions [Fig. 1.5(a)], magnetic anisotropy, and magnetic dipolar interactions, determines the operation frequency of magnons. Specifically, these magnetic interactions yields a very large internal effective magnetic field that acts on a magnetic moment, which can be up to 1000 T in magnetic solids, resulting in magnon frequency ranging from sub-THz to THz. Furthermore, the magnetic interactions also determine how magnon propagate in magnetic solids. For instance, easy-plane magnetic anisotropy in an antiferromagnet induces varying magnon polarization magnitudes from 0 to \hbar [21]. The presence of anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, such as Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) [Fig. 1.5(b)], can induce non-trivial topological magnon propagation, in which there exists magnon states that propagate only at the edges of the magnets and allow only one direction of propagation (chiral) in THz frequency, free from back-scattering [22–30]. This is called chiral edge states and lies only at the frequency gap of magnon spectrum.

In an approximate semiclassical picture, magnons in collinear magnets with only isotropic spin-exchange interactions and local magnetic anisotropy are well described under linear spin-wave theory (LSWT), where multiple interactions or scatterings between magnons are ignored. However, the DMI, the magnetic interactions that drives topological magnons in magnetic solids, generates high-order terms beyond the LSWT approximation, which physically correspond to the scatterings between magnons and result in magnon

Figure 1.5: (a) Isotropic spin-exchange interactions with an exchange constants J_{ij}^{ex} and (b) Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions with a vector \mathbf{D}_{ij} , which align and twist magnetic moment \mathbf{S}_i and \mathbf{S}_j , respectively.

decay or damping [31–34]. The scatterings between magnons reduces the efficiency of magnon edge states propagation, by shifting and broadening the absorption response in magnetic susceptibility measurement from the theoretical prediction by the LSWT. Therefore, it is necessary to confirm the existence of magnon edge states under multiple magnon interactions, i.e., higher-order terms beyond the LSWT approximation.

1.1.3 Computational Method for General Magnetic Interactions

The magnetic interactions present in magnetically ordered solids are commonly obtained by mapping multiple variation of magnetic configurations into multiple magnetic energy expressions (also called magnetic Hamiltonian). For collinear magnets, in which all magnetic moments point in one direction either in parallel or anti-parallel, the computational time and cost are relatively undemanding, and the accuracy of the obtained magnetic interaction depends only on the convergency of the total energy of each magnetic configuration. Particularly, one needs to employ large magnetic supercell and figure out multiple collinear magnetic configurations that are symmetrically distinct, such as different antiferromagnetic orders, ferrimagnetic orders, and a ferromagnetic order. The computational time and cost comes from the use of multiple self-consistent calculations and large magnetic supercell.

On the other hand, for non-collinear magnets, in which each magnetic moment points in an arbitrary direction, the total energy mapping is generalized by taking into account the magnetic moment directions and symmetrically distinct non-collinear magnetic configurations. This is called as generic four-states methods [35], where for each magnetic interaction between a pair of magnetic moment, one needs to calculate total energy of four non-collinear magnetic configurations for only one type of magnetic interactions. This results in the tremendous computational time and cost due to the use of multiple non-collinear self-consistent calculations in the supercell.

One possible route to tackle the computational demand of general magnetic interactions calculations is to employ a method based on electronic wave-functions and energies, which is known as magnetic force theorem (MFT) [36]. In the collinear magnetic configurations, the MFT is computationally fast and convenient due to the use of one initial guess of magnetic configurations in a magnetic unit cell, instead of a magnetic supercell. The computational cost and time comes only from the convergency of the self-consistent

calculation in one initial guess magnetic configuration. However, in order to calculate the non-collinear magnetic interactions, such as DMIs in Fig. 1.5(b), one needs to generalize the MFT to take into account the non-collinearity in the linear response theory. The generalization of the MFT will speed and ease the calculations of non-collinear magnetic interactions, without the need of manually taking into account the symmetry consideration in the magnetic configurations, since the electronic wave-functions already includes the symmetry of the crystals. The comparison between the total energy mapping, four-states method, and MFT are summarized in the Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Comparison between computational methods to calculate magnetic interactions in a magnetically periodic solid.

	Total Energy Mapping	Four-States Method [35]	MFT [36]
Magnetic Configurations	Multiple Collinear	Multiple Non-Collinear	One Collinear
Size of Unit Cell	Supercell	Supercell	Unit Cell
Output	Isotropic	Isotropic+Anisotropic	Isotropic

1.2 Group 3 Transition-Metal-Based Magnetic Insulators

1.2.1 Three-Dimensional (3D) Transition-Metal Monoxides (TMOs)

Transition-metal monoxides (TMOs) is a class of antiferromagnetic insulators with rock-salt crystal structure belonging to $Fm\bar{3}m$ space group. Based on their electronic band dispersion, the TMOs are classified as Mott-type insulators [37, 38], where standard one-electron band theory predicted the TMOs to be electrically conducting, but the strongly-correlated $3d$ orbitals electrons in the TM cations results in the electrically insulating properties. In the paramagnetic phase, the primitive unit cell consists of one TM cations (Mn, Fe, Co, or Ni) and one oxygen anions, while it consists of two TM cations with opposite magnetic moments and two oxygen anions in the antiferromagnetic phase type-II (AFM-II) below their respective Néel temperature. In the antiferromagnetic phase, TM cations are antiferromagnetically arranged along [111] direction and ferromagnetically arranged within the (111) plane, as shown in Fig. 1.6. Additionally, each TM cations is connected to six second-nearest neighbors Ni atoms with opposite magnetic moments mediated by oxygen atoms and forms an octahedra coordination. This octahedra coordination is also responsible for the stable antiferromagnetic structure, in which the interaction between two second-nearest neighboring TM cations mediated by oxygen known are super-exchange interaction.

Different electron occupation in the minority t_{2g} states among the TMOs results in different strength of magnetic interactions, i.e., isotropic spin-exchange constants and magnetocrystalline anisotropy from spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effects, which are the driving forces of THz magnon excitation. Different Néel temperatures between the TMOs are the indication of different strength of isotropic spin-exchange interactions, e.g., the strength of the 180° TM-O-TM super-exchange interactions [39]. Furthermore, different electron occupation in the minority t_{2g} states results in different magnetic easy axis and magnetic anisotropy between the TMOs. For instance, empty and fully-occupied minority t_{2g} states in the MnO and NiO results in negligible contribution of magnetocrystalline anisotropy from SOC to the total magnetic anisotropy, while the partially occupied minority t_{2g} states in the FeO and CoO results in the large contribution of magnetocrystalline anisotropy from SOC to the total magnetic anisotropy [40].

Experimentally, the TMOs also exhibits antiferromagnetic resonance (AMFR) frequencies, which is known as zero- \mathbf{k} magnon frequencies, in THz regimes [41–47]. However, how the magnetic interactions, i.e., the spin-exchange interactions and the magnetic anisotropy affect the magnon excitation in the $3d$ TMOs remains unaddressed, which are the key for designing AFM materials for THz-frequency signal applications.

Figure 1.6: Cubic rock-salt structure of a transition-metal monoxide (TMO) in an antiferromagnetic type-II (AFM-II) phase, where the the TM cations are ferromagnetically ordered within the (111) plane and antiferromagnetically ordered along the [111] directions. The blue and red semi-transparent planes represent the (111) planes. Blue and green spheres represent the TM cation (Mn, Fe, Co, or Ni) and O atoms, respectively. The red and blue arrows indicate the magnetic moment of TM cations.

1.2.2 Two-Dimensional (2D) Transition-Metal Trihalides (TMTHs)

Exfoliation of atomically thin graphene from a bulk graphite marked the beginning of two-dimensional (2D) van der Waals (vdW) materials [48–51] and opened new avenues for engineering the physical properties via heterostructures and theoretical advances, such as topology and fluctuation-driven generation of new phases [52–55]. Furthermore, the observation of ferromagnetism in a single layer CrI_3 [56] and pristine double layer $\text{Cr}_2\text{Ge}_2\text{Te}_6$ [57] opened a new material class in 2D vdW materials that exhibit finite temperature magnetism in reduced dimensions, which tackles the Mermin-Wagner restriction of 2D magnetism [58]. This is possible due to the strong magnetic anisotropy compensating spin fluctuation, which allows magnetic order to form at finite temperature. The combination of magnetism and 2D structures enables tuning of electronic and magnetic states by stacking order [59–62], strain [63–68], electric gating [69–72], magneto-optical effects, and proximity effects.

Transition-metal trihalides (TMTHs), with a formula MX_3 (where the M is a transition-metal atom and X is a halide atom) and honeycomb structures, offer a broad range of electronic and magnetic properties. For magnonics application, it is desirable to have a magnetic insulator as a platform for magnon propagation, and Cr-based ferromagnetic insulators TMTH satisfy this purpose in the monolayer limit. Furthermore, the honeycomb structure of TMTH guarantees the existence of Dirac points in either electronic band dispersion or the magnon dispersion, which is a key ingredient for realizing non-trivial topological phase in electronic or magnonic properties.

The electron interactions and magnetic interactions in the TMTH determines whether the Dirac points is opened or not. In terms of topological magnonics properties, CrBr_3 [73] and CrI_3 [74, 75] have been identified as a topological magnon insulators, which possesses gapped bulk magnon dispersion at the Dirac point and chiral magnon edge states driven by the DMIs between second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms. In contrast, CrCl_3 , with a weak SOC effects, is identified as magnon Dirac materials, which is characterized by a gapless Dirac point in the magnon dispersion [76, 77].

In terms of magnetic anisotropy, although the Cr atoms has a quenched orbital angular momentum ($\mathbf{L} = 0$), the magnetic anisotropy in the Cr-based TMTH shows large variation of magnitude, ranging from 0.01 to 3 T of magnetic anisotropy field. This large variation of magnetic anisotropy is mainly attributed by the strong SOC of the non-magnetic ligands, i.e., the Cl^- , Br^- , and I^- ions [78–81], rather than that of Cr atom itself. Multiplet cluster model [82] revealed that anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, called Kitaev interactions, between first-nearest neighbor Cr atoms mediated by the ligands are responsible for large magnetic anisotropy in Cr-based TMTH, which strongly depends on the SOC strength of the ligands. In line with multiple cluster model, the calculation based on strong-coupling perturbation theory [83] also confirmed the non-local origin of large magnetic anisotropy due to the Kitaev interactions between the first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms via super-exchange with I atoms.

The finite DMIs, that open Dirac points in the magnon dispersion, and Kitaev interactions,

that give rise to large magnetic anisotropy, signify the importance of anisotropic spin-exchange interactions via non-magnetic ligands in the TMTH. For this reason, CrI_3 is a good choice for magnonic application due to the strong SOC of I atoms compared to other halogen ligands. Additionally, magneto-Raman spectroscopy [84, 85] observed the THz magnon excitation in a monolayer CrI_3 , which indicates suitability of CrI_3 as a material platform for THz signal processing via magnons.

By exploiting weak interlayer vdW interactions, stacking CrI_3 with other CrI_3 layer or different materials has proven to effectively tune the magnetic interactions and magnon excitation in the CrI_3 , which is experimentally possible by performing mechanical interlayer sliding [86], terahertz light pulse-induced interlayer shear strain [87], and ion intercalation [88]. In a CrI_3 bilayer, the stacking order between two layers of CrI_3 defines the magnetic ground states, and it was demonstrated that shifting one layer of CrI_3 relative to another drives the ferromagnetic phase into layered antiferromagnetic phase via the interlayer isotropic spin-exchange interactions [89]. Additionally, the stacking order in the CrI_3 bilayer defines the topological magnon phase indicated by the stacking-dependent gap opening at Dirac point, which is mainly attributed to modulation of intralayer DMIs and Kitaev interactions by the stacking orders [90]. In CrI_3/Cu and CrI_3/Au , interfacial charge transfer from metallic atom into the I sublayer induces a significant change of DMIs, while the isotropic spin-exchange interactions relatively unchanged [91]. The ratio between the DMI and the isotropic spin-exchange interactions reaches around 20%, which induces the formation of chiral spin texture as the magnetic ground state in the CrI_3 . This is in agreement with the skyrmion formation condition, where the ratio larger than 15% is needed to form the skyrmion magnetic structure [92–95]. In CrI_3/As , CrI_3/Sb , and CrI_3/Bi , significant change of isotropic spin-exchange interactions was observed up to four times from that of monolayer CrI_3 , which results in enhanced Curie temperature from 44 to 165 K [96]. Additionally, the small lattice mismatch between CrI_3 and triangular lattice of non-magnetic As, Sb, and Bi makes the bilayer between them is preferable, since no magnon states splitting occurs due to large magnetic unit cell, in contrary to CrI_3/Cu and CrI_3/Au as one would expect.

In order to have a stable and experimentally observable chiral edge states in topological magnon insulators, it is necessary to have large enough DMIs to open the Dirac gap, but not too large as it drives the formation of non-collinear magnetic ground states. The ratios between DMIs and isotropic spin-exchange interactions among Cr-based 2D vdW materials with honeycomb structure, including CrI_3 based heterostructure, are shown in Fig. 1.7. To have large topological magnon gap while retaining the collinear ferromagnetic phase, the ratio needs to be smaller than 15%, but large enough to induce gap opening.

Figure 1.7: The ratio between Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) and isotropic spin-exchange interactions in several Cr-based heterostructures with honeycomb structures, in unit of percentage, including the CrI_3 -based. In $\text{Cr}_2\text{Ge}_2\text{Te}_6/\text{PtSe}_2$, two stacking orders are labeled as (A) and (B). The superscript [a], [b], and [c] correspond to references [91], [67], and [62], respectively.

1.3 Purposes and Content of Manuscript

Based on previous introductions, in this work, the interplay between magnetic interactions, e.g., isotropic spin-exchange, Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions, and magnetic anisotropy, on THz magnon dynamics of 3D (bulk) TMOs and 2D (film) vdW CrI₃/As bilayers are investigated. The magnetic force theorem is performed to extract the generalized spin-exchange interactions, and the physical origin of the isotropic and anisotropic spin-exchange interactions are discussed in terms of electronic states of 3D TMOs and 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayers. Then, the linear spin-wave theory is performed to analyze the interplay between magnetic interactions on magnon dynamics in 3D TMOs and 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayers. The extension to many-body Green's function of magnons is additionally performed to elucidate the stability of topological magnons in the multiple stacking orders of 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayers.

This manuscript is organized into five chapters. The background of the study and purposes is presented in Chapter 1. The details for first-principles calculation based on full-potential linearized augmented plane wave is presented in Chapter 2. Special emphasis is put on magnetic force theorem, in which the expression of generalized spin-exchange interactions, including the isotropic and anisotropic parts such as DMIs, is derived in terms of the linearized augmented plane wave basis, which allows us to calculate the isotropic spin-exchange and Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions directly from electronic states. The quantum theory of magnons is also presented, where the linear spin-wave theory and many-body Green's function that acts as a perturbation to magnons are presented in detail. The benchmarking of magnetic force theorem and linear spin-wave theory on bulk transition-metal monoxides (TMOs), consisting of MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO, are presented in Chapter 3, where the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions and magnetic anisotropy on the THz AFMR frequencies are particularly discussed. The bulk TMOs are chosen due to the rich experimental data related to the spin-exchange interactions and magnon excitation, making them as good testbed for benchmarking the developed methods. Calculation results on monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As bilayers are presented in Chapter 4, including the modulation of isotropic spin-exchange interactions, DMIs, THz topological magnon properties, and the magnon damping of the edge states. The conclusion of this work is stated in Chapter 5.

Chapter 2

First-Principles Calculation

2.1 Introduction

The interactions between nuclei and electrons in solid-state matter give rise to observable chemical and physical properties, which can be exploited for utilization in modern electronic devices. Mathematically, the behaviours of the nuclei and electrons in solid-state matters are governed by the solution of a many-body Schrödinger equation, and solving such a many-body equation is not a trivial task. First approach to solve the equation is to assume that the timescale in which nuclei move around the equilibrium position is longer than the timescale of electrons due to the heavy mass of nuclei, and this approximation is known as *Born-Oppenheimer* approximation [97]. The time-independent many-body Hamiltonian of electrons is written as,

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \nabla_i^2 + \sum_{i=1, j \neq i}^N \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|} + \sum_{i=1}^N V(\mathbf{r}_i), \quad (2.1)$$

where the first term is the sum of kinetic energy of individual electrons in the system, the second term is the two-body Coulomb interaction between electrons, and the third term represents the interaction between individual electron and an external field. The solutions of this equation is the wavefunction of all electrons $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N)$, which correspond to the ground state energy E . Note that this is a nonrelativistic case, and no spin of electrons is considered up to this point.

Various methods for obtaining the solution of this many-body equation under the Born-Oppenheimer approximation have been developed for decades, such as Hartree-Fock method [98], where the wavefunction of many-body electrons is the product of every wavefunction of individual electrons with an antisymmetric property included. Furthermore, in density functional theory (DFT), proposed by Hohenberg and Kohn in 1964 [99], the ground state properties of a many-electron system are determined from its ground state electron density, which reduces the many-body interactions into effective interactions that act on one electron, as shown in Fig. 2.1. This proposal reduces the problem of solving a many-electron system from $3N$ variables into 3 variables.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the simplification that density functional theory (DFT) offers, which reduces a many-body problem of interacting particles into a system consisting of an electron density with an effective interaction [100].

2.2 Density Functional Theory

2.2.1 Hohenberg-Kohn Theorem

In 1964, Walter Kohn and Pierre Hohenberg laid the foundation of DFT, which is known as *Hohenberg-Kohn* theorem. This foundation consists of two theorems. First theorem expresses that (1) *the ground state energy E of a system from Schrödinger equation is a unique functional of the electron density $n(\mathbf{r})$* . This theorem can be extended into the spin-polarized case by defining a total energy as a functional of two electron densities with opposite spins, $E[n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r})]$.

While the first theorem only tells the existence of a total energy and an electron density, the second theorem specifies the electron density that corresponds to the ground state of the system. The second theorem expresses that (2) *The electron density that minimizes the energy of the overall functional is the true electron density corresponding to the full solution of the Schrödinger equation*. With the help of a variational principle, the ground state density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$ is obtained and corresponds to the ground state energy functional $E_0[n_0(\mathbf{r})]$ given by,

$$E_0[n_0(\mathbf{r})] \leq E[n(\mathbf{r})], \quad (2.2)$$

and, the total energy functional is given by,

$$E[n] = T[n] + E_H[n] + V[n]. \quad (2.3)$$

$T[n]$ is the kinetic energy of the interacting electrons, $E_H[n]$ represents Hartree energy, which is a Coulomb interaction of electron charge density including self-interaction, and $V[n]$ is the interactions between electrons and an external potential.

2.2.2 Kohn-Sham Equation

In 1965, Walter Kohn and Lue Jeu Sham [101, 102] proposed that the interacting energy functional can approximately be replaced by an energy functional of the non-interacting

electrons that is subject to an "effective" potential. The resulting equation is known as the Kohn-Sham equation and has become the core of every DFT-based calculation method.

The electron density is given by a sum of non-interacting electron densities,

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{i=1} |\psi_i(\mathbf{r})|, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\psi_i(\mathbf{r})$ is a non-interacting electron wavefunction, and the densities are summed over states i . The integral of electron density $n(\mathbf{r})$ over real space correspond to the number of electron, N ,

$$N = \int d^3\mathbf{r} n(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.5)$$

The total energy functional is given by,

$$E_{\text{KS}}[n] = T_{\text{s}}[n] + E_{\text{H}}[n] + V[n] + E_{\text{xc}}[n], \quad (2.6)$$

where $T_{\text{s}}[n]$ is the kinetic energy of non-interacting electrons,

$$T_{\text{s}}[n] = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \langle \psi_i(\mathbf{r}) | \nabla^2 | \psi_i(\mathbf{r}) \rangle. \quad (2.7)$$

The Hartree term and the external potential functional in Eq. (2.6) are expressed as,

$$E_{\text{H}}[n] = \frac{e^2}{2} \int \int d^3\mathbf{r} d^3\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}, \quad (2.8)$$

$$V[n] = \int d^3\mathbf{r} v_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.9)$$

The new term in Eq. (2.6), $E_{\text{xc}}[n]$, is an exchange-correlation energy functional. By comparing to the total energy functional in Eq. (2.3), this term accounts for the correction to the non-interacting energy functional due to many-body interactions. This part of the energy functional contains parameters obtained semi-empirically and gives a fairly good approximation in most general cases.

Kohn-Sham equation of the ground state is obtained through variational principles, as expressed in the second theorem of Hohenberg-Kohn, under the constraint of number of electrons, which is given by,

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} L = \frac{\delta}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} \left(E[n] - \varepsilon_i \left(\int d^3\mathbf{r} n(\mathbf{r}) - N \right) \right), \quad (2.10)$$

and the resulting equation is a one-electron eigenvalue problem, expressed as,

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla_i^2 + v_{\text{eff}} \right] \psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = \varepsilon_i \psi_i(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.11)$$

where ε_i is an energy eigenvalue of the wavefunction $\psi_i(\mathbf{r})$, and the v_{eff} is an effective

potential given by,

$$v_{\text{eff}} = v_{\text{H}} + v_{\text{ext}} + v_{\text{xc}}, \quad (2.12)$$

$$v_{\text{H}} = \frac{\delta E_{\text{H}}[n(\mathbf{r})]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} = \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}, \quad (2.13)$$

$$v_{\text{ext}} = \frac{\delta V[n(\mathbf{r})]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})}, \quad (2.14)$$

$$v_{\text{xc}} = \frac{\delta E_{\text{xc}}[n(\mathbf{r})]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})}. \quad (2.15)$$

The Hartree, v_{H} , and external potential, v_{ext} , can be calculated directly once the electron density, $n(\mathbf{r})$, and the external potential functional, V , are given, while the exchange-correlation potential, v_{xc} , contains several semi-empirical approximations and will be particularly discussed in the next section.

From Eq. (2.13) - (2.15), the effective potential is obtained from the electron density, in which the electron density is obtained from the wavefunction, as shown in Eq. (2.4). On the other hand, the effective potential is required in order to obtain the wavefunction by solving the Kohn-Sham equation. Therefore, the ground state density, $n_0(\mathbf{r})$, is obtained through a self-consistent iteration, which is depicted in Fig. 2.2.

Kohn-Sham equation can be extended into the spin-polarized case by adding an external magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{ext} . In addition, the wavefunction is expressed as a spinor $\Psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = (\psi_i^\uparrow, \psi_i^\downarrow)^T$, and the exchange-correlation potential is a function of the electron's spin. The Kohn-Sham equation has an additional term that represents the interaction between the spin of electrons and the external magnetic fields, and the Kohn-Sham equation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{\text{H}} + v_{\text{xc}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{ext}} \right] \Psi_i(\mathbf{r}) &= \varepsilon_i \Psi_i(\mathbf{r}), \\ \left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{\text{H}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}} \right] \Psi_i(\mathbf{r}) &= \varepsilon_i \Psi_i(\mathbf{r}), \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

where the effective magnetic field, $\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{B}_{\text{ext}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{xc}}$, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is Pauli matrices $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$. In a collinear spin-polarized case, only the B_{eff}^z is non-zero, and this reduces 2×2 matrix problem into two separate equations for the spin-up and spin-down electrons, given as,

$$\begin{aligned} \left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{\text{H}} + B_{\text{eff}}^z \right] \psi_i^\uparrow &= \varepsilon_i^\uparrow \psi_i^\uparrow, \\ \left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{\text{H}} - B_{\text{eff}}^z \right] \psi_i^\downarrow &= \varepsilon_i^\downarrow \psi_i^\downarrow. \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

The B_{xc}^z is obtained from the functional derivative of the exchange-correlation functional, which is expressed as,

$$B_{\text{xc}}^z = \frac{\delta E_{\text{xc}}[n(\mathbf{r}), \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r})]}{\delta m^z(\mathbf{r})}. \quad (2.18)$$

From the wavefunction of spin-up and spin-down obtained from Eq. (2.17), the charge

density and spin moment can be expressed as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 n(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\uparrow}} |\psi_i^{\uparrow}(\mathbf{r})|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\downarrow}} |\psi_i^{\downarrow}(\mathbf{r})|^2, \\
 m^z(\mathbf{r}) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\uparrow}} |\psi_i^{\uparrow}(\mathbf{r})|^2 - \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\downarrow}} |\psi_i^{\downarrow}(\mathbf{r})|^2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.19}$$

In both $n(\mathbf{r})$ and $m^z(\mathbf{r})$, the first term summation represents density of spin-up electrons, while the second summation represents that of spin-down electrons.

Figure 2.2: Flowchart of self-consistent iteration in the density functional theory (DFT) calculations. The charge density, $n(\mathbf{r})$, is first assumed, and the ground-state density is obtained when the charge density of the i -th iteration is consistent with that of the $(i - 1)$ -th iteration.

2.3 Exchange-Correlation Potential

Determining the exchange-correlation potential for solving non-interacting Kohn-Sham equation is crucial in DFT calculation, since this potentials accounts for quantum many-body effects and contains non-Coulomb electron-electron interactions. Various approximations have been proposed to numerically calculate this contribution.

A *local density approximation* (LDA) is one of the approaches to calculate the exchange-correlation potential, where the electron density $n(\mathbf{r})$ is assumed to be slowly varying in space and can be approximated locally as a homogeneous electron gas. The exchange-correlation energy density, ε_{xc} , is a function of a uniform density $n(\mathbf{r})$,

$$E_{xc} \approx \int d^3\mathbf{r} n(\mathbf{r})\varepsilon_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r})). \quad (2.20)$$

The exchange-correlation potential is obtained by a functional derivative of E_{xc} ,

$$\begin{aligned} v_{xc} &= \frac{\delta E_{xc}}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})}, \\ &= \varepsilon_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r})) + n(\mathbf{r}) \frac{d\varepsilon_{xc}[n(\mathbf{r})]}{dn(\mathbf{r})}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

Extension to the spin-polarized case is done by expressing total charge density $n(\mathbf{r})$ into each spin contribution ($n(\mathbf{r}) = n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}) + n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r})$). This is known as *local spin density approximation* (LSDA), where the spin of electrons is taken into account in the LDA. The exchange-correlation functional is given by,

$$E_{xc}[n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow] \approx \int d\mathbf{r} [n^\uparrow + n^\downarrow] \varepsilon_{xc}(n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow). \quad (2.22)$$

Similar assumption is used as in the non-spin-polarized case, i.e., local homogeneous electron density. In the spin-polarized case, the exchange-correlation potential consists of contributions from the two electron spins, expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} v_{xc}^\uparrow &= \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow]}{\delta n^\uparrow} \\ &= \varepsilon_{xc}(n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow) + [n^\uparrow + n^\downarrow] \frac{d\varepsilon_{xc}(n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow)}{dn^\uparrow}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

and similar expression can be obtained for v_{xc}^\downarrow . The form of $\varepsilon_{xc}(n^\uparrow, n^\downarrow)$ has been approximated by several groups, e.g., Hedin-Lundqvist [103], von-Barth-Hedin [104], and Gunnarsson-Lundqvist [105].

While L(S)DA only considers a locally homogeneous electron density, this approximation gives a less accurate description of electrons in the case of rapidly varying electron density in space. Therefore, the *generalized gradient approximation* (GGA) was proposed to treat the non-locality of the electron density. The exchange-correlation functional E_{xc} is expressed as a functional of not only electron density, but also the gradient of electron

density ∇n^σ for each spin denoted with σ , given by,

$$E_{\text{xc}}[n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r})] = \int d^3\mathbf{r} f(n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r}), \nabla n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), \nabla n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r})). \quad (2.24)$$

In this work, GGA with a function $f(n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r}), \nabla n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}), \nabla n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r}))$ is employed and was proposed by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) [106] for its versatility on magnetic systems. Additionally, both the LDA and GGA fail to predict several experimental results for the localized and strongly correlated systems, and thus, another correction has to be taken into account, e.g., GGA+U method, which will be discussed in section 2.5.

2.4 Full-Potential Linearized Augmented Plane-Wave (FLAPW)

2.4.1 Eigenvalue Problem

In previous section, it has been shown that the total energy functional can be re-expressed in the form of an eigenvalue problem for non-interacting electrons with the variational principles, which allows numerical calculations to be performed. In particular, an eigenvalue problem is a secular problem solved by Rayleigh-Ritz principle [107], which leads to the diagonalization of the Hamiltonian matrix.

To obtain the matrix representation of the Hamiltonian, the basis function of $\psi(\mathbf{r})$ has to be defined in the first place. In the simplest case for a system with periodicity in real space, the Bloch function with a periodic boundary condition is invoked,

$$\psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_j C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.25)$$

where \mathbf{k}_j is a shorthand for $\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}_j$, σ is the spin index, b is a band index, $C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma$ are the expansion coefficients, and $\phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r})$ is an orthonormal basis function. In theory, the sum extends over all possible reciprocal lattice vector \mathbf{G}_j . However, it is numerically practical to truncate the expansion up to a *cut-off* radius, $|\mathbf{k}_{\text{max}}|$.

The Hamiltonian matrix is obtained by substituting this basis function into Eq. (2.11) (in collinear spin polarized case, Eq. (2.17)) and applying the variational principles for each basis function. In Dirac notation, this procedure yields,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma | H_{\text{KS}} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma \rangle - \varepsilon_{i,b}^\sigma \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma \rangle &= 0, \\ \sum_j C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma H^{j',j} - \varepsilon_{i,b}^\sigma S^{j',j} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

where,

$$H^{j',j} = \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma | H_{\text{KS}} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma \rangle = \int d^3\mathbf{r} \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^{\sigma*}(\mathbf{r}) \left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + v_{\text{eff}} \right] \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.27)$$

$$S^{j',j} = \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma \rangle = \int d^3\mathbf{r} \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^{\sigma*}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.28)$$

are the elements of the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian and overlap matrices, respectively. If one

type of Bloch function is used for the entire region of the unit cell, the overlap matrix is diagonal due to the orthogonality of its basis function $\phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r})$. However, the use of augmented basis functions generally gives non-zero off-diagonal matrix elements in the overlap matrix, as we shall see in the case of linearized augmented plane-wave basis.

The expansion coefficient $C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma$ is obtained from the diagonalization of Eq. (2.26), and the charge density $n(\mathbf{r})$ is calculated using these expansion coefficients. Then, the new Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian matrix is solved using this charge density as input for the effective potential. This process is done iteratively until the charge density converges, i.e., the charge density that is used to generate the effective potential is approximately equal to the charge density produced from the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian matrix diagonalization, resulting in a self-consistent process.

2.4.2 Linearized Augmented Plane-Wave (LAPW) Basis

In 1937, Slater [108] realized that due to the singularity of the crystal potential at the nucleus, plane-wave electron wavefunction rapidly varies near the nucleus which results in slow convergence. Initially, employing a calculation with a large cut-off wavevector $\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}_j$ was a solution to this problem, but computationally it was not practical and required a huge computational cost. For this reason, fewer basis functions were preferred for fast computational time while still maintaining accurate description of the materials.

To solve this, augmented plane-wave (APW) method was proposed, which divides the space into two regions: (1) a spherical muffin tin region with a particular radius (e.g., R_α for α atom) centered at each atom site, and (2) an interstitial region in the remaining space between atoms. The muffin tin sphere radii of the atom sites are chosen to maximize all possible space that the spheres can occupy, while keeping multiple muffin tin spheres from overlapping. The effective potential in the muffin tin sphere is approximately spherically symmetric, while it is constant in the interstitial region. Solution of the Schrödinger equation in a constant potential is a plane-wave, while it is a product of spherical harmonics and a radial function under a spherically symmetric potential. Therefore, the basis function is separated depending on the region it belongs to. The single wavefunction $\psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma$ has the form of

$$\psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma = \sum_j^{\mathbf{k}_{max}} C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.29)$$

where,

$$\phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}}, & \mathbf{r} \in \text{interstitial} \\ \sum_{\alpha,l,m} a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} u_l(r_\alpha, E_l) Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}_\alpha), & \mathbf{r} \in \text{muffin tin of atom } \alpha \end{cases} \quad (2.30)$$

with Ω is volume of the unit cell, l, m are quantum numbers, $Y_{l,m}$ are spherical harmonics, which is a solution of angular part of spherical Schrödinger equation, and u_l are the radial

function, which is a solution of radial part with energy parameter E_l , given by

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} + V(r) - E_l \right] r u_l(r) = 0. \quad (2.31)$$

We dropped the spin index σ in the expression for the sake of simplicity. $a_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j}$ is determined from the continuous boundary condition of the wavefunction between the muffin tin region and the interstitial region on the surface of the spheres. For convenience, the plane-wave expansion is applied to re-express the plane-wave as a linear combination of spherical harmonics, which describes a plane-wave at point \mathbf{r} in terms of a linear combination of spherical harmonics with a center located at $(0, 0)$. Therefore, if the α atom is shifted ($\mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}$) from the global $(0, 0)$, the expansion at point \mathbf{r} from $\mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}$, according to Fig. 2.3, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}} &= e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot (\mathbf{r}_{0\alpha} + \mathbf{r}_\alpha)}, \\ &= e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} 4\pi \sum_{l,m} i^l Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{k}_j) j_l(k_j r_\alpha) Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}_\alpha), \end{aligned} \quad (2.32)$$

where $j_l(k_j r_\alpha)$ is a Bessel function. Due to the orthogonality of spherical harmonics, each basis function inside the muffin tin sphere of $\phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}(\mathbf{r})$ in Eq. (2.30) has to be equal with the basis function of the expanded plane-wave given by Eq. (2.32) at surface of the sphere, $\mathbf{r}_\alpha = R_\alpha \hat{r}_\alpha$, which yields to,

$$a_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} 4\pi i^l Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{k}_j) \frac{j_l(k_j R_\alpha)}{u_l(R_\alpha, E_l)}. \quad (2.33)$$

In this scheme, E_l is taken as a fixed parameter for the APW basis. However, this presents a new problem since the resulting energy band $\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},b}$ from the matrix diagonalization has to be matched with E_l , which is a fixed parameters in radial function u_l , in other words, it misses a variational freedom. The Hamiltonian H_{KS} is now a function of not only \mathbf{k} , but also the energy band itself $H(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},b})$, which introduces the non-linearity in the process and demands more computational cost.

Figure 2.3: The space is divided into two regions: (I) muffin tin sphere region where the spherical harmonics and radial functions are used as the basis functions, and (II) the interstitial region where the plane-waves are used. The position coordinate relative to the global origin \mathbf{r} , the position relative to the center of muffin tin sphere α \mathbf{r}_α , and the position of the muffin tin center in the global coordinate $\mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}$ are also shown in the figure.

Another difficulty arises from the real shape of the potential in the interstitial region, which is a non-spherical potential rather than just a constant potential as assumed in APW [109, 110]. By the continuous boundary condition of potential at the surface of muffin tin sphere, non-constant potential in the interstitial would affect the orbitals characters inside the sphere, in other words the orbitals now experience different effective potential. Hence, the energy parameters E_l is no longer given by fitting the E_l to the band energy.

In 1975, Andersen [111], Koelling, and Arbman [112] proposed a linearized augmented plane-wave (LAPW) to overcome the problem regarding the APW. The idea was to expand the radial function u_l as a function of energy E , deviating from the energy parameter E_l with the Taylor expansion, which is given by,

$$u_l(r, E) = u_l(r, E_l) + (E - E_l)\dot{u}_l(r, E) + O((E - E_l)^2) \quad (2.34)$$

where \dot{u}_l is the energy derivative of radial function ($\partial u_l / \partial E$), and $O((E - E_l)^2)$ denotes the deviation introduced by second-order energy difference. Therefore, the deviation from energy parameter E_l introduced in the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian matrix with the LAPW basis and the calculated band energies will be fourth-order smaller than that with the APW basis, and it is sufficient to treat all valence bands by a single energy parameter.

The basis function of the LAPW are obtained by adding the energy derivative of radial function u_l for the basis inside the muffin tin sphere,

$$\phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}}, & \mathbf{r} \in \text{interstitial}, \\ \sum_{\alpha, l, m} \left[a_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} u_l(r_\alpha, E_l) + b_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} \dot{u}_l(r_\alpha, E_l) \right] Y_{l, m}(\hat{r}_\alpha), & \mathbf{r} \in \text{muffin tin } \alpha. \end{cases} \quad (2.35)$$

In addition, the radial function u_l satisfies orthonormality for every quantum number l ,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_l | u_{l'} \rangle_{R_\alpha} &= \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 u_l^2(r_\alpha) \\ &= \delta_{l, l'}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.36)$$

Orthogonality between u_l and \dot{u}_l can be obtained by calculating derivative of the u_l orthonormality with respect to the E_l in Eq. (2.36), as given by,

$$\langle u_l | \dot{u}_{l'} \rangle_{R_\alpha} = 0. \quad (2.37)$$

This proves the validity of adding \dot{u}_l in the basis function of LAPW due to its orthogonality with u_l .

The expansion coefficient $a_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j}$ and $b_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j}$ in Eq. (2.35) are obtained from the continuous boundary condition of plane-wave and spherical wavefunctions at the surface of muffin tin sphere, given by,

$$\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{\Omega}} i^l e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} Y_{l, m}^*(\hat{k}_j) j_l(k_j R_\alpha) = a_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} u_l(R_\alpha, E_l) + b_{l, m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} \dot{u}_l(R_\alpha, E_l), \quad (2.38)$$

$$\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{\Omega}} i^l e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_j) k_j j_l'(k_j R_\alpha) = a_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} u_l'(R_\alpha, E_l) + b_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} \dot{u}_l'(R_\alpha, E_l). \quad (2.39)$$

Solving Eq. (2.38) and Eq. (2.39) for the expansion coefficients yields,

$$\begin{aligned} a_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} &= e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} \frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{\Omega W}} \left(\dot{u}_l'(R_\alpha, E_l) j_l(k_j R_\alpha) - \dot{u}_l(R_\alpha, E_l) k_j j_l'(k_j R_\alpha) \right) i^l Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_j), \\ b_{l,m}^{\alpha, \mathbf{k}_j} &= e^{i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} \frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{\Omega W}} \left(-u_l'(R_\alpha, E_l) j_l(k_j R_\alpha) + u_l(R_\alpha, E_l) k_j j_l'(k_j R_\alpha) \right) i^l Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_j), \end{aligned} \quad (2.40)$$

where the Wronskian, W , is given by

$$W = u_l(R_\alpha) \dot{u}_l'(R_\alpha) - u_l'(R_\alpha) \dot{u}_l(R_\alpha). \quad (2.41)$$

2.4.3 Hamiltonian Matrix Elements of LAPW

The Hamiltonian and the overlap matrix in the LAPW framework are divided into two parts, one from the interstitial region, and another from inside the muffin tin spheres, as given by,

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_I + \hat{H}_{\text{MT}} \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{S} = \hat{S}_I + \hat{S}_{\text{MT}}, \quad (2.42)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{MT}} &= \sum_{\alpha} \hat{H}_{\text{MT}}^{\alpha}, \\ \hat{S}_{\text{MT}} &= \sum_{\alpha} \hat{S}_{\text{MT}}^{\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.43)$$

In each of the muffin tin sphere, the effective potential is divided into spherical, $\hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^{\alpha}$, and non-spherical parts, $\hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^{\alpha}$ which can be expressed as a linear combination of spherical harmonics $Y_{l,m}$, as given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{\text{MT}}^{\alpha} &= \hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^{\alpha} + \hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^{\alpha}, \\ \hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^{\alpha} &= \sum_{l \neq 0, m} V_l^{\alpha}(r_\alpha) Y_{l,m}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

The calculation of interstitial and muffin-tin regions will be treated separately.

Muffin tin Hamiltonian matrix

The element of Hamiltonian matrix in the muffin tin sphere, $\hat{H}_{\text{MT}}^{\alpha}$, is obtained from both spherical and non-spherical parts of the muffin-tin Hamiltonian. On the basis of LAPW, the element of the Hamiltonian matrix in the muffin tin sphere is given by,

$$H_{\text{MT}}^{j,j'} = \sum_{\alpha} \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^{\alpha} | \hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^{\alpha} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}}^{\alpha} \rangle + \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^{\alpha} | \hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^{\alpha} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}}^{\alpha} \rangle. \quad (2.45)$$

The spherical part of the muffin tin Hamiltonian is defined in terms of radial part of the spherically symmetric Schrödinger equation, $\hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^{\alpha}$, in Eq. (2.31) and the derivative of

radial part with respect to then energy, E_l , which is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^\alpha u_l^\alpha &= E_l u_l^\alpha, \\ \hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^\alpha \dot{u}_l^\alpha &= E_l \dot{u}_l^\alpha + u_l^\alpha.\end{aligned}\quad (2.46)$$

Using the properties of the $\hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^\alpha$, the elements of the spherical part of the muffin tin Hamiltonian matrix are written as,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\alpha | \hat{H}_{\text{sp}}^\alpha | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}}^\alpha \rangle_{R_\alpha} &= \sum_{l,m} \sum_{l',m'} \left(a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* a_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} E_l \delta_{l,l'} \delta_{m,m'} \\ &+ \left(a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* b_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \delta_{l,l'} \delta_{m,m'} \\ &+ \left(b_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* b_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} E_l N_l \delta_{l,l'} \delta_{m,m'},\end{aligned}\quad (2.47)$$

where N_l is defined as,

$$N_l = \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 (\dot{u}_l)^\alpha. \quad (2.48)$$

The non-spherical contributions to the muffin tin Hamiltonian matrix, $\hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^\alpha$, are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\alpha | \hat{V}_{\text{ns}}^\alpha | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}}^\alpha \rangle &= \sum_{l,m} \sum_{l',m'} \sum_{l'',m''} \left(a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* a_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,uu} G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'} \\ &+ \left(a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* b_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,ui} G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'} \\ &+ \left(b_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* a_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,iu} G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'} \\ &+ \left(b_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* b_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,i\dot{u}} G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'},\end{aligned}\quad (2.49)$$

where $G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'}$ is called Gaunt coefficient, and the radial integrations are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}G_{l,l'',l'}^{m,m'',m'} &= \int d\Omega Y_{l,m}^* Y_{l'',m''} Y_{l',m'}, \\ I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,uu} &= \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 u_l^\alpha(r_\alpha) u_{l'}^\alpha(r_\alpha) V_{l''}^\alpha(r_\alpha), \\ I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,ui} &= \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 u_l^\alpha(r_\alpha) \dot{u}_{l'}^\alpha(r_\alpha) V_{l''}^\alpha(r_\alpha), \\ I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,iu} &= \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 \dot{u}_l^\alpha(r_\alpha) u_{l'}^\alpha(r_\alpha) V_{l''}^\alpha(r_\alpha), \\ I_{l,l'',l'}^{\alpha,i\dot{u}} &= \int_0^{R_\alpha} dr_\alpha r_\alpha^2 \dot{u}_l^\alpha(r_\alpha) \dot{u}_{l'}^\alpha(r_\alpha) V_{l''}^\alpha(r_\alpha).\end{aligned}\quad (2.50)$$

The overlap matrix element in muffin-tin sphere α is given by,

$$\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j}^\alpha | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}}^\alpha \rangle_{R_\alpha} = \sum_{l,m} \sum_{l',m'} \left(a_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* a_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \delta_{l,l'} \delta_{m,m'} + \left(b_{l,m}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_j} \right)^* b_{l',m'}^{\alpha,\mathbf{k}_{j'}} N_l \delta_{l,l'} \delta_{m,m'}, \quad (2.51)$$

Interstitial Hamiltonian matrix

In the interstitial region, the Hamiltonian and overlap matrix elements are constructed using the plane-wave basis functions of LAPW,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j} | \hat{H}_I | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \rangle_I &= \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_I d^3\mathbf{r} e^{-i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}} \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r}) \right) e^{i\mathbf{k}_{j'} \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \\ \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \rangle_I &= \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_I d^3\mathbf{r} e^{-i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}} e^{i\mathbf{k}_{j'} \cdot \mathbf{r}}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.52)$$

If the integration is performed over the entire unit cell, the Hamiltonian and overlap matrix elements are straightforward to calculate, where the overlap matrix and the kinetic part of the Hamiltonian matrix elements would be diagonal in the matrices. However, the separation of regions in space into interstitial and muffin tin spheres with different basis functions in each region poses an additional complication to the integration.

One intuitive trick to tackle this difficulty is to use a step function, where the value is zero inside the muffin tin sphere and unity in the interstitial region, as such,

$$\Theta(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{r} \in \text{Interstitial} \\ 0, & \mathbf{r} \in \text{Muffin tin spheres} \end{cases}\quad (2.53)$$

Adding this step-function into the integration and extending the integration over the entire unit cell, the Hamiltonian and overlap matrix elements are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j} | \hat{H}_I | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \rangle_I &= \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_{u.c.} d^3\mathbf{r} e^{-i\mathbf{k}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}} \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r}) \right) \Theta(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{k}_{j'} \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \\ \langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j} | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \rangle_I &= \frac{1}{\Omega} \int_{u.c.} d^3\mathbf{r} \Theta(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i(\mathbf{G}_j - \mathbf{G}_{j'}) \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \\ &= \Theta_{j-j'}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.54)$$

The overlap matrix elements are now seen as a Fourier transform of a step-function, and the Hamiltonian matrix is now written as,

$$\langle \phi_{\mathbf{k}_j} | \hat{H}_I | \phi_{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \rangle_I = \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}_j|^2 \Theta_{j-j'} + (V\Theta)_{j-j'}\quad (2.55)$$

where the Fourier coefficient of step function Θ_j and $V\Theta_j$ are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\Theta_j &= \delta_{\mathbf{G}_j, 0} - \sum_{\alpha} e^{-i\mathbf{G}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}_{0\alpha}} \frac{4\pi(R_{\alpha})^3}{\Omega} \frac{j_1(G_j R_{\alpha})}{G_j R_{\alpha}}, \\ (V\Theta)_j &= \int_{u.c.} d^3\mathbf{r} V(\mathbf{r}) \Theta(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\mathbf{G}_j \cdot \mathbf{r}}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.56)$$

2.4.4 Full-Potential Method

The separation of space into two regions, i.e. muffin tin spheres and interstitial, gives a quite good approximation for close-packed metals. However, this approximation often fails

to describe open structure systems, e.g., semiconductors, perovskites, solids with reduced symmetry, or system with localized electrons. This is due to that the density, $n(\mathbf{r})$, suffers from rapid variation near the atomic core, which results in slow Fourier transform convergence of the Coulomb potential in the reciprocal space, while the long-range nature of the density in real space complicates the direct calculation of the Coulomb potential. A full-potential LAPW (FLAPW), developed based on a pseudocharge method by Weinert [113], is suitable for strongly correlated systems and structures with low symmetry. The fundamental idea behind this method was based on the fact that the interstitial density is a fairly smooth function and is connected to the density inside the muffin tin spheres by appropriate boundary conditions, i.e., Dirichlet boundary value problem on the surface of the muffin tin spheres. Therefore, the method consists of two steps, where the potential in the interstitial is obtained first, and those in the muffin tin spheres are obtained using the boundary value problem from that in the interstitial.

The potential at any point outside the muffin tin spheres generated by local charge distribution inside muffin tin sphere is determined by its multiple moment $q_{l,m}$,

$$V(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^{m=l} \frac{4\pi}{2l+1} \frac{q_{l,m}}{r^{l+1}} Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}), \quad (2.57)$$

where the multipole moment $q_{l,m}$ is given by,

$$q_{l,m} = \int_{\text{MT}} d^3\mathbf{r} Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{r}) r^l n(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.58)$$

The charge density $n(\mathbf{r})$ can be separated into interstitial part and inside muffin tin part,

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = n_I(\mathbf{r})\Theta(\mathbf{r} \in I) + \sum_{\alpha} n_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})\Theta(\mathbf{r} \in MT_{\alpha}). \quad (2.59)$$

This charge density, however, leads to a slowly converging Fourier expansion due to rapid variation near the nuclei, while the Fourier representation of charge density in the interstitial region quickly converges.

The charge density in Eq. (2.59) can be rewritten as,

$$\begin{aligned} n(\mathbf{r}) &= n_I(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{\alpha} [n_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) - n_I(\mathbf{r})] \Theta(\mathbf{r} \in MT_{\alpha}), \\ &= n_I(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{\alpha} \tilde{n}_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) \Theta(\mathbf{r} \in MT_{\alpha}), \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

where the charge density in the interstitial is now expanded into the entire space, including the muffin tin sphere, and the term inside the square brackets is called pseudocharge density $\tilde{n}_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$. This means that once we obtain the pseudocharge density $\tilde{n}_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$, the real charge density inside the muffin tin sphere $n_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$ can be obtained from both pseudocharge density and interstitial charge density. Details of the mathematical methods to obtain pseudocharge \tilde{n}_{α} are referred to [113]. Then, the potential inside the muffin tin is a

boundary-value problem, with a solution consisting Green function,

$$V_{MT}^\alpha(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{MT_\alpha} d^3r' n_\alpha(\mathbf{r}')G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') - \frac{R_\alpha^2}{4\pi} \oint_{S^\alpha} d\Omega' V_I(\mathbf{r}') \frac{\partial G}{\partial n'}, \quad (2.61)$$

where S^α denotes the surface of the muffin tin sphere α , and the Green function is given by,

$$G^\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = 4\pi \sum_{l,m} \frac{Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}')Y_{l,m}(\hat{r})}{2l+1} \frac{r_{<}^l}{r_{>}^{l+1}} \left(1 - \left(\frac{r_{>}}{R_\alpha} \right)^{2l+1} \right), \quad (2.62)$$

where $r_{>} = \max(|\mathbf{r}|, |\mathbf{r}'|)$ and $r_{<} = \min(|\mathbf{r}|, |\mathbf{r}'|)$, and the normal derivative of Green function is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial G}{\partial n'} &= \frac{\partial G}{\partial r'} \Big|_{r'=R_\alpha} \\ &= -\frac{4\pi}{R_\alpha^2} \sum_{l,m} \left(\frac{r}{R_\alpha} \right)^l Y_{l,m}^*(\hat{r}') Y_{l,m}(\hat{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.63)$$

Note that, in Eq. (2.61) we used the actual charge density inside the sphere, and the potential is now correct for every region in space.

2.5 Hubbard Correction for Strongly Correlated Electrons

Although conventional exchange-correlation potentials, e.g., LDA and GGA, produce excellent descriptions for ground-state properties of a wide range of materials, such approximations are still inadequate to explain several ground-state properties of strongly correlated systems, where transition metals or rare-earth metal ions are usually present in the system. In these systems, electrons in d (or f) orbitals are localized near the atoms and do not form an overlap with surrounding ligands to form a bond, in contrast to s and p orbitals. Under the LDA and GGA, these orbitals may suffer from self-interaction error that leads to incorrect energy band gaps, magnetic moments, lattice constants, and other ground-state properties.

To improve the calculation for electrons in localized orbitals with strong Coulomb interactions, one can extend the energy functional to include a correction, and this method is called DFT+U [114]. This method is based on a Hubbard model [115, 116], where the electron-electron Coulomb repulsion in a certain atom is parameterized by a Hubbard energy. Anisimov et.al. [114] improved the DFT by adding an orbital-dependent correction term to the Kohn-Sham energy functional, which takes the form of two-electron interaction terms as in the Hatree-Fock method. In this study, the implementation of DFT+U into the FLAPW was employed, following the works by Shick et.al. [117].

The DFT+U total energy functional is taken in form of,

$$E_{\text{total}}[n(\mathbf{r}), \hat{n}] = E_{\text{DFT}}[n(\mathbf{r})] + E_{\text{ee}}[\hat{n}] - E_{\text{dc}}[\hat{n}], \quad (2.64)$$

where E_{DFT} is total energy functional under the LDA or GGA approximation only, $n(\mathbf{r})$

are electron density for each spin ($n^\uparrow(\mathbf{r})$ and $n^\downarrow(\mathbf{r})$), E_{ee} is the energy functional of electron-electron interaction, and E_{dc} is a "double-counting" functional, which acts as a correction to cancel the double-counting for electron-electron interaction that already exists in E_{DFT} . Both new terms are energy functionals of a density matrix \hat{n} of localized orbitals in the atom of interest.

E_{ee} is taken from the multiband Hubbard model for $d(f)$ electrons, as given by,

$$E_{ee} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{m_1, m_2, \\ m_3, m_4}} \sum_{\sigma, \sigma'} n_{m_1, m_2}^\sigma (\langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_2, m_4 \rangle - \langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_2, m_4 \rangle \delta_{\sigma, \sigma'}) n_{m_3, m_4}^{\sigma'}, \quad (2.65)$$

where V_{ee} is an effective on-site "Coulomb" interaction, $\langle | \rangle$ indicates integrals over angular part of space, and n_{m_1, m_2}^σ represents the occupation matrix of on-site $d(f)$ orbitals in spin-orbital space. The matrix element of electron-electron interaction in the atomic limit is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_2, m_4 \rangle &= \sum_k a_k(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) F_k, \\ a_k(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) &= \frac{4\pi}{2k+1} \sum_{q=-k}^k \langle Y_{lm_1} | Y_{kq} | Y_{lm_2} \rangle \langle Y_{lm_3} | Y_{kq}^* | Y_{lm_4} \rangle, \\ F_k &= \int_0^\infty dr_1 dr_2 r_1^2 r_2^2 R_{nl}^2(r_1) R_{nl}^2(r_2) \frac{r_1^l}{r_2^{k+1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

In these equations, the k index for quantum numbers covers $0 \geq k \geq 2l$, $|Y_{l,m}\rangle$ is the spherical harmonics of localized orbital of interest, (i.e. d and f orbitals), and F_k are Slater integrals with $r_<$ and $r_>$ represents $\min(r_1, r_2)$ and $\max(r_1, r_2)$ respectively. The integrals of three spherical harmonics are the Gaunt coefficients, as in Eq. (2.50). Note that, in the case of $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$, the first term in Eq. (2.65) cancels the second term.

The double-counting term is taken so that it satisfies an 'atomic-like' limit of the DFT energy, as given by,

$$E_{dc}[\hat{n}] = \frac{U}{2} n(n-1) - \frac{J}{2} \sum_\sigma n^\sigma (n^\sigma - 1), \quad (2.67)$$

where Hubbard energy U and exchange constants J are written as,

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \frac{1}{(2l+1)^2} \sum_{m_1, m_3} \langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_1, m_3 \rangle, \\ J &= U - \frac{1}{2l(2l+1)} \sum_{m_1, m_3} (\langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_1, m_3 \rangle - \langle m_1, m_3 | V_{ee} | m_3, m_1 \rangle), \end{aligned} \quad (2.68)$$

and $n^\sigma = \text{Tr}(\hat{n}^\sigma) = \text{Tr}(n_{m, m'}^\sigma)$, $n = \sum_\sigma n^\sigma$ are spin and total the occupational numbers of $d(f)$ on-site respectively.

In the case of d electrons, which is the focus of this research, F_0 , F_2 , and F_4 are the

only Slater integrals needed to identify on-site U and J in Hartree-Fock-like atomic limit.

$$\begin{aligned} U &= F_0, \\ J &= \frac{F_2 + F_4}{14}, \\ \frac{F_2}{F_4} &\approx 0.625. \end{aligned} \quad (2.69)$$

In addition, the exchange interaction parameters J is taken to be 0 and the Hubbard energy U is replaced by an effective Hubbard energy $U_{\text{eff}} = U - J$ [118].

2.5.1 Implementation to FLAPW Method

The spin density of electrons with LAPW basis functions inside muffin tin spheres Eq. (2.35) is given by,

$$n^\sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k},b} f_{\mathbf{k},b} |\psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma|^2 \quad (2.70)$$

with $f_{\mathbf{k},b}$ is the occupation of the state and b is a band index. The spin-density, projected onto the Y_{lm} subspace for the LAPW basis functions, is written as,

$$\begin{aligned} n_{lm,l'm'}^\sigma &= \sum_{\mathbf{k},b} f_{\mathbf{k},b} \sum_{\mathbf{G}_{j'},\mathbf{G}_j} C_{\mathbf{k}_{j'},b}^{\sigma,*} C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma \\ &\times \int dr r^2 \left[a_{l',m'}^{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} u_{l'}^\sigma(r_i) + b_{l',m'}^{\mathbf{k}_{j'}} \dot{u}_{l'}^\sigma(r_i) \right]^* \left[a_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_j} u_l^\sigma(r_i) + b_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_j} \dot{u}_l^\sigma(r_i) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.71)$$

Using the property in Eq. (2.36) and Eq. (2.37) and keeping only the diagonal terms, the density matrix element is rewritten as,

$$n_{m,m'}^\sigma = \sum_{\mathbf{k},b} f_{\mathbf{k},b} \sum_{\mathbf{G}_{j'},\mathbf{G}_j} C_{\mathbf{k}_{j'},b}^{\sigma,*} C_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^\sigma \left[a_{l,m'}^{\mathbf{k}_{j'}*} a_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_j} + b_{l,m'}^{\mathbf{k}_{j'}*} b_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_j} \langle \dot{u}_l | \dot{u}_l \rangle \right]. \quad (2.72)$$

The density matrix element in Eq. (2.72) can be projected into the spherical and radial basis functions, as given by,

$$n_{m,m'}^\sigma = \sum_{\mathbf{k},b} f_{\mathbf{k},b} \left[\langle u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m} | \psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma \rangle \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma | u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle + \frac{1}{\langle \dot{u}_l | \dot{u}_l \rangle} \langle \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m} | \psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma \rangle \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma | \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle \right]. \quad (2.73)$$

To obtain the Kohn-Sham equation in the presence of correction terms, a functional derivative is performed on the total energy functional in Eq. (2.64) with respect to $\psi_{\mathbf{k}_j,b}^*$,

$$\frac{\delta E}{\delta \psi_i^{\sigma*}} - \frac{\delta \sum e_j f_j \langle \psi_j^\sigma | \psi_j^\sigma \rangle}{\delta \psi_i^{\sigma*}} = 0, \quad (2.74)$$

where $i = \{\mathbf{k}, b\}$, and this gives us,

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + v_{\text{eff}}^\sigma \right] \psi_i^\sigma(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{m,m'} V_{m,m'}^\sigma \frac{\delta n_{m,m'}^\sigma}{\delta \psi_i^{\sigma*}} = e_i^s \psi_i^\sigma(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.75)$$

The terms inside square brackets are the Kohn-Sham equation with conventional one-particle exchange-correlation potentials, i.e., LDA or GGA. $V_{m,m'}^\sigma$ acts only on the $Y_{l,m}$ subspace ($d(f)$ orbitals) of the atom of interest and is given by,

$$V_{m,m'}^\sigma = \sum_{p,q,\sigma'} (\langle m, p | V_{ee} | m', q \rangle - \langle m, p | V_{ee} | q, m' \rangle \delta_{\sigma,\sigma'}) n_{p,q}^{\sigma'} - \delta_{m,m'} U \left(n - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \delta_{m,m'} J \left(n^\sigma - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (2.76)$$

and using Eq. (2.73), the density matrix derivative with respect to the wavefunction in Eq. (2.75) is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta n_{m,m'}^\sigma}{\delta \psi_i^{*,\sigma}} &= \langle u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m} | \psi_i^\sigma \rangle \langle u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle + \frac{1}{\langle \dot{u}_l | \dot{u}_l \rangle} \langle \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m} | \psi_i^\sigma \rangle \langle \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle, \\ &= \left[|u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle \langle u_l^\sigma Y_{l,m}| + \frac{1}{\langle \dot{u}_l | \dot{u}_l \rangle} | \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m'} \rangle \langle \dot{u}_l^\sigma Y_{l,m}| \right] | \psi_i^\sigma \rangle, \\ &= P_{m'm}^\sigma | \psi_i^\sigma \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (2.77)$$

where $P_{mm'}^\sigma$ is the element of the projection matrix of the LAPW basis inside the muffin tin spheres.

2.5.2 Second Variation Procedure

To solve Kohn-Sham equation with $+U$ correction in Eq. (2.75), second variations approach is employed [117]. First, an auxiliary orthogonal basis set is defined as a solution of the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian matrix without the Hubbard correction,

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + v_{\text{eff}}^\sigma \right] \varphi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma \varphi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.78)$$

Here, the density formed from $\varphi_{\mathbf{k},b}^\sigma$ does not directly enter the calculation of v_{eff}^σ in the next self-consistent iteration. Instead, an intermediate self-consistent loop is performed to account for the Hubbard correction, where the Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian orthogonal basis, $\varphi_{\mathbf{k},b}$, forms a new orthogonal basis set for the DFT+U, $\psi_{\mathbf{k},i}$, as expressed as,

$$| \psi_{\mathbf{k},i} \rangle = \sum_j d_j^i | \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j} \rangle. \quad (2.79)$$

Using this new basis set, the Kohn-Sham equation in Eq. (2.75) is rewritten as,

$$\sum_j \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},j} d_j^i | \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j} \rangle + \sum_j d_j^i \sum_{mm'} V_{m,m'} P_{m',m} | \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j} \rangle = e_i \sum_j d_j^i | \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j} \rangle. \quad (2.80)$$

Considering the orthogonality of $\langle \varphi_i | \varphi_j \rangle = \delta_{i,j}$, and applying dot-product with a ket $\langle \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j'} |$ to the Eq. (2.80), the second variation Hamiltonian matrix element takes the form of,

$$H_{j',j}^\sigma = \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},j} \delta_{j',j} + \langle \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j'} | \hat{V} \hat{P} | \varphi_{\mathbf{k},j} \rangle. \quad (2.81)$$

To summarize, the flowchart of solving Kohn-Sham equation under $+U$ correction by second variations procedures is shown in Fig. 2.4. The self-consistent calculation is now modified to be,

1. solve Kohn-Sham equation without $+U$ correction (Eq. (2.78)) and obtain an orthogonal auxiliary basis set φ_j ,
2. use the orthogonal auxiliary basis set and the eigenvalues of Eq. (2.78), solve the new Hamiltonian matrix Eq. (2.81) and obtain the expansion coefficient d_j^i ,
3. form the charge and spin density from the expansion coefficient, d_j^i , of Eq. (2.79) to calculate v_{eff}^σ in the one-electron Kohn-Sham equation.

Figure 2.4: Flowchart of second variations schemes for DFT+U.

2.6 Scalar Relativistic Approximation

For materials containing light atoms, a standard DFT calculation provides a well description of ground state properties. However, for materials containing heavy atoms where d or f orbitals electrons have significant roles in the ground states properties, the non-relativistic Schrödinger equation fails due to the relativistic motion of its electrons near the nuclei, in addition to its localized properties. Therefore, the electrons in the muffin tin spheres should be treated relativistically, while those in the interstitial or vacuum can still be treated non-relativistically.

To account for the relativistic effect inside the muffin tin spheres, the Kohn-Sham equation is extended to the many-body Dirac equation, which results in a single-particle Dirac-like equation known as the Kohn-Sham-Dirac equation [119],

$$\{c\hat{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{p} + (\hat{\beta} - 1)mc^2 + \mathbb{1}_{4 \times 4}v_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r})\}\psi_i = \varepsilon\psi_i, \quad (2.82)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ are 4×4 matrices, given by,

$$\hat{\alpha} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \hat{\sigma}_{\mathbf{r}} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{\mathbf{r}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbb{1}_{4 \times 4} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{\mathbb{1}}_{2 \times 2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.83)$$

and the Pauli and identity matrices are,

$$\hat{\sigma}_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.84)$$

with m and c are the electron mass and the speed of light, respectively, and \mathbf{p} is the momentum operator, $\mathbf{p} = -i\hbar\nabla$. In the relativistic Dirac equation, new and convenient quantum numbers κ and μ are introduced and replacing the non-relativistic quantum numbers l , m , and s . The κ is an eigenvalue of operator \hat{K}

$$\hat{K} = \hat{\beta}(\hat{\sigma} \cdot \hat{l}), \quad (2.85)$$

while μ is an eigenvalue of total angular momentum $\hat{\mathbf{j}}$ (and \hat{j}_z),

$$\hat{\mathbf{j}} = \hat{\mathbf{l}} + \hat{\mathbf{s}} \quad (2.86)$$

The eigenstates of Eq. (2.82) for a spherically symmetric potential inside the muffin tin sphere are expressed in $\kappa\mu$ space [120] as follows,

$$\psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = \psi_{\kappa\mu}(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{pmatrix} g_{\kappa}(\mathbf{r})\chi_{\kappa\mu} \\ -if_{\kappa}(\mathbf{r})\sigma_{\mathbf{r}}\chi_{\kappa\mu} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.87)$$

The spin angular, $\chi_{\kappa\mu}$, are eigenfunctions of $\hat{\mathbf{j}}$, \hat{j}_z , \hat{K} , and S^2 operators with eigenvalues of j , μ , κ , and $s = 1/2$, respectively. It is convenient to have the quantum numbers expressed

in l , m , and s quantum numbers, since the non-relativistic basis functions of the DFT are expressed in these quantum numbers. Mathematically, this translates into expressing the $\kappa\mu$ into sum of product of spherical harmonics lm and Pauli spinors s , where the coefficient expansions are basically the Clebsh-Gordan coefficients. $g_\kappa(\mathbf{r})$ and $f_\kappa(\mathbf{r})$ are called as large and small components, respectively, both of which satisfy these coupled equations,

$$\begin{aligned} f'_\kappa(r) &= \frac{1}{c} (v_{\text{eff}} - E) g_\kappa(r) + \left(\frac{\kappa - 1}{r} \right) f_\kappa(r), \\ g'_\kappa(r) &= \left(\frac{\kappa + 1}{r} \right) g_\kappa(r) + 2Mc f_\kappa(r). \end{aligned} \quad (2.88)$$

Here, the relativistic mass M is defined as $M = m + (E - v_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}))/2c^2$, and the primed terms indicate derivative with respect to radius, r , i.e., $f'_\kappa = \partial f_\kappa / \partial r$ and $g'_\kappa(r) = \partial g_\kappa / \partial r$, and E is a rest energy, $E = mc^2$. Solving the coupled equations for $g_\kappa(r)$ in Eq. (2.88), the differential equation becomes,

$$-\frac{1}{2M} \left[g''_\kappa + \frac{2}{r} g'_\kappa - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} g_\kappa \right] - \frac{V' g'_\kappa}{4M^2 c^2} - \frac{\kappa + 1}{r} \frac{V' g_\kappa}{4M^2 c^2} = E g_\kappa. \quad (2.89)$$

The second term, with $(dV/dr)(dg/dr)$ in the nominator in the left-hand side, is called Darwin term, while the third term is known as the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) term. The SOC term depends on κ , which takes value of,

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} l & \text{for } j = l + 1/2 \\ -(l + 1) & \text{for } j = l - 1/2. \end{cases} \quad (2.90)$$

If ones ignore the Darwin and SOC terms, Eq. (2.89) resembles an exact radial Schrödinger equation Eq. (2.31). g_κ can be obtained by keeping spin quantum number s as a good quantum number, although it is practically still difficult to obtain with high precision. Moreover, calculating core state density may require small components of f_κ .

In 1970, Kölling and Harmon [121] proposed the scalar-relativistic approximation (SRA) method to overcome this difficulty by treating SOC term as a perturbation after the relativistic spin-polarized calculation is performed. In other words, the Kohn-Sham-Dirac equation is reduced into a series of calculation, where a standard Kohn-Sham equation without SOC is performed, and the SOC is introduced later under the second variation procedures. In this scheme, the spin quantum number can be kept as a good quantum number, which is an advantage of this method.

The SRA solution can be obtained by first defining a new function $\phi_\kappa(r)$,

$$\phi_\kappa(r) = \frac{1}{2Mc} g'_\kappa, \quad (2.91)$$

and the f_κ is written as,

$$f_\kappa(r) = \phi_\kappa + \frac{\kappa + 1}{2Mc r} g_\kappa. \quad (2.92)$$

Using Eq. (2.91) and Eq. (2.92), Eq. (2.88) and (2.89) can be rewritten as,

$$\begin{aligned} g'_\kappa &= 2Mc\phi_\kappa, \\ \phi'_\kappa &= -\frac{2}{r}\phi_\kappa + \left[\frac{l(l+1)}{2Mc^2r^2} + \frac{1}{c}(V-E) + \frac{\kappa+1}{2Mc^2r}M' \right] g_\kappa, \end{aligned} \quad (2.93)$$

with $\kappa(\kappa+1) = l(l+1)$ and $M' = \partial M/\partial r$ have been used. The third term in the square brackets is the SOC term and is dropped in the SRA since this term couples the spin-up and -down.

The wavefunction in Eq. (2.87) is rewritten as,

$$\psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = \psi_{\kappa,\mu}(\mathbf{r}) \approx \begin{bmatrix} g_\kappa \chi_{\kappa\mu} \\ -i(\phi_l + \frac{\kappa+1}{2Mc^2r})\sigma_{\mathbf{r}}\chi_{\kappa\mu} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.94)$$

where Eq. (2.92) has been used. The non-relativistic quantum numbers l , m , s are obtained by calculating the Clebsh-Gordan coefficients, which result in,

$$\psi_{l,m,s}(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{pmatrix} g_l Y_{l,m}\chi_s \\ \frac{i}{2Mc}\sigma_{\mathbf{r}} \left(-g'_l + \frac{1}{r}g_l\hat{\sigma} \cdot \hat{L} \right) Y_{l,m}\chi_s \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.95)$$

with non-relativistic spinors χ_s . As we can see, the large component consists of a pure spin function, while the small component contains mixture of spins. Omitting the small component may offer a simple solution, since most of the relativistic correction is given by the large component g_l . However, when calculating the core charge density, the small component is required to obtain a good description of the core charge density. Therefore, to satisfy this requirement, the second variation method is introduced.

A new function is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} P_l &= rg_l, \\ Q_l &= rc\phi_l, \end{aligned} \quad (2.96)$$

both of which are used to re-express Eq. (2.93), as follow,

$$\begin{aligned} P'_l &= 2McQ_l + \frac{1}{r}P_l, \\ Q'_l &= -\frac{1}{r}Q_l + \left[\frac{l(l+1)}{2Mr^2} \right] P_l. \end{aligned} \quad (2.97)$$

These transformations yield a new wavefunction, given by

$$\psi_{l,m,s}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{r} \begin{bmatrix} P_l Y_{l,m}\chi_s \\ -i\mathbf{r} \cdot \sigma_{\mathbf{r}} \left(-Q_l + \frac{P_l}{2Mc^2r}\hat{\sigma} \cdot \hat{L} \right) Y_{l,m}\chi_s \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.98)$$

which is obtained through the second variation method [121] in practice.

The relativistic Hamiltonian including SOC with eigenfunction obtained by the second variation method is written as,

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_0 + \hat{H}_{SOC}, \quad (2.99)$$

with \hat{H}_0 is a non-relativistic DFT Hamiltonian and \hat{H}_{SOC} is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_{SOC} &= \sum_{\alpha} \xi(r_{\alpha}) \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}, \\ \xi(r_{\alpha}) &= \frac{\hbar}{(2Mc)^2} \frac{1}{r_{\alpha}} \frac{dV(r_{\alpha})}{dr_{\alpha}}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.100)$$

Additionally, the spin quantization axis (z -component of spin) can be set to any particular direction specified by spherical angles θ and ϕ relative to global coordinates by introducing a 2×2 rotation matrix $U(\theta, \phi)$ in the Weigner notation,

$$U(\theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ -\sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\frac{\phi}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\phi}{2}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.101)$$

and transforms the SOC Hamiltonian operators,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}} = U(\theta, \phi) [\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}] U^{\dagger}(\theta, \phi). \quad (2.102)$$

Figure 2.6 illustrates the rotation.

The procedure to obtain SOC correction is shown in the flowchart of Fig. 2.5. The procedure consists of following steps:

1. solve the conventional Kohn-Sham equation to get SRA one-electron wavefunction φ_{RSA} ,

$$H_{\text{DFT}} \varphi^{\text{SRA}} = \varepsilon \varphi^{\text{SRA}}, \quad (2.103)$$

without taking into account the SOC correction,

2. construct a new wavefunction, ψ , for second variation procedures

$$\psi = \sum_j d_j^i \varphi_j^{\text{SRA}}, \quad (2.104)$$

and calculate the matrix element of a full-relativistic Hamiltonian including H_{SOC} ,

$$\begin{aligned}H_{j',j} &= \varepsilon_j \langle \varphi_{j'}^{\text{SRA}} | \varphi_j^{\text{SRA}} \rangle + \langle \varphi_{j'}^{\text{SRA}} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \varphi_j^{\text{SRA}} \rangle, \\ &= \varepsilon_j \delta_{j',j} + \langle \varphi_{j'}^{\text{SRA}} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \varphi_j^{\text{SRA}} \rangle,\end{aligned}\quad (2.105)$$

where the correction term from SOC is derived as,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \varphi_{j'}^{\text{SRA}} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \varphi_j^{\text{SRA}} \rangle &= \sum_{l',m',l,m} \left(A_{l',m',j'}^{\sigma'}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* A_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) \langle u_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | u_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle \\ &+ \left(A_{l',m',j'}^{\sigma'}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* B_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) \langle u_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \dot{u}_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle \\ &+ \left(B_{l',m',j'}^{\sigma'}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* A_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) \langle \dot{u}_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | u_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle \\ &+ \left(B_{l',m',j'}^{\sigma'}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* B_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) \langle \dot{u}_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \dot{u}_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle\end{aligned}\quad (2.106)$$

with,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle u_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | u_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle &= 4\pi\delta_{l',l}(\chi_{\sigma'}^{\dagger} Y_{l',m'}^* [\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}] Y_{l,m} \chi_{\sigma}) \int dr r^2 \xi(r) P_{l'} P_l, \\
 \langle u_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \dot{u}_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle &= 4\pi\delta_{l',l}(\chi_{\sigma'}^{\dagger} Y_{l',m'}^* [\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}] Y_{l,m} \chi_{\sigma}) \int dr r^2 \xi(r) P_{l'} \dot{P}_l, \\
 \langle \dot{u}_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | u_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle &= 4\pi\delta_{l',l}(\chi_{\sigma'}^{\dagger} Y_{l',m'}^* [\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}] Y_{l,m} \chi_{\sigma}) \int dr r^2 \xi(r) \dot{P}_{l'} P_l, \\
 \langle \dot{u}_{l',m'}^{\sigma'} | H_{\text{SOC}} | \dot{u}_{l,m}^{\sigma} \rangle &= 4\pi\delta_{l',l}(\chi_{\sigma'}^{\dagger} Y_{l',m'}^* [\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}] Y_{l,m} \chi_{\sigma}) \int dr r^2 \xi(r) \dot{P}_{l'} \dot{P}_l,
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.107}$$

and the $A_{l,m}^{j,\sigma}$ and $B_{l,m}^{j,\sigma}$ are given by,

$$A_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_i C_{\mathbf{k}_i,j}^{\sigma} a_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_i,\sigma}, \quad B_{l,m,j}^{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_i C_{\mathbf{k}_i,j}^{\sigma} b_{l,m}^{\mathbf{k}_i,\sigma}. \tag{2.108}$$

3. obtain the expansion coefficient d_j^i and energy correction eigenvalues e and project back the eigenfunction ψ to obtain the charge density.

In the second variation procedures for SOC, it is important to note that the second variation Hamiltonian matrix size is the sum of the number of spin-up and spin-down eigenvalues, which implies that more computational cost is needed than in the standard Kohn-Sham Hamiltonian matrix calculation. This is because the SOC Hamiltonian matrix consists of $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta, \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{L}}$ which couples the spin-up and spin-down states, unlike the Hamiltonian matrix from Hubbard correction in section 2.5, where the spin-up and spin-down Hamiltonian matrices are diagonalized separately.

Figure 2.5: Flowchart of second variation schemes for scalar-relativistic approximation (SRA) SOC calculation.

Figure 2.6: (a) Spin quantization axis of magnetic atoms which originally directs in global z -direction. Transformation with $U(\theta, \phi)$ rotates the spin quantization axis into a new direction specified by polar coordinates θ and ϕ . (b) This rotation can also be viewed as Cartesian coordinates transformation from $\{x, y, z\}$ to $\{x', y', z'\}$.

2.7 Spin-Exchange Interaction and Magnetic Force Theorem

2.7.1 Origin of Spin-Exchange Interactions

Different types of magnetic interactions exist in magnetic solid, which allow one magnetic moment to communicate with others and produce a long-range magnetic order. In most magnetic solids, spin-exchange interaction is the dominant interaction that determines their long-range magnetic order. The spin-exchange interaction was discovered by Heisenberg [122] and Dirac [123] in 1926, where Heisenberg used the London method to explain the spin-exchange interaction. This type of interaction is nothing more than electrostatic interactions arising due to charges of the same sign cost energy when they are close together and save energy when they are apart.

To understand the origin of exchange-interaction, consider a simple model with two electrons in a state a and b having two spatial coordinates \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 , respectively. The joint wavefunction is expressed as a product of two individual spatial wavefunctions $\psi_a(\mathbf{r}_1)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_2)$. However, the total wavefunction, which takes into account spatial and spin states, has to be antisymmetric under particle exchange. This leads to the condition where, if the spatial state is antisymmetric, the spin-state must be a symmetric χ_+ , i.e., spin triplet state with $S = 1$, while if the spatial state is symmetric, the spin-state must be an anti-symmetric χ_- , i.e., spin singlet state with $S = 0$, as given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\Psi_S(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\psi_a(\mathbf{r}_1)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_2) + \psi_a(\mathbf{r}_2)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_1)] \chi_-, \\ \Psi_T(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\psi_a(\mathbf{r}_1)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_2) - \psi_a(\mathbf{r}_2)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_1)] \chi_+, \end{aligned} \quad (2.109)$$

where Ψ_S and Ψ_T are singlet and triplet total wavefunctions, respectively [124]. The energies of two states are expressed as integrals in two electrons coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned}E_S &= \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 d^3\mathbf{r}_2 \Psi_S^* \hat{H} \Psi_S, \\ E_T &= \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 d^3\mathbf{r}_2 \Psi_T^* \hat{H} \Psi_T. \end{aligned} \quad (2.110)$$

Substituting Eq. (2.109) in Eq. (2.110) and considering only the spatial integrals, the difference between the singlet and triplet states energy is written as,

$$E_S - E_T = 2 \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 d^3\mathbf{r}_2 \psi_a^*(\mathbf{r}_1)\psi_b^*(\mathbf{r}_2) \hat{H} \psi_a(\mathbf{r}_2)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_1). \quad (2.111)$$

Additionally, for a singlet state, $\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2 = -\frac{3}{4}$, while for the triplet state $\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2 = \frac{1}{4}$ ¹. With the defined E_S , E_T , $E_S - E_T$, and the $\mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j$, the Hamiltonian operator, \hat{H} , can be

¹This result can be obtained from an angular momentum addition where

$$2\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2 = (\mathbf{S}_{\text{tot}})^2 - (\mathbf{S}_1)^2 - (\mathbf{S}_2)^2.$$

The $(\mathbf{S}_{\text{tot}})^2 = 0(0+1)$ for a singlet state in which the $S = 0$, while $(\mathbf{S}_{\text{tot}})^2 = 2$ for a triplet state in which the $S = 1$. Both $(\mathbf{S}_1)^2$ and \mathbf{S}_2 are $\frac{3}{4}$ in the case of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ electrons. Therefore, the $\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2 = -\frac{3}{4}$ for the singlet state, and $\frac{1}{4}$ for the triplet state.

effectively expressed in the form of,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{4}(E_S + 3E_T) - (E_S - E_T)\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2. \quad (2.112)$$

The coefficient in the second term, which consists of $\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2$, is called a spin-exchange constant, J , given by

$$J = \frac{E_S - E_T}{2} = \int d^3\mathbf{r}_1 d^3\mathbf{r}_2 \psi_a^*(\mathbf{r}_1)\psi_b^*(\mathbf{r}_2) \hat{H} \psi_a(\mathbf{r}_2)\psi_b(\mathbf{r}_1). \quad (2.113)$$

Hence, the spin Hamiltonian between two electrons with spin is given by,

$$\hat{H}^{\text{spin}} = -2J\mathbf{S}_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}_2. \quad (2.114)$$

This motivates generalization to all neighboring atoms that carry a finite spin angular momentum, which is known as the Heisenberg model, where the spin Hamiltonian is given by,

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (2.115)$$

with $\frac{1}{2}$ is used to avoid double counting. The spin-exchange constant J will determine the ground-state magnetic order of magnetic solids. From direct observation of Eq. (2.115), if $J < 0$, the spin alignment between i -th and j -th spins will prefer anti-parallel alignment, which can result in antiferromagnetic order. On the other hand, if $J > 0$, parallel alignment is preferred, which results in ferromagnetic order.

The spin Hamiltonian in Eq. (2.115) can also be generalized in the case of anisotropic spin-exchange interactions present in the system, which can originate from the SOC effects of magnetic atoms, or non-magnetic atoms with strong SOC in the vicinity of the magnetic atom, given by,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{S}_i)^T \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (2.116)$$

and the spin-exchange constants are no longer defined in scalar form (known as "isotropic" spin-exchange constants), but instead as a 3×3 matrix defined for each spin pair,

$$\overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} J_{ij}^{xx} & J_{ij}^{xy} & J_{ij}^{xz} \\ J_{ij}^{yx} & J_{ij}^{yy} & J_{ij}^{yz} \\ J_{ij}^{zx} & J_{ij}^{zx} & J_{ij}^{zz} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.117)$$

and the negative sign in the general spin Hamiltonian has been absorbed into the elements of the matrix. The examples of these interactions are Kitaev, Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya, and Γ interactions.

2.7.2 Magnetic Force Theorem

Practically, spin-exchange constants in magnetic materials are not calculated directly by performing integration in Eq. (2.113). The common methods to calculate spin-exchange

constants include: (i) magnetic force theorem (MFT) [36, 125, 129, 130], (ii) spin-spiral (or frozen magnon) [126, 127], and (iii) total energy differences [35]. In the MFT, the spin-exchange constants are calculated as a response to infinitesimally rotating or tilting classical spins at two different lattice sites, which is then mapped onto the classical Heisenberg Hamiltonian via multiple scattering theory [36]. In frozen magnon, spin-exchange constants are obtained from the Fourier transform of the second derivative of spin-spiral total energy, E_q , with respect to a change of tilting angle between two different lattice sites [126]. Finally, in total energy difference, various magnetic configurations are used, which are mapped into the corresponding modeled spin Hamiltonian to extract the spin-exchange constants.

In this work, the MFT method is generalized to extract the spin-exchange tensor from a given magnetic structure, as it has several advantages. First, the MFT allows the calculation of the spin-exchange constants non-self-consistently from one assumed initial magnetic configuration, and the resulting spin-exchange constant trend as a function of interaction distance is independent of the choice of initial magnetic configuration, as demonstrated by [128]. Furthermore, the MFT gives good magnetic descriptions for a system in which the d orbital electrons give rise to finite magnetic moments and are localized within the atoms.

Infinitesimal Spin Rotation

Before finding the change of energy due to the infinitesimal spin rotations, it is convenient to express the generalized total spin Hamiltonian in Eq. (2.116) in the local coordinate systems, where each spin magnetic moment is aligned along local axis, \mathbf{z}' , and this is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{spin}} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} (\mathbf{s}_i)^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{s}_j, \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} (\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i)^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\tilde{J}}_{ij} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j, \end{aligned} \quad (2.118)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\tilde{J}}_{ij} &= \left[(\mathbf{U}_i)^{\text{T}} \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \mathbf{U}_j \right], \\ \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i &= (\mathbf{U}_i)^{\text{T}} \mathbf{s}_i, \\ \mathbf{U}_i &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_i^{(0)} \cos \phi_i^{(0)} & -\sin \phi_i^{(0)} & \sin \theta_i^{(0)} \cos \phi_i^{(0)} \\ \cos \theta_i^{(0)} \sin \phi_i^{(0)} & \cos \phi_i^{(0)} & \sin \theta_i^{(0)} \sin \phi_i^{(0)} \\ -\sin \theta_i^{(0)} & 0 & \cos \theta_i^{(0)} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.119)$$

In this notation, $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i$ is defined in the local coordinate systems and connected to the unit vector in the global coordinate system, \mathbf{s}_i , via the site unitary transformation matrix, \mathbf{U}_i . Accordingly, the spin-exchange tensor, $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\tilde{J}}_{ij}$, is also defined in the two local coordinate systems, $\{\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}'\}$ and $\{\mathbf{x}'', \mathbf{y}'', \mathbf{z}''\}$. All the vector notations, global, and local coordinate systems are illustrated in Fig. 2.7.

To obtain the expression of total energy change under infinitesimal spin rotations, the

Figure 2.7: Illustration of the equilibrium unit spin vector in the global and local coordinate systems, $\mathbf{s}_i^{(0)}$ ($\theta_i^{(0)}$, $\phi_i^{(0)}$) and $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}$, respectively. The infinitesimal rotation in the local coordinate system, $\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i$, and the rotated unit spin vector, $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{\text{rot}}$ are also illustrated.

infinitesimally rotated spin unit, $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{\text{rot}}$, is given by,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{\text{rot}} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} + [\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}] + \mathcal{O}(|\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}|^2), \quad (2.120)$$

where, the equilibrium unit vector, $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}$, is aligned along a local coordinate axis \mathbf{z}' , and the infinitesimal rotation $\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i$ is given by,

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i = \vartheta_i^{x'} \mathbf{x}' + \vartheta_i^{y'} \mathbf{y}'. \quad (2.121)$$

Note that, the ϑ_i^α denotes the infinitesimal rotation angle, while the $\theta_i^{(0)}$ denotes the polar angle of the unit spin vector in the equilibrium. Substituting Eq. (2.120) into the total energy of spin configuration, Eq. (2.118) and grouping all the term based on the order of $\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i$, the E_{spin} is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{spin}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left[& \left(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} \right)^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j^{(0)} \right. \\ & + \left(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} \right)^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot [\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_j \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j^{(0)}] + [\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}]^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j^{(0)} \\ & \left. + [\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}]^{\text{T}} \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{ij} \cdot [\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_j \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j^{(0)}] + \mathcal{O}(|\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i|^3) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.122)$$

In this equation, the first term corresponds to the interactions between the equilibrium components of a spin pair, the second and third terms correspond to the interactions between equilibrium and that in the infinitesimal components of a spin pair, and the fourth term represents the interactions between the infinitesimal components of a spin pair. It is straightforward to prove that, the element of spin-exchange tensor, $\tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$ is obtained from the second derivative of the E_{spin} with respect to two-site infinitesimal spin rotations, and given by,

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\vartheta_i^\gamma \partial\vartheta_j^\nu} E_{\text{spin}} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\alpha\gamma\lambda} \epsilon_{\beta\nu\eta} \tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} s_i^{(0),\lambda} s_j^{(0),\eta}, \quad (2.123)$$

where $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is a Levi-Civita symbol. This equation tells that, in order to obtain the element of spin-exchange tensor $\tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$, one needs to infinitesimally rotate spin vector at site i (j) along a direction perpendicular to the local \mathbf{z}' , e.g, λ (η), and to the local α (β).

Perturbation on One-Electron Kohn-Sham Energies from Infinitesimal Spin Rotation

The idea of MFT is that, the infinitesimal spin rotation is treated as a perturbation to the one-electron energies, and the energy change due to the perturbation is then mapped into the generalized spin Hamiltonian in Eq. (2.118), to obtain the expression of the spin-exchange tensor in terms of one-electron Kohn-Sham wavefunctions and energies. By taking a look into the expression of spin-polarized Kohn-Sham equation in Eq. (2.16), the only part of Kohn-Sham equation that changes under infinitesimal rotation is the last term, which contains effective magnetic field $\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff},i}$ at site i . Assuming that the $\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff},i}$ is parallel to the spin magnetic moment, $\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff},i} = B_{\text{eff},i}\mathbf{s}_i$, the perturbation induced from infinitesimal rotation on spin-polarized Kohn-Sham equation is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta E_{\text{KS}} &\approx \sum_i B_{\text{eff},i} \left(\mathbf{s}_i^{\text{rot}} - \mathbf{s}_i^{(0)} \right) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ &= \sum_i B_{\text{eff},i} \left(\mathbf{U}_i (\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{\text{rot}} - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}) \right)^{\text{T}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ &= \sum_i B_{\text{eff},i} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{\text{rot}} - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} \right)^{\text{T}} \mathbf{U}_i^{\text{T}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ &= \sum_i B_{\text{eff},i} \left(\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \times \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} \right) \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}},\end{aligned}\tag{2.124}$$

where the $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ are Pauli matrices in the local coordinate system, and Eq. (2.120) has been invoked in the last line of above equation. The change of one-electron Kohn-Sham energies under this perturbation is obtained via second-order perturbation theory, which is given by,

$$\Delta E_{\text{KS}}^{(2)} = \sum_{i,j} \sum_n^{\text{occ}} \sum_{n' \neq n} \frac{\langle \Psi_n | \left[\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \times B_{\text{eff},i} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)} \right] \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} | \Psi_{n'} \rangle \langle \Psi_{n'} | \left[\delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_j \times B_{\text{eff},j} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_j^{(0)} \right] \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} | \Psi_{n'} \rangle}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{n'}},\tag{2.125}$$

where ϵ_n and $|\Psi_n\rangle$ are the one-electron Kohn-Sham energies and wavefunctions in spinor. Changing the summation over occupied states into $\sum_n^{\text{occ}} \dots = \sum_n f_n \dots$ and the $\mathbf{B}_i = B_{\text{eff},i} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(0)}$ and using the cross and dot products identity, the second-order correction is rewritten as,

$$\Delta E_{\text{KS}}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \sum_{n,n' \neq n} \frac{f_n - f_{n'}}{\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{n'}} \langle \Psi_n | \delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_i \cdot [\mathbf{B}_i \times \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}] | \Psi_{n'} \rangle \langle \Psi_{n'} | \delta\boldsymbol{\phi}_j \cdot [\mathbf{B}_j \times \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}] | \Psi_{n'} \rangle.\tag{2.126}$$

The spin-exchange tensor can now be obtained by taking the second-order derivative of $\Delta E_{KS}^{(2)}$ with respect to the infinitesimal rotation ϑ_i^γ and ϑ_j^ν , following the Eq. (2.123),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vartheta_i^\gamma \partial \vartheta_j^\nu} \Delta E_{KS}^{(2)} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n, n' \neq n} \frac{f_n - f_{n'}}{\varepsilon_n - \varepsilon_{n'}} \langle \Psi_n | [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \times \mathbf{B}_i]_\gamma | \Psi_{n'} \rangle \langle \Psi_{n'} | [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \times \mathbf{B}_j]_\nu | \Psi_{n'} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\alpha\gamma\lambda} \epsilon_{\beta\nu\eta} \tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.127)$$

To have a direct and explicit form of $\tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$, the Pauli matrices in local coordinate systems are redefined, as such,

$$\hat{\sigma}_{x'} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_{y'} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_{z'} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.128)$$

and by exploiting the translational symmetry of spin-exchange tensor $\tilde{J}_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} = \tilde{J}_{\mathbb{T}_n+i, \mathbb{T}_n+j}^{\alpha\beta}$ with \mathbb{T}_n being the translational symmetry operations, the general spin-exchange tensor in the MFT method is written as,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q}) &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{n, n'} \frac{f_{\mathbf{k}, n} - f_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'}}{\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}, n} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'}} \langle \Psi_{\mathbf{k}, n} | [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \times \mathbf{B}_\tau]_\alpha | \Psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'} \rangle \langle \Psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'} | [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \times \mathbf{B}_{\tau'}]_\beta | \Psi_{\mathbf{k}, n} \rangle, \\ \tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{\alpha\beta} &= \frac{\Omega}{(2\pi)^D} \int_{u.c} d^D \mathbf{q} \tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q}) e^{-i\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{l'}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.129)$$

$\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{\alpha\beta}$ represents the spin-exchange interactions between the spin at site τ in the unit cell at the origin and the spin at site τ' in the unit cell $R_{l'}$, as illustrated in Fig. 2.8. As one can see from Eq. (2.129), the Fourier component of spin-exchange constants $\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q})$ is first calculated for all \mathbf{q} in the Brillouin zone, and then Fourier transformation is performed to obtain the spin-exchange constants in the real space. The spin-exchange tensor in the global coordinate system, $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}$, can be obtained by performing the unitary transformation given in Eq. (2.119).

2.7.3 Implementation of Magnetic Force Theorem in FLAPW Method

Collinear and no SOC case (isotropic)

In the case of collinear and no SOC, only the B_τ^z survives. Consequently, it can be shown that only four out of nine elements of the spin-exchange constants can be calculated, which are J^{xx} , J^{yy} , J^{xy} , and J^{yx} . Furthermore, the wavefunction spinor can be expressed as,

$$\Psi_{\mathbf{k}, n} = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n}^\uparrow \\ \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n}^\downarrow \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.130)$$

Additionally, the collinear and no SOC calculation allows the separate calculation of spin-up and spin-down Kohn-Sham equations, and the spin-up (spin-down) electron wavefunctions can be written as $\psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\uparrow}^\uparrow$ ($\psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\downarrow}^\downarrow$).

Figure 2.8: The notation of spin-exchange constants $\vec{J}_{0+\tau, R_l'+\tau'}$ between two magnetic atoms, where the two magnetic atoms are located at τ and τ' within the unit cells separated with translation lattice vector $\mathbf{R}_{l'}$. Blue and red circles represent the magnetic atoms in the unit cell.

Applying these wavefunctions to Eq. (2.129), it can be shown that the J^{yy} are equal to J^{xx} , while J^{yx} are equal to $-J^{xy}$, which are given by,

$$J_{0+\tau, R_l'+\tau'}^{xx}(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\substack{\nu, \nu' \neq \nu \\ \in \{\uparrow, \downarrow\}}} \sum_{n_\nu, n'_{\nu'}} \frac{f_{\mathbf{k}, n_\nu} - f_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_{\nu'}}}{\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}, n_\nu} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_{\nu'}}} \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\nu}^\nu | B_\tau^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_{\nu'}}^{\nu'} \rangle \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_{\nu'}}^{\nu'} | B_{\tau'}^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\nu}^\nu \rangle, \quad (2.131)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_{0+\tau, R_l'+\tau'}^{xy}(\mathbf{q}) &= -i \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{n_\uparrow, n'_\downarrow} \frac{f_{\mathbf{k}, n_\uparrow} - f_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\downarrow}}{\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}, n_\uparrow} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\downarrow}} \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\uparrow}^\uparrow | B_\tau^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\downarrow}^\downarrow \rangle \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\downarrow}^\downarrow | B_{\tau'}^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\uparrow}^\uparrow \rangle \\ &+ i \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{n_\downarrow, n'_\uparrow} \frac{f_{\mathbf{k}, n_\downarrow} - f_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\uparrow}}{\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}, n_\downarrow} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\uparrow}} \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\downarrow}^\downarrow | B_\tau^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\uparrow}^\uparrow \rangle \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_\uparrow}^\uparrow | B_{\tau'}^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\downarrow}^\downarrow \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (2.132)$$

In both cases of Eq. (2.131) and Eq. (2.132), the matrix element of $\langle \psi_{\mathbf{k}, n_\nu}^\nu | B_\tau^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}, n'_{\nu'}}^{\nu'} \rangle$ has to be calculated. The B_τ^z is taken as the difference between the effective potential of spin-up and spin-down electrons inside the muffin tin of the atom at site τ , as given by

$$B_\tau^z(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(v_{\text{eff}, \tau}^\uparrow(\mathbf{r}) - v_{\text{eff}, \tau}^\downarrow(\mathbf{r}) \right), \quad (2.133)$$

where this effective local field inside the muffin tin can be expanded as the sum of spherical harmonics, as given by,

$$B_\tau^z(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{l, m} B_{l, \tau}^z(r) Y_{l, m}(\hat{r}). \quad (2.134)$$

Hence, the LAPW basis function in the muffin tin in Eq. (2.35) is invoked, and the matrix

element is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \psi_{\mathbf{k},n\nu}^{\nu} | B_{\tau}^z | \psi_{\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q},n'\nu'}^{\nu'} \rangle = & \sum_{l,m} \sum_{l',m''} \left(\left(A_{l,m,n\nu}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,uu} A_{l',m'',n'\nu'}^{\tau,\nu'}(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}) \right. \\
 & + \left(A_{l,m,n\nu}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,u\dot{u}} B_{l',m'',n'\nu'}^{\tau,\nu'}(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}) \\
 & + \left(B_{l,m,n\nu}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,\dot{u}u} A_{l',m'',n'\nu'}^{\tau,\nu'}(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}) \\
 & \left. + \left(B_{l,m,n\nu}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k}) \right)^* t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,\dot{u}\dot{u}} B_{l',m'',n'\nu'}^{\tau,\nu'}(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}) \right), \tag{2.135}
 \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,uu} &= \sum_{l'm'} G_{ll'l'm'}^{mm'm''} \int_{\tau} r^2 dr u_{l,\nu}^{\tau}(r) u_{l',\nu'}^{\tau}(r) B_{l'\tau}^z(r), \\
 t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,u\dot{u}} &= \sum_{l'm'} G_{ll'l'm'}^{mm'm''} \int_{\tau} r^2 dr \dot{u}_{l,\nu}^{\tau}(r) u_{l',\nu'}^{\tau}(r) B_{l'\tau}^z(r), \\
 t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,\dot{u}u} &= \sum_{l'm'} G_{ll'l'm'}^{mm'm''} \int_{\tau} r^2 dr u_{l,\nu}^{\tau}(r) \dot{u}_{l',\nu'}^{\tau}(r) B_{l'\tau}^z(r), \\
 t_{ll',\nu\nu'}^{\tau,\dot{u}\dot{u}} &= \sum_{l'm'} G_{ll'l'm'}^{mm'm''} \int_{\tau} r^2 dr \dot{u}_{l,\nu}^{\tau}(r) \dot{u}_{l',\nu'}^{\tau}(r) B_{l'\tau}^z(r), \tag{2.136}
 \end{aligned}$$

and $A_{l,m}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k})$ and $B_{l,m}^{\tau,\nu}(\mathbf{k})$ are given by Eq. (2.108), and $G_{l,l',l''}^{m,m',m''}$ is the Gaunt coefficient.

Collinear and spin-orbit coupling case (anisotropic)

All nine elements of the spin-exchange tensor can be obtained by exploiting the spin rotation via the SOC, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\theta^{(0)}, \phi^{(0)}) \cdot \mathbf{L}$, as discussed in section 2.6 and shown in Fig. 2.6. By rotating the spin quantization axis along one particular direction $(\theta^{(0)}, \phi^{(0)})$, the local effective magnetic field points along the same direction. In the collinear magnetic order calculations with SOC correction, if the spin quantization axis directions are aligned along the three orthogonal axes of global coordinate system, each direction will produce four elements of spin-exchange tensor in local coordinate systems, i.e., $\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{x'x''}$, $\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{y'y''}$, $\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{x'y''}$, and $\tilde{J}_{0+\tau, R_{l'+\tau'}}^{y'x''}$, as given by Eq. (2.131) and (2.132). Then, the four elements of spin-exchange tensor are mapped into four elements of spin-exchange tensor in global coordinate system via the unitary transformation operations in Eq. (2.119). Therefore, the calculation requires less computational time and cost, since the self-consistent calculation is performed only once, and different magnetization directions are non-iteratively introduced via the SOC correction as a perturbation.

2.8 Theory of Magnons

In this section, the method for solving spin Hamiltonian equation in Eq. (2.116) is presented to obtain the energy of collective spin moments precession in a periodic lattice of magnetic materials. All electronic spins at an atomic site i , in Eq. (2.116) are first treated as a single localized 'collective spin', denoted as \mathbf{S}_i . First, the semi-classical spin-precession under an effective magnetic field via Larmor equation is first demonstrated in Sec. 2.8.1. Then, quantum formulation of spin-precession is introduced, where transformation from spin operators to the local magnon operators are carried out via Holstein-Primakoff transformation [131], which gives us infinite orders of magnonic field operators, as will be discussed in Sec. 2.8.2. The simplest, yet descriptive solution at low temperature limit is obtained by taking the diagonalizable orders of field operators, which in the magnon case is the second-order of magnon Hamiltonian, as will be discussed in Sec. 2.8.4. The diagonalization procedure of the second-order magnon Hamiltonian is introduced in Sec. 2.8.6, which differs from a standard unitary diagonalization due to the symmetric nature of bosonic wavefunctions. Alternatively, one can view the second-order magnon Hamiltonian as a 'free magnon', in analogy to the 'free electron' in one electron approximation. The higher order of magnon Hamiltonian represents the interactions between free magnons, in analogy to two-body Coulomb interactions in one electron approximation, and in a many-body perturbation framework, these interactions give rise to an energy renormalization and quasiparticle relaxation. The treatment for multi-magnon interactions is described in Sec. 2.8.8, where the third-order magnon Hamiltonian is taken as a perturbation to the free magnon using the many-body Green's function method and Dyson's equation, which gives us the magnon energy renormalization and magnon damping expression induced by the three-magnon interactions.

2.8.1 Semi-Classical Larmor Precession Equation

To study the dynamics of spin at site i , $\mathbf{S}_i(t)$, under the effective magnetic field, $\mathbf{B}_i^{\text{eff}}$, the phenomenological Larmor precession equation, which is a spin-precession equation of motion, is given as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{S}_i(t)}{dt} = \gamma \mathbf{S}_i(t) \times \mathbf{B}_i^{\text{eff}}, \quad (2.137)$$

where γ is a gyromagnetic ratio, and the spin-precession is illustrated in Fig. 2.9(a). The local \mathbf{z} -component of spin is assumed to be constant in time, and the time dependence of spin dynamics is contained in the transversal components. In this way, the spin vector is taken as,

$$\mathbf{S}_i(t) = \begin{pmatrix} S_i^x e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}_i - \omega t)} \\ S_i^y e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}_i - \omega t)} \\ S_i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.138)$$

where \mathbf{r}_i is the position of spin at site i in the real space and S_i is the spin quantum number, and the effective magnetic field is given by,

$$\mathbf{B}_i^{\text{eff}} = \nabla_{\mathbf{S}_i} \hat{H}, \quad (2.139)$$

and \hat{H} is given by Eq. (2.116).

To obtain the magnetic resonance frequency, ω , an eigenvalue problem to be solved is given by

$$\omega \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{S}^x \\ i\mathbb{S}^y \end{pmatrix} = \mathbb{H} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{S}^x \\ i\mathbb{S}^y \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.140)$$

where \mathbb{S}^x and \mathbb{S}^y are column vectors of S_i^x and S_i^y , and \mathbb{H} is a matrix formed by coupled linear equations consisting several magnetic interactions. Note that the matrix in Eq. (2.140) is generally not Hermitian. The eigenvalue ω from the spin-precession equation represents a magnetic resonance frequency, also known as magnon resonance frequencies, which can generally be a complex number. The eigenfunctions consisting of \mathbb{S}^x and \mathbb{S}^y correspond to the shape of classical spin-precession of the corresponding magnetic resonance frequencies ω . To achieve applicability for signal processing applications, all magnetic resonance frequencies must have zero imaginary part, in which non-zero imaginary part causes decaying spin precession. Thus, the imaginary part of magnon frequencies is responsible for the stability of magnetic order, in analogy to that of phonon frequencies being responsible for the stability of crystal structure.

The phenomenological Larmor precession equation only gives the information about the magnetic resonance frequencies and the shape of classical spin-precession, while it gives no information about the dissipation from the damping process during the precession. In the next section, it will be demonstrated that the quantum formulation of spin-precession by Holstein-Primakoff transformation allows one to investigate magnon damping via magnon-magnon interactions.

2.8.2 Holstein-Primakoff Transformation

Consider an arbitrary particle with a spin- S with S takes a value of $j = \frac{1}{2}, 1, \frac{3}{2}, 2, \dots$. The spin quantum states forms an orthonormal set $|S, m_S\rangle$ which are simultaneously the eigenstate of following operators,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}^2 |S, m_S\rangle &= S(S+1) |S, m_S\rangle, \\ \hat{S}^z |S, m_S\rangle &= m_S |S, m_S\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (2.141)$$

with value of m_S depends on the S ,

$$m_S = \begin{cases} \pm S, \pm(S-1), \dots, 0 & \text{for } S \text{ is an integer,} \\ \pm S, \pm(S-1/2), \dots, \pm 1/2 & \text{for } S \text{ is a half-integer.} \end{cases} \quad (2.142)$$

It is convenient to have a general expression of m_S that depends on S without having to specify the type of spin quantum number whether it is an integer or a half-integer. This will be advantageous when dealing with a system containing particles with different types of spin quantum numbers. The general form takes the form of

$$m_S = S - n \quad \text{where } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 2S. \quad (2.143)$$

By writing m_S in this form, for a fixed value of S , m_S and n have one-to-one correspondence. This means that $|S, m_S\rangle$ can be rewritten as $|S, n\rangle$, which is also the simultaneous eigenstates of \hat{S}^2 and \hat{S}^z . For simplicity, $|S, n\rangle$ is denoted as $|n\rangle$, similar to $|S, m_S\rangle$ as $|m_S\rangle$. Taking the example of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$, the eigenstates $|m_S = +\frac{1}{2}\rangle$ and $|m_S = -\frac{1}{2}\rangle$ can be written as $|n = 0\rangle$ and $|n = 1\rangle$, respectively. Furthermore, substituting the expression of m_S in Eq. (2.143) to eigenequation for \hat{S}^z in Eq. (2.141) results in

$$\hat{S}^z|n\rangle = (S - n)|n\rangle. \quad (2.144)$$

If the \hat{S}^z operators is redefined to be,

$$\hat{S}^z = S - \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}, \quad (2.145)$$

the

$$\hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}|n\rangle = n|n\rangle, \quad (2.146)$$

becomes occupation number operators, which tells us number of magnon particles, n , occupy that state, and a vacuum state $|0\rangle$ corresponds to the state $|S, m_S = S\rangle$. As the occupation number n increases, the corresponding m_S decreases, described by Eq. (2.143), and this is diagrammatically shown in Fig. 2.9(b). The creation and annihilation operators \hat{a}^\dagger and \hat{a} also have properties, as given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}|n\rangle &= \sqrt{n}|n-1\rangle, & 1 \leq n \leq 2S, \\ \hat{a}^\dagger|n\rangle &= \sqrt{n+1}|n+1\rangle, & 0 \leq n \leq 2S-1, \end{aligned} \quad (2.147)$$

with a range of n has to be set in order to be consistent with definition in Eq. (2.143).

To have a full description of spin dynamics of the system, the transversal components of spin, \hat{S}^x and \hat{S}^y , also have to be defined in terms of magnon creation and annihilation operators. From quantum mechanics, these transversal components operators are obtained from definition of $\hat{S}^\pm = \hat{S}^x \pm i\hat{S}^y$, where

$$\hat{S}^+|m_S\rangle = \sqrt{(S - m_S)(S + m_S + 1)}|m_S + 1\rangle. \quad (2.148)$$

Based on Eq. (2.143), if m_S increases by one, n decreases by one, which mathematically translates into $|m_S + 1\rangle \rightarrow |n - 1\rangle$. This gives us,

$$\hat{S}^+|n\rangle = \sqrt{n(2S - (n - 1))}|n - 1\rangle. \quad (2.149)$$

Figure 2.9: (a) The classical illustration of a spin, \mathbf{S}_i , precession around the effective magnetic field, $\mathbf{B}_i^{\text{eff}}$. (b) The illustration of the correspondence between spin operators and magnonic field operators in the case of $S = 2$. Deviation of spin from its quantization axis, \hat{S}^z , is perceived as a 'creation' of magnons, while the aligning of spin to its quantization axis is perceived as a 'annihilation' of magnons.

Substituting Eq. (2.147) to replace $|n-1\rangle$ yields to,

$$\hat{S}^+|n\rangle = \sqrt{(2S - (n-1))\hat{a}}|n\rangle. \quad (2.150)$$

Notice that the operators that produces the coefficient $\sqrt{2S - (n-1)}$ in the final state $|n-1\rangle$ must be in a function of the occupation number operators $\hat{b}^\dagger\hat{b}$ from the initial state $|n\rangle$, which gives us,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}^+(\hat{a}^\dagger, \hat{a}) &= \sqrt{2S - \hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}}\hat{a} \\ &= (2S)^{1/2} \left(1 - \frac{\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}}{2S}\right)^{1/2} \hat{a}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.151)$$

If same procedures applies for \hat{S}^- operator, similar results are obtained, as given by

$$\hat{S}^-(\hat{a}^\dagger, \hat{a}) = (2S)^{1/2}\hat{a}^\dagger \left(1 - \frac{\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}}{2S}\right)^{1/2} \quad (2.152)$$

By having \hat{S}^+ and \hat{S}^- expressed in terms of \hat{a}^\dagger and \hat{a} , the transversal component operators can also be expressed in terms of these boson creation and annihilation operators by $\hat{S}^\pm = \hat{S}^x \pm i\hat{S}^y$.

2.8.3 Transformation to the Global Coordinate System

Previously, the Holstein-Primakoff transformation was discussed in terms of local coordinate system $\{\hat{S}^{x'}, \hat{S}^{y'}, \hat{S}^{z'}\}$, where magnons are created (annihilated) from spin deviating from (aligning to) local spin quantization axis direction. In the system where local spins have different spin quantization axis directions depending on which atomic site they belong, it is convenient to define the local spin in global coordinate system due to the spin-exchange constants in Eq. (2.116) are defined in global coordinate system. Then, the interacting

spins under general spin-exchange interactions in Eq. (2.116) can mathematically be described as matrix multiplication [132]. Suppose that a local spin at site τ in the unit cell \mathbf{R}_i is rotated by an angle of (θ_τ, ϕ_τ) relative to the global coordinate systems, as shown in Fig. 2.6(b), the relation between spin in local (rotated) coordinate system $\{x', y', z'\}$ and that in global coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$ is given by,

$$\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^x \\ \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^y \\ \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_\tau \cos \phi_\tau & \cos \theta_\tau \sin \phi_\tau & -\sin \theta_\tau \\ -\sin \phi_\tau & \cos \phi_\tau & 0 \\ \sin \theta_\tau \cos \phi_\tau & \sin \theta_\tau \sin \phi_\tau & \cos \theta_\tau \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^{x'} \\ \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^{y'} \\ \hat{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^{z'} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.153)$$

By substituting the $\hat{S}^{x'}$, $\hat{S}^{y'}$, and $\hat{S}^{z'}$ from Eq. (2.151), (2.152) and (2.145), the $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}$ is rewritten as,

$$\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)} = \sqrt{\frac{S(\tau)}{2}} \left(\mathbf{u}_{(\tau)} \hat{F}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i} + \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^* \hat{F}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}^\dagger \right) + \mathbf{v}_{(\tau)} \left(S(\tau) - \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i} \right), \quad (2.154)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{v}_{(\tau)} = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta_\tau \cos \phi_\tau \\ \sin \theta_\tau \sin \phi_\tau \\ \cos \theta_\tau \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_\tau \cos \phi_\tau + i \sin \phi_\tau \\ \cos \theta_\tau \sin \phi_\tau - i \cos \phi_\tau \\ -\sin \theta_\tau \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.155)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i} &= \left(1 - \frac{\hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}}{2S(\tau)} \right)^{1/2} \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}, \\ &= \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i} - \frac{\hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i} \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{R}_i}}{4S(\tau)} + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (2.156)$$

and binomial expansion has been invoked to express the square root of field operators in Eq. (2.156) in the form of infinite series of field operators, which leads to an infinite order of magnon Hamiltonian, as shall be discussed in next section. The $\mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}$ represents the two axes vectors, along which the $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}$ oscillates, while the $\mathbf{v}_{(\tau)}$ identifies the spin quantization axis vector of the spin at site τ in the global coordinate system.

2.8.4 Magnon Hamiltonian

In a periodic lattice, the spin Hamiltonian in Eq. (2.116) between spins in any arbitrary spin quantization axes can be rewritten as,

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{i,j}^{N_{uc}} \sum_{\tau,\tau'}^{N_{at}} \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{J}_{\mathbf{R}_i+\tau, \mathbf{R}_j+\tau'} \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_j(\tau')} + \sum_{i,\tau}^{N_{uc}, N_{at}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}, \quad (2.157)$$

where indices i and j run over number of unit cells, N_{uc} , while τ and τ' run over number of magnetic atom sites within a unit cell, N_{at} . The first term represents local and non-local quadratic spin interactions between spins $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}$ and $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_j(\tau')}$, e.g., magnetic dipolar interactions, single-ion anisotropy, symmetric spin-exchange, Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya, and

Kitaev interactions, while the second term represents Zeeman term from an applied magnetizing field.

Substitution of the $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R}_i(\tau)}$ from Eq. (2.154) to the total spin Hamiltonian Eq. (2.157) and grouping all the terms based on the order of magnon field operators yields,

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}^{(0)} + \hat{H}^{(1)} + \hat{H}^{(2)} + \hat{H}^{(3)} + \hat{H}^{(4)} + \dots \quad (2.158)$$

The $\hat{H}^{(n)}$ is called as n -th order magnon Hamiltonian. The zeroth order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(0)}$, contains no magnon field operators and represents the energy of static magnetic structure. The first order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(1)}$, contains terms that are linear in magnon field operators and vanishes automatically if the magnetic structure is a ground state magnetic structure [33]. The second-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(2)}$, contains terms that are quadratic in magnon field operators and represents the noninteracting quanta of spin dynamics, i.e., magnons in zero temperature limit. The third-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, represents perturbation to the magnons via three-magnon scatterings. This third-order magnon Hamiltonian arises from the coupling between transverse component of spin (first parentheses in Eq. (2.154)) that oscillating during the precession and longitudinal component of spin (second parentheses in Eq. (2.154)) that is conserved during the precession. In the collinear magnetic structures, this coupling is enabled by the off-diagonal elements of 3×3 matrix of spin-exchange interactions in Eq. (2.117). In general, the $(2m + 1)$ -th order magnon Hamiltonian always arises from the coupling between transverse and longitudinal components, while the $(2m)$ -th order magnon Hamiltonian arises from coupling either between transverse components or between longitudinal components. However, the high-order magnon Hamiltonian has weaker strength in perturbation due to the increasing power of $S_{(\tau)}$ in the denominator. Hence, the third-order magnon Hamiltonian is taken as a perturbation, as discussed in Sec. 2.8.8.

2.8.5 Linear Spin-Wave Theory (LSWT) for Solving Second-Order Magnon Hamiltonian

Taking all the terms in $\hat{H}^{(2)}$ and performing Fourier transformations to the reciprocal space, the second-order Hamiltonian is given by a matrix product expression as,

$$\hat{H}^{(2)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}>0} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (2.159)$$

where $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} = (\hat{a}_{(1)\mathbf{k}}, \dots, \hat{a}_{(N_{at})\mathbf{k}}, \hat{a}_{(1)-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger, \dots, \hat{a}_{(N_{at})-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger)^\top$ and $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is a $2N_{at} \times 2N_{at}$ Hermitian Hamiltonian matrix. The $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ can be written in terms of two $N_{at} \times N_{at}$ sub-matrices [132],

$$\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{A}_{\mathbf{k}} & \mathbb{B}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \mathbb{B}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger & \mathbb{A}_{-\mathbf{k}}^* \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.160)$$

The elements of matrices $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbf{k}}$ and $\mathbb{B}_{\mathbf{k}}$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau,\tau')} &= \frac{\sqrt{S_{(\tau)}S_{(\tau')}}}{2} \left(\text{Re}[\mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k})\mathbf{u}_{(\tau')}] \right) - \delta_{\tau\tau'} \sum_{\tau''=1}^{N_{at}} \mathbf{v}_{(\tau)}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau''}(0)\mathbf{v}_{(\tau'')} \\ \mathbb{B}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau,\tau')} &= \frac{\sqrt{S_{(\tau)}S_{(\tau')}}}{2} \left(\text{Re}[\mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k})\mathbf{u}_{(\tau')}^*] \right),\end{aligned}\quad (2.161)$$

where the matrix $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k})$ corresponds to a Fourier component of $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_j(\tau')}$ matrix in Eq. (2.129),

$$\mathbf{J}_{\tau\tau'}^{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_j^{N_{uc}} \mathbf{J}_{0+\tau,\mathbf{R}_j+\tau'}^{\mu\nu} \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_j(\tau')}).$$
 (2.162)

μ and ν run over Cartesian coordinates, and $\mathbf{d}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_j(\tau')}$ denotes the vector that connects magnetic atom at τ' at unit cell j to magnetic atom τ at unit cell at the origin. Contribution from \mathbf{B} to $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is given as,

$$\mathbb{A}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau,\tau')} = -\delta_{\tau\tau'} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{v}_{(\tau)}.$$
 (2.163)

Magnon dispersion is obtained by performing Bogoliubov transformation on the $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$, that transforms local creation and annihilation field operators, $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}$, into magnon mode creation and annihilation operators, $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}} = (\hat{\alpha}_{(1)\mathbf{k}}, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_{(N_m)\mathbf{k}}, \hat{\alpha}_{(1)-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_{(N_m)-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger)^T$, by a transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} &= \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}} \\ &= \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.164)$$

The $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ satisfies the following relation,

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger g \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}} = g,$$
 (2.165)

where $g = \text{diag}(1, \dots, 1, -1, \dots, -1)$. $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ is a diagonal matrix and its diagonal elements give the magnon dispersion of N_m magnon modes as, $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} = \hbar \text{diag}(\omega_{(1)\mathbf{k}}, \dots, \omega_{(N_m)\mathbf{k}}, \omega_{(1)-\mathbf{k}}, \dots, \omega_{(N_m)-\mathbf{k}})$.

2.8.6 Bosonic Diagonalization

As expressed in Eq. (2.165), the transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is not a unitary matrix, but rather a paraunitary matrix. This is a consequence of the commutation relations of magnonic field operators $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}$ and $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, as given by,

$$[\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}, \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger] = g, \quad [\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}, \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger] = g.$$
 (2.166)

Note that g is a matrix of $\text{diag}(1, \dots, 1, -1, \dots, -1)$, not to be confused with an atomic g factor. Therefore, diagonalization by a paraunitary matrix needs to be performed, which is known as Bogoliubov diagonalization. In this work, the numerical Bogoliubov diagonalization for a semi-positive definite quadratic boson Hamiltonian is employed [133].

To diagonalize the matrix $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ in Eq. (2.160), Cholesky decomposition is performed on

$\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ to find a lower triangular matrix that satisfies,

$$\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} = \mathbb{K}^\dagger \mathbb{K}. \quad (2.167)$$

Then, a standard unitary diagonalization is performed on a Hermitian matrix $\mathbb{K}g\mathbb{K}^\dagger$, resulting set of eigenvectors \mathbb{U} and diagonal eigenvalues matrix \mathbb{L} , such that the first N_m eigenvectors have positive eigenvalues, while the last N_m eigenvectors have negative eigenvalues. The true eigenvalues of $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is given by,

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} = g\mathbb{L}, \quad (2.168)$$

in which all diagonal elements are positive or zero-valued. The transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ are obtained by the relation of

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}} = \mathbb{K}^{-1}\mathbb{U}\Omega^{1/2}. \quad (2.169)$$

Given the $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ and $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, other magnonic properties can be calculated based on the results of diagonalization from the second-order magnon Hamiltonian.

2.8.7 Third- and Fourth-Order Magnon Hamiltonian

Taking all the terms in $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ and performing Fourier transformations to the reciprocal space, the third-order magnon Hamiltonian is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}^{(3)} = & \sum_{\tau, \tau'}^{N_{at}} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q} \in BZ} -\sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau)}}{2}} \left(V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau\tau')}(\mathbf{q}) \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{k}} + V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}\bar{\tau}') }(\mathbf{q}) \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}} \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \right) \\ & - \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau')}}{2}} \left(\left[V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau'\tau)}(\mathbf{p}) \right]^T \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{k}} + \left[V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}'\bar{\tau})}(\mathbf{p}) \right]^T \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}} \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.170)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}$ is the momentum conservation condition from the Fourier transformation, $\bar{\tau} = \tau + N_{at}$, and the $V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau\tau')}$ and $V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}\bar{\tau}')}$ are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau\tau')}(\mathbf{k}) &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')}, \\ V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}\bar{\tau}') }(\mathbf{k}) &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.171)$$

and the element of $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau\tau'}$ is given by Eq. (2.162). In this work, I proposed that for a given set of $\{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}\}$, all the terms in the third-order magnonic field operators can be represented

by a third rank tensor, which is given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(3)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q} \in BZ} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{q}}^{\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(N_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{N}_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.172)$$

where $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)}$ and $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})}$ are $2N_{at} \times 2N_{at}$ matrices whose elements are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau' \tau'')} &= \delta_{\tau' \tau''} V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau \tau')}(\mathbf{q}) + \delta_{\tau \tau''} \left[V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau' \tau)}(\mathbf{p}) \right]^{\text{T}}, \\ \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}' \bar{\tau}'')} &= \delta_{\bar{\tau}' \bar{\tau}''} V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau} \bar{\tau}')(\mathbf{q})} + \delta_{\bar{\tau} \bar{\tau}''} \left[V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}' \bar{\tau})}(\mathbf{p}) \right]^{\text{T}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.173)$$

Using the transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ that obtained from diagonalization of second-order magnon Hamiltonian, the third-rank tensor in Eq. (2.172) is transformed from the basis of $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}$ to the basis of $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, as given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(3)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q} \in BZ} \Psi_{\mathbf{q}}^{\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(m)} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_{\mathbf{p}}^{\dagger} \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(2N_m)} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.174)$$

where the matrix element of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^m$ is expressed as,

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(m)(m' m'')} = \sum_{\tau=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau'=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau''=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\tau m)*} \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\tau' m')*} \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau'' m'')} V_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau' \tau'')}. \quad (2.175)$$

$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(m)(m' m'')}$ represents a three-magnon interaction vertex of a particular process, and all possible three-magnon interactions are shown in Fig. 2.10. In total, there are four distinct processes of three-magnon interactions. In the first interaction, one magnon is splitting into two magnons, which is mathematically represented by term like $\hat{\alpha}_i^{\dagger} \hat{\alpha}_j^{\dagger} \hat{\alpha}_k$ and diagrammatically shown in Fig. 2.10(a). The second interaction corresponds to the reverse process of the first interaction, in which two magnons recombine into one magnon, and this process is mathematically represented by term like $\hat{\alpha}_i \hat{\alpha}_j \hat{\alpha}_k^{\dagger}$ and diagrammatically shown in Fig. 2.10(b). The third interaction corresponds to simultaneous creation of three magnons from a vacuum state, which is mathematically represented by term like $\hat{\alpha}_i^{\dagger} \hat{\alpha}_j^{\dagger} \hat{\alpha}_k^{\dagger}$ and diagrammatically shown in Fig. 2.10(c). The fourth interaction correspond to simultaneous annihilation of three magnons into the vacuum state, which is mathematically represented by term like $\hat{\alpha}_i \hat{\alpha}_j \hat{\alpha}_k$ and diagrammatically shown in Fig. 2.10(d), and this interaction is the reverse process of the third interaction. Note that during all these interactions, the total momentum of created and annihilated magnons is conserved.

Figure 2.10: Feynman diagram of four types of three-magnon interactions, where (a) one magnon is splitting into two magnons, (b) two magnons recombine into one magnon, (c) three magnons are simultaneously created, and (d) three magnons are simultaneously annihilated. For each process, the corresponding interaction vertices are represented by the tensor elements of $C_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}$, as shown in the figure.

The fourth-order magnon Hamiltonian in reciprocal space is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{H}^{(4)} = & \sum_{\tau, \tau'}^{N_{at}} \sum_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4} \left(V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \tau)} (\mathbf{k}_1 - \mathbf{k}_4) \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) \mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) \mathbf{k}_3} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_4} \right. \\
 & - \frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau)}}{S_{(\tau')}}} \left(V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \tau')} (\mathbf{k}_2) \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) \mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_3} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_4} + V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau' \tau)} (\mathbf{k}_3) \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) \mathbf{k}_3} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_4} \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \bar{\tau}')} (\mathbf{k}_2) \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) \mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau') - \mathbf{k}_3} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_4} + V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\bar{\tau} \tau')} (\mathbf{k}_2) \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau) - \mathbf{k}_2} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_3} \hat{a}_{(\tau') \mathbf{k}_4} \right) \right) \\
 & \Delta(\mathbf{K}),
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.176}$$

where $\Delta(\mathbf{K}) = \Delta(\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 - \mathbf{k}_3 - \mathbf{k}_4)$ is a three-dimensional delta Dirac function. $V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau \tau')(\tau'' \tau''')}(\mathbf{k})$ is a fourth-rank tensor element from magnetic interactions and a function of \mathbf{k}_1 , \mathbf{k}_2 , \mathbf{k}_3 , and \mathbf{k}_4 . The coefficient $V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}$ are given as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \tau)}(\mathbf{k}) &= \mathbf{v}_{(\tau)}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau \tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')}, \\
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \tau')}(\mathbf{k}) &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau \tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau')}, \\
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau' \tau)}(\mathbf{k}) &= \left[V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \tau')}(\mathbf{k}) \right]^*, \\
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \bar{\tau}')}(\mathbf{k}) &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau \tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau')}^*, \\
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\bar{\tau} \tau')}(\mathbf{k}) &= \left[V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' \tau')(\tau \bar{\tau}')}(\mathbf{k}) \right]^*
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.177}$$

All the terms in the $\hat{H}^{(4)}$ can be represented by a fourth-rank tensor, which is given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(4)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \mathbb{V}(\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4) \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_4} \Delta(\mathbf{K}), \tag{2.178}$$

where

$$\mathbb{V}(\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(11)} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_3} & \cdots & \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(1\bar{N}_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_3} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\bar{N}_{at}1)} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_3} & \cdots & \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_2}^\dagger \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\bar{N}_{at}\bar{N}_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}_3} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2.179}$$

and the element of matrix $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau \tau')}$ is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau \tau')(\tau'' \tau''')} &= \delta_{\tau \tau'} \left(\delta_{\tau'' \tau'''} \mathbf{v}_{(\tau'')}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau \tau'}(\mathbf{k}_1 - \mathbf{k}_4) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')} - \delta_{\tau'' \tau'} \frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau'')}}{S_{(\tau')}}} \mathbf{u}_{(\tau'')}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau'' \tau'}(\mathbf{k}_2) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau')} \right. \\
 & - \delta_{\tau'' \tau'} \frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau''')}}{S_{(\tau'')}}} \mathbf{u}_{(\tau''')}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau'' \tau'''}(\mathbf{k}_3) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau'')}^* - \delta_{\tau'' \tau'} (\tau' + N_{at}) \frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau'')}}{S_{(\tau')}}} \mathbf{u}_{(\tau'')}^\dagger \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau'' \tau'}(\mathbf{k}_2) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau')}^* \\
 & \left. - \delta_{\tau'' \tau'} (\tau' + N_{at}) \frac{1}{8} \sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau''')}}{S_{(\tau'')}}} \mathbf{u}_{(\tau''')}^T \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{J}}_{\tau'' \tau'''}(\mathbf{k}_2) \mathbf{u}_{(\tau'')} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.180}$$

Using the transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$ that obtained from diagonalization of second-order magnon Hamiltonian, the fourth-rank tensor in Eq. (2.178) is transformed from the basis

of $\mathcal{Y}_{\mathbf{k}}$ to the basis of $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, as given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(4)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}_1}^\dagger \mathbb{C}(\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4) \Psi_{\mathbf{k}_4} \Delta(\mathbf{K}), \quad (2.181)$$

where the tensor element of $\mathbb{C}(\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4)$ is given by,

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(mm')(m''m''')} = \sum_{\tau=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau''=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau'''=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau'=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} Q_{\mathbf{k}_1}^{(\tau m)*} Q_{\mathbf{k}_2}^{(\tau'' m'')*} Q_{\mathbf{k}_3}^{(\tau'''' nm''')} Q_{\mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau' m')} V_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_3, \mathbf{k}_4}^{(\tau \tau')(\tau'' \tau''')}. \quad (2.182)$$

2.8.8 Many-Body Perturbation Green's Function

To take into account the effect of interactions between multiple magnons on the propagation of the unperturbed/free magnons, the many-body Green's function is employed and applied it to the magnons. In particular, the solution of the second-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(2)}$, is taken as the unperturbed magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$, and the time evolution of the unperturbed magnon states under three-magnon interactions, given by the $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, is described by the Green's function [134], defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\tau) &= - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^\beta d\tau_1 \dots \int_0^\beta d\tau_n \langle \mathcal{T} \hat{\alpha}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\tau) \hat{\alpha}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(0) \hat{H}^{(3)}(t_1) \dots \hat{H}^{(3)}(t_n) \rangle, \\ &= G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau) + G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(1)}(\tau) + G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(2)}(\tau) + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (2.183)$$

where τ_n is an imaginary time notation, $\beta = 1/k_B T$, \mathcal{T} is a time ordering operator, and $\hat{\alpha}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\tau) = \exp(-\tau \Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}) \langle n_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^0 \rangle$ is the time evolution of magnon field operators with thermal average distribution $\langle n_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^0 \rangle = 1 / [\exp(\beta \Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}) - 1]$.

By performing Matsubara frequency summation, the zeroth-order Green's function in an imaginary frequency domain is given by,

$$G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(i\omega_n) = - \int_0^\beta d\tau e^{i\omega_n \tau} \langle \mathcal{T} \hat{\alpha}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\tau) \hat{\alpha}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^\dagger(0) \rangle = \frac{1}{\Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}} - i\omega_n}, \quad (2.184)$$

where $\omega_n = 2\pi n/\beta$ with n being an integer. The zeroth-order Green's function describes the time evolution of the magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ from 0 to τ with the energies of the quasiparticle being conserved at $\Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$, and therefore it is called the free magnon propagator. Diagrammatically, it is given by a straight line propagator, as shown in Fig. 2.11(a), where no interaction/scattering occurs between two time-points 0 and τ .

2.8.9 Green's Function under Perturbation from $\hat{H}^{(3)}$

In the case of $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ is considered, the higher order Green's function in Eq. (2.183) needs to be calculated, particularly starting from the second order Green's function $G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(2)}$ that gives largest contribution of $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ on $G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}$. The first-order Green's function, $G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(1)}$, vanishes according to Wick's theorem due to the imbalance number of creation and annihilation

magnonic field operator pairs [134].

By using Wick's theorem, the second-order Green's function, considering three-magnon interactions in Fig. 2.10, is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(2)}(\tau) = & \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)} \int_0^\beta d\tau_1 \int_0^\beta d\tau_2 G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau - \tau_1) G_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}(\tau_1 - \tau_2) G_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}(\tau_1 - \tau_2) G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau_2) \\
 & + C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(b)} \int_0^\beta d\tau_1 \int_0^\beta d\tau_2 G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau - \tau_1) G_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}(\tau_1 - \tau_2) G_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau_2 - \tau_1) G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau_2) \\
 & + C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(c)} \int_0^\beta d\tau_1 \int_0^\beta d\tau_2 G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau - \tau_1) G_{(n)-\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}(\tau_2 - \tau_1) G_{(l)-\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau_2 - \tau_1) G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau_2),
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.185}$$

where the three terms in Eq. (2.185) represent three distinct process occur between time interval 0 and τ , and the Feynman diagrams of these terms are shown in Fig. 2.11(b)-2.11(d) for first, second, and third term of Eq. (2.185), respectively. The first term in Eq. (2.185) represents a process in which the magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ decays into virtual states $(n)\mathbf{q}$ and $(l)\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}$, and the resulted states recombine into the original states $(m)\mathbf{k}$, as shown in Fig. 2.11(b). The second term in Eq. (2.185) represents a collision process between magnon of states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ and an excited magnon state $(l)\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{k}$, and since there are no thermally excited magnons at zero temperature, this process has no contribution to the time evolution of magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ at zero temperature, as shall be proved later. The third term in Eq. (2.185) represents a process in which the magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ is annihilated with other two magnon states and later created again from simultaneous creation governed by process in Fig. 2.10(c). The coefficient $C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)}$, $C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(b)}$, and $C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(c)}$ are the combination of interaction vertices or tensor elements in Eq. (2.175) that correspond to three-magnon interactions at each given time point, τ_n , in Fig. (2.11). For instance, the $C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)}$ is obtained from multiple combinations of (\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}) that correspond to the three-magnon interaction in Fig. 2.10(a), and this is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{(m,l,n)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)} = & \left| \tilde{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(m \rightarrow n, l)} + \left(\tilde{C}_{-\mathbf{k} \rightarrow -\mathbf{q}, -\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{m} \rightarrow \bar{n}, \bar{l})} \right)^* \right|^2, \\
 \tilde{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(m \rightarrow n, l)} = & \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}}^{(n)(l, m)} + \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}}^{(l)(n, m)} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{q} \rightarrow -\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{m})(l, \bar{n})} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{q} \rightarrow \mathbf{p}, -\mathbf{k}}^{(l)(\bar{m}, \bar{n})} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{p} \rightarrow -\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}}^{(\bar{m})(n, \bar{l})} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}, -\mathbf{k}}^{(n)(\bar{m}, \bar{l})},
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.186}$$

with $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}$, and similar notation with opposite sign applies to $\tilde{C}_{-\mathbf{k} \rightarrow -\mathbf{q}, -\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{m} \rightarrow \bar{n}, \bar{l})}$.

Our next task is to find the correction to the $\Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$ due to these processes, and this corresponds to finding the expression of self-energies in the frequency domain Green's function. By applying Matsubara summation on Green's function in Eq. (2.185) and performing analytic continuation ($i\omega_n \rightarrow \omega + i0$), the Green's function becomes the so-

called Dyson's equation, which is given as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega) &= G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\omega) + (G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\omega))^2 \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega) + \dots \\
 &\approx \frac{G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\omega)}{1 - G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\omega) \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega)} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}} + \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega) - \omega - i0},
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.187}$$

where the Eq. (2.184) has been invoked in the last line, and the $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega)$ is called a self-energy, which is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega) &= \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(a)}(\omega) + \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(b)}(\omega) + \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(c)}(\omega), \\
 \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(a)}(\omega) &= \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} \frac{C_{(m,n,l)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)}}{\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + \Omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}} - \omega - i0} \left(1 + \langle n_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^0 \rangle + \langle n_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}^0 \rangle\right), \\
 \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(b)}(\omega) &= \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} \frac{C_{(m,n,l)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(b)}}{\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} - \Omega_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}} - \omega - i0} \left(\langle n_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^0 \rangle - \langle n_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}^0 \rangle\right), \\
 \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(c)}(\omega) &= - \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} \frac{C_{(m,n,l)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(c)}}{\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + \Omega_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}} + \omega - i0} \left(\langle n_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^0 \rangle + \langle n_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}^0 \rangle + 1\right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.188}$$

From the above equation, the $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(b)}(\omega)$ vanishes at zero temperature as $\langle n_{(n)\mathbf{q}}^0 \rangle \rightarrow 0$ and $\langle n_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}^0 \rangle \rightarrow 0$ for $T \rightarrow 0$ K, while the $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(c)}(\omega)$ has no imaginary part since $\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}}$ and $\Omega_{(l)\mathbf{q}-\mathbf{k}}$ are always positive-valued as shown in Eq. (2.168), and therefore does not contribute to the magnon damping [135]. In this work, $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(a)}(\omega)$ will be mainly considered, and the effect of $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(b)}(\omega)$ and $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(c)}(\omega)$ is omitted.

Numerically, the off-shell Dyson equation is iteratively solved to obtain the energy renormalization/correction and magnon damping in Eq. (2.187), as proposed by Ref. [33]. Suppose that the Dyson equation has a solution (or pole) at a complex energy, $\omega = \tilde{\Omega}_{(m)\mathbf{k}} - i\Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$, where $\Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}} > 0$ and represents magnon damping at states $(m)\mathbf{k}$. The magnon energy, including the energy renormalization from self-energies, and the magnon damping at states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\Omega}_{(m)\mathbf{k}} &= \Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}} + \text{Re} \left[\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega^*) \right], \\
 \Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}} &= -\text{Im} \left[\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega^*) \right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.189}$$

where energy renormalization and magnon damping are given by the modified zero temperature self-energy [33], expressed as,

$$\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}(\omega^*) = \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} C_{(m,n,l)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}^{(a)} \frac{\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + \Omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\Omega}_{(m)\mathbf{k}} - i\Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}}{(\Omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + \Omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}} - \tilde{\Omega}_{(m)\mathbf{k}})^2 + \Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^2}. \tag{2.190}$$

This self-energy is computed iteratively, and the real part is added to the free magnon energies $\Omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$, while the imaginary part is taken as the magnon damping $\Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$. The new

Figure 2.11: Feynman diagram of Green's function that describes the time evolution of magnon states $(m)\mathbf{k}$ from 0 to τ . Feynman diagram that represents (a) $G_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(0)}(\tau)$ or free magnon, (b) first, (c) second, and (d) third term in Eq. (2.185).

magnon energies $\tilde{\Omega}_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$ and magnon damping $\Gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$ are then used again to compute the self-energy in the next iteration until the convergence is achieved.

Chapter 3

Benchmarking the Magnetic Force Theorem and Linear Spin-Wave Theory in $3d$ Transition-Metal Monoxides

3.1 Introduction

Antiferromagnetic insulator $3d$ transition-metal monoxides (TMOs) in bulk, namely MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO, have gained renewed attention for their antiferromagnetic resonance (AFMR) frequencies in THz regimes [41–47]. From experiments, such as far-infrared or magnetic susceptibility measurements, the AFMR frequencies are determined from the peak of absorption spectra. Additionally, the width of the peak commonly represents magnetic damping. Far-infrared spectroscopy [42] for single-crystal MnO observed AFMR frequency as large as 0.82 THz, while spin flop measurement [43] observed a lower frequency of 0.05 THz. Inelastic neutron scattering for wustite FeO in multi-domain structure [44] yielded AFMR frequencies of 0.75 and 4.59 THz. For CoO, far-infrared spectroscopy [45] showed multiple AFMR frequencies corresponding to 6.47, 6.63, and 7.74 THz, while the inelastic neutron scattering [46] on single crystal CoO showed AFMR frequencies of 4.83 and 9.67 THz. Light-scattering measurement [47] on NiO yielded two AFMR frequencies around 0.14 and 1.28 THz. The magnetic damping of high-quality grown NiO can be one order of magnitude higher than that of yttrium iron garnet [136–138]. Recently, modulations of AFMR frequencies in NiO by cation substitution with magnetic and non-magnetic impurities were achieved [138, 139].

The magnetism of $3d$ TMOs, including strength of spin-exchange constants, magnetic easy axis (plane), and origin of magnetic anisotropy, depends on the TM cations due to different electron occupations. For MnO and NiO, the magnetization favours to be within (111) plane, where the main origin is attributed to the magnetic dipolar interactions (MDI) [140]. On the other hand, the magnetic easy axes in FeO and CoO are out-of-plane with

respect to (111) plane, due to the strong spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effect [40]. Density functional theory calculations also revealed that different strengths of hybridization between TM cations and oxygen anions result in variation of spin-exchange constants among 3d TMOs [141], which gives rise to varying Néel temperatures, as observed from experiments. Despite the abundance of investigations on the magnetic properties, there is still a lack in understanding these effects on the AFMR frequencies, which are essential for designing AFM materials for THz-frequency signal applications.

In this chapter, the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions, magneto-crystalline anisotropy (MCA) induced by SOC, and MDIs on the Néel temperatures and AFMR frequencies in 3d TMOs is investigated. Additionally, the developed magnetic force theorem and linear spin-wave theory, as presented thoroughly in Chapter 2, are also benchmarked in these 3d TMOs by using the Néel temperatures and AFMR frequencies as the benchmark physical properties. First, the isotropic spin-exchange interactions, obtained via magnetic force theorem, are employed to calculate the Néel temperatures of each 3d TMO. Second, effects of the magnetic easy axes and magnetic parameters variation among the 3d TMOs, particularly those contributing to the magnetic anisotropy, on the AFMR frequencies are addressed. Magnetic anisotropy, consisting of MDIs and MCA induced by SOC, are taken into account in the spin Hamiltonian model based on linear spin-wave theory, in addition to isotropic spin-exchange interaction. Using calculated magnetic parameters, the magnon dispersions and the AFMR frequencies of 3d TMOs are calculated.

3.2 Calculation Models

A cubic rock-salt structure and rhombohedral lattice vectors for the TMOs in antiferromagnetic ordering type-II (AFM-II) was employed in this study, as shown in Fig. 1.6. GGA+ U correction was employed to treat strongly-correlated electrons in d orbitals of TM cations, and U_{eff} of 4.0, 4.0, 3.0, and 2.5 eV were used, based on previous works in TMOs [118, 142–145]. The $7 \times 7 \times 7$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh was used for Brillouin zone (BZ) sampling that ensures the convergence of spin-exchange constants, while $35 \times 35 \times 35$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh was used for the BZ sampling to obtain the MCA constants and magnetic moment of TM cations. Muffin tin spheres radii of 1.005 and 0.952 Å were employed for TM and O atoms, respectively. For spherical harmonics expansion within the muffin tin spheres, the angular momentum cut-offs l_{max} of 8 and 6 were used for TM and O muffin tin spheres, respectively. Plane-wave cut-off $|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}| \leq 7.37 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was used for plane wave expansion in reciprocal space. The lattice constants of 4.47, 4.317, 4.259, and 4.194 Å for MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO, respectively, were obtained from geometry optimization of each TMOs in magnetic primitive unit cell via Murnaghan equation.

The spin interactions in each TMOs is modeled by spin Hamiltonian given by,

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{i,j} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \overleftrightarrow{J}_{ij}^{\text{Total}} \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\overleftrightarrow{J}_{ij}^{\text{Total}}$ is given by,

$$\overleftrightarrow{J}_{ij}^{\text{Total}} = J_{ij}^{\text{ex}} \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} + \delta_{ij} \mathbb{K}_i^{\text{MCA}} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|^3} \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} - \frac{3}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|^5} \mathbf{r}_{ij} \mathbf{r}_{ij}^{\text{T}} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$\mathbb{K}_i^{\text{MCA}} = \begin{pmatrix} K_i^{\text{MCA},x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_i^{\text{MCA},y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.3)$$

The first term in Eq. (3.2) represents the spin-exchange interactions with isotropic spin-exchange constants, J_{ij}^{ex} , as magnetic parameters. The anisotropic spin-exchange interactions is omitted due to negligible SOC effects in the O atoms, and MCA is assumed to be locally driven by the SOC effects in the TM cations. The second term, represents the single-ion MCA constants along transversal directions, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} axes, parameterized by $K_i^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K_i^{\text{MCA},y}$, respectively. The third term with parentheses represents the MDI with magnetic moment of TM cations as the magnetic parameters. In this term, the \mathbf{r}_{ij} represents a vector that connects two magnetic moments, and consequently gives rise to magnetic anisotropy via second term in the parentheses. The spin Hamiltonian in Eq. (3.1) is solved by using the linear spin-wave theory, as explained in details in Sec. 2.8.

The Néel temperature of the bulk TMOs is obtained via mean-field approximation, as the largest eigenvalues of the following matrix [146],

$$\Theta_{\nu\nu'} = -\frac{2}{3k_B} J_{\nu\nu'}^{\text{ex}}(0), \quad (3.4)$$

where the element of this matrix is given by,

$$J_{\nu\nu'}^{\text{ex}}(k) = \mathbf{v}_{(\tau)}^{\text{T}} \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')} \sum_j^{N_{uc}} J_{0+\tau, \mathbf{R}_j+\tau'}^{\text{ex}} \exp(\mathbf{i}k \cdot \mathbf{d}_{0(\tau), \mathbf{R}_j(\tau')}), \quad (3.5)$$

with the notation explained in Sec. 2.7 and Sec. 2.8.

3.3 Isotropic Spin-Exchange Constants

The isotropic spin-exchange constants, J_{ij}^{ex} , were plotted as a function of magnetic moment-pair interactions distance, r_{ij} , in Fig. 3.1(a), 3.1(b), 3.1(c), 3.1(d) for MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO, respectively. The first- and second-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, dominate the isotropic spin-exchange constants in all TMOs and give rise to the antiferromagnetic order, as indicated by their dominant positive sign. The $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ in the present work also agree reasonably well with those obtained from experiments, as show in Table 3.1 in terms of sign and magnitude.

The trend of first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$, shows that the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ in MnO exhibits antiferromagnetic coupling, while the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ in FeO, CoO, and NiO exhibits ferromagnetic coupling. By the direct spin-exchange interactions mechanism, the antiferromagnetic coupling of the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ in MnO can qualitatively be explained by half-filled Mn d orbitals, i.e., all electron occupying the d orbitals belong to the majority spin channel. The half-filled Mn d orbitals only allows electron with opposite spin from one Mn cation to hop to another Mn cation due to Pauli exclusion rule, and this is only possible if the two Mn cations are antiferromagnetic aligned. With an increasing electron occupation of minority spin channel from MnO to NiO, more electrons from the minority spin channel in one TM cation are allowed to hop to another TM cations by the Pauli exclusion rule, even if the two first-nearest neighboring TM cations are ferromagnetically coupled. In the crystal structure, The two ferromagnetically coupled first-nearest neighboring TM cations belong to the same (111) plane, as shown by blue and red semi-transparent planes in Fig. 1.6.

The second-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants, $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, exhibits a trend of increasing magnitude from MnO to NiO, in which occupation of electron in minority spin channel grows from MnO and NiO. In the FeO, CoO, and NiO, the $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ becomes the dominant isotropic spin-exchange interactions that drives the antiferromagnetic order, with magnitude of $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ reach 3.5 and 9 times larger than that of $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ in CoO and NiO, respectively. The origin of increasing $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ trend from MnO to NiO can be explained from the increasing probability of TM-O-TM hopping between the electrons in the minority spin channel of

Figure 3.1: The isotropic spin-exchange constants, J_{ij}^{ex} in meV, as a function of interaction distance r_{ij} in Å, for (a) MnO, (b) FeO, (c) CoO, and (d) NiO. The first- and second-nearest neighbor isotropic spin-exchange constants are indicated by $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, respectively. The negative (positive) sign of the J_{ij}^{ex} corresponds to the ferromagnetic (antiferromagnetic) alignment between a pair of spins.

TM cations, as the electron occupation number in minority spin channel increases. The second-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants constitute linear 180° super-exchange interaction TM-O-TM, where there are two possible orbital hopping mechanism, i.e., TM $e_g \xleftrightarrow{pd\sigma}$ O $p \xleftrightarrow{pd\sigma}$ TM e_g and TM $t_{2g} \xleftrightarrow{pd\pi}$ O $p \xleftrightarrow{pd\pi}$ TM t_{2g} , as shown in Fig. 3.2(a) and 3.2(b), respectively. Since the $pd\sigma$ bond is stronger than the $pd\pi$ bond, the dominant orbital hopping mechanism is the TM $e_g \xleftrightarrow{pd\sigma}$ O $p \xleftrightarrow{pd\sigma}$ TM e_g . Furthermore, due to the two electrons in one O p orbital have opposite spins, only antiferromagnetic configuration between two TM cations is allowed to form by the Pauli exclusion principles, as shown in Fig. 3.3(a) and 3.3(b) for antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic configurations, respectively. The increasing occupation on TM t_{2g} states in minority spin channels from MnO to NiO causes the TM e_g states in the minority spin channels being closer to Fermi level, and this lowers the energy requirement for electron hopping between O and TM cations. As the consequence, this leads to the increasing trend of J_2^{ex} from MnO and NiO.

Using the isotropic spin-exchange interactions, the Néel temperature of each bulk TMO is calculated and given in the Table 3.2. The Néel temperature of each bulk TMO in the present work gives a good quantitative good agreement with that in experiments and exhibits an increasing trend from MnO to NiO. The increasing trend of the Néel temperature from MnO to NiO is mainly attributed to the second-nearest neighbor spin-exchange interactions, $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, that stabilize the antiferromagnetic order along [111] direction. On the other hand, the first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange interactions, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$, consist of six parallel and six anti-parallel alignment of two magnetic TM cations, which cancel each other and has no total contribution to the Néel temperature.

Table 3.1: Isotropic spin-exchange constants between first- and second-nearest neighboring transition-metal (TM) atoms, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, respectively, from present work and experiments (in the unit of meV).

TMO	$J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$		$J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$	
	Present Work	Exp.	Present Work	Exp.
MnO	2.26	2.64 [41]	2.02	2.79 [41]
FeO	-2.49	-1.84 [44]	3.59	3.24 [44]
CoO	-1.88	-1.07 [44]	6.76	6.30 [46]
NiO	-0.18	-0.69 [140]	9.16	9.51 [140]

Table 3.2: Néel temperatures, T_N , of the 3d transition-metal monoxides (TMOs) from present work and experiments (in the unit of Kelvin).

TMO	T_N	
	Present Work	Exp.
MnO	84.95	120.0 [147]
FeO	169.86	198.0 [148]
CoO	290.12	289.0 [149]
NiO	422.04	523.0 [150]

Figure 3.2: The 180° super-exchange hopping path between two second-nearest neighboring TM cations mediated by the O p orbitals, in which TM (a) t_{2g} and (b) e_g states are involved in the super-exchange. The hopping between t_{2g} states are mediated by $pd\pi$ bond, while that between e_g states are mediated by $pd\sigma$ bond.

Figure 3.3: (a) Energy level diagram for orbital hopping mechanism between d orbitals in two TM cations and degenerate p orbital in an O atoms in antiferromagnetic configurations. (b) Similar energy level diagram for ferromagnetic configurations. In (b), one hopping mechanism between TM d orbitals and O p orbitals is prohibited by the Pauli exclusion rule.

3.4 Magnetic Anisotropy

Two mechanisms that leads to magnetic anisotropy in the TMOs, namely the MDI and the MCA from SOC effects, were calculated as a function of an angle, where $(\theta, \varphi) = (0^\circ, 0^\circ)$ correspond to the in-plane $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ direction, $(\theta, \varphi) = (90^\circ, 0^\circ)$ correspond to the out-of-plane $[111]$ direction, and $(\theta, \varphi) = (90^\circ, 90^\circ)$ correspond to the in-plane $[\bar{1}10]$ direction, as schematically given by Fig. 3.4(a). Undistorted rock-salt structures of the TMOs are also assumed, in which the effect from Jahn-Teller distortions, that change the energy level splitting of TM d orbitals and hence the magnetic anisotropy, is ignored.

The MDI energy is plotted in Fig. 3.4(b), and the in-plane $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ direction gives the lowest MDI energy, while the out-of-plane $[111]$ direction gives the maximum MDI energy in all TMOs. The MDI energy of MnO in the $[111]$ is highest among all TMOs, and the MDI energy decreases as the occupation number of minority spin channel of d orbitals increases from MnO to NiO. The decrease of the MDI energy from MnO and NiO in the $[111]$ directions is mainly attributed to the decrease of magnetic moment of TM cations from the increase occupation of minority spin channel in d orbitals. The MDI energy along the in-plane (111) directions, i.e., $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2] \rightarrow [\bar{1}10] \rightarrow [11\bar{2}]$, were also calculated and no variation of the MDI energy in all the TMOs is found.

On the other hand, the MCA energy exhibits different trend between the TMOs, as seen in Fig. 3.4(c). The MCA energy of MnO and NiO shows no variation as the magnetic moment direction varied from $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ to $[111]$ directions, while that of FeO and CoO shows opposite variation. The MCA energy of FeO shows a minimum value along the in-plane $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ direction, while that of CoO shows a minimum value along out-of-plane $[111]$ direction. Additionally, the magnitude of MCA energy along $[111]$ direction in CoO is larger than that of MDI energy along the same direction, which implies that the magnetic anisotropy is dominated by the MCA energy rather than by the MDI energy. The MCA energy along the in-plane (111) directions, i.e., $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2] \rightarrow [\bar{1}10] \rightarrow [11\bar{2}]$ was also calculated, and no variation of MCA energy in all the TMOs is found. In the MnO and NiO, the MCA does not produce significant contribution to the magnetic anisotropy from the half-occupied and fully occupied t_{2g} states in Mn and Ni cations, respectively [40, 151]. On the other hand, the MCA energy in FeO and CoO is attributed to the SOC effect from the electrons in partially occupied t_{2g} states [40]. Octahedral crystal field in Fe and Co cations splits the d orbitals into triplet t_{2g} and duplet e_g states. The minority electrons in the partially occupied t_{2g} states delocalize between the t_{2g} states, which form strong direction dependence of orbital angular momentum [40, 152] and are coupled to their spins via SOC. Coulomb repulsion between these electrons and O anions induces the MCA energy, and the repulsion is minimized when the spin is orienting in out-of-plane with respect to (111) plane in CoO, and within the (111) plane in the FeO.

In the experiments, the FeO and CoO suffer from a monoclinic distortion that changes the magnetic easy axis direction, while the MnO and NiO suffer from a rhombohedral distortion that breaks the degeneracy in magnetic easy plane (111) direction [40, 153–156]. The MCA energy of the FeO and CoO under monoclinic distortion obtained from the

experiments [155, 156] as a function of angles were calculated and illustrated in Fig. 3.4(a). The MCA energy under monoclinic distortion are shown in Fig. 3.4(d) and Fig. 3.4(e) as a function of θ for fixed values of $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and 90° , respectively. Using the angle-dependence of MCA energy of FeO and CoO, the magnetic easy axes, \mathbf{z} , under the monoclinic distortion are summarized in the Table 3.3, in terms of (θ, φ) defined in Fig. 3.4(a). The magnetic easy axis of FeO is located near the $[\bar{1}10]$ direction, while that of CoO is located between $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ and $[111]$ directions. Then, the transversal directions \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , are chosen as such the MCA constant between the transversal and magnetic easy axis direction yields the largest magnitude, and the MCA constants are given by,

$$K_i^{\text{MCA},x} = E^{\text{MCA}}(\mathbf{x}) - E^{\text{MCA}}(\mathbf{z}), \quad K_i^{\text{MCA},y} = E^{\text{MCA}}(\mathbf{y}) - E^{\text{MCA}}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (3.6)$$

Table 3.3 also shows the MCA constants for all TMOs calculated from the above equation. The monoclinic distortions in the FeO and CoO give rise to the O anions being not equally positioned at the edge of octahedral nearest neighbors, and the Jahn-Teller distortions induce different crystalline electric field splitting in Fe and Co cations. Consequently, the MCA energy is no longer minimized at direction not exactly within the (111) plane for FeO and out-of-plane $[111]$ directions for CoO, as in the undistorted case.

Figure 3.4: (a) Crystallographic directions on (111) plane, where three orthogonal axes and magnetic moment rotation angles, (θ, φ) are indicated. (b) Magnetic dipolar interactions (MDIs) and magnetocrystalline anisotropy (MCA) energy of a given $(\theta, 0^\circ)$, relative to those of $(0^\circ, 0^\circ)$. The MCA energy for a distorted monoclinic FeO and CoO, for (d) $(\theta, 0^\circ)$ and (e) $(\theta, 90^\circ)$, relative to that of $(0^\circ, 0^\circ)$. In all figures, red triangles, orange squares, green pentagons, and blue hexagons represent magnetic anisotropy energy of MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO, respectively.

Table 3.3: Magnetic easy axes of all TMOs, \mathbf{z} , in terms of angle (θ, φ) defined in Fig. 3.4(a). The \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are also given for each TMO and chosen as such it yields maximum magnitude and diagonal matrix form of the MCA constants, $K_i^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K_i^{\text{MCA},y}$ (in the unit of meV).

TMO	$\mathbf{z}(\theta, \varphi)$	$\mathbf{x}(\theta, \varphi)$	$\mathbf{y}(\theta, \varphi)$	$K_i^{\text{MCA},x}$ (meV)	$K_i^{\text{MCA},y}$ (meV)
MnO	$(0.00^\circ, 0.00^\circ)$	$(90.00^\circ, 0.00^\circ)$	$(90.00^\circ, 90.00^\circ)$	0.0	0.0
FeO	$(89.98^\circ, -89.95^\circ)$	$(72.95^\circ, 0.05^\circ)$	$(17.04^\circ, 0.01^\circ)$	0.92	1.79
CoO	$(34.36^\circ, 0.11^\circ)$	$(89.94^\circ, -89.97^\circ)$	$(55.64^\circ, 0.01^\circ)$	0.95	1.64
NiO	$(0.00^\circ, 0.00^\circ)$	$(90.00^\circ, 0.00^\circ)$	$(90.00^\circ, 90.00^\circ)$	0.0	0.0

Table 3.4: Magnetic anisotropy energy from the MDI, $K_i^{\text{MDI},x}$ and $K_i^{\text{MDI},y}$, and the total magnetic anisotropy, $K_i^{\text{MA},x}$ and $K_i^{\text{MA},y}$, of the distorted monoclinic FeO and CoO in the unit of meV. The \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} is given by Table 3.3.

TMO	$K_i^{\text{MDI},x}$	$K_i^{\text{MDI},y}$	$K_i^{\text{MA},x}$	$K_i^{\text{MA},y}$
FeO	0.31	0.03	1.23	1.82
CoO	-0.06	0.13	0.89	1.77

Figure 3.5: Magnon dispersions for (a) MnO, (b) FeO, (c) CoO, and (d) NiO. Two magnon modes, higher (α mode) and lower (β mode) frequencies, are represented by solid and dashed lines, respectively. Insets show the magnon dispersions near Γ .

3.5 Magnon Frequencies and Antiferromagnetic Resonance Frequencies

3.5.1 Magnon dispersion

The magnon dispersions of all 3d TMOs are shown in Fig. 3.5. Since two TM cations in the unit cell constitute an antiferromagnetic structure, two magnon modes may be excited, labeled as $\omega_{(\alpha)\mathbf{k}}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\mathbf{k}}$ for higher and lower magnon frequencies. These modes correspond to orthogonal magnetization precession trajectories [151], as seen from the right-side of Fig. 3.6. At wave-vectors near zone boundary, \mathbf{T} , the frequency increases from MnO to NiO, which corresponds to the increase of magnitude of $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ from MnO to NiO, as suggested by the previous *ab initio* calculations [157]. At wave-vectors near Γ ($\mathbf{k} \simeq 0$), the $\omega_{(\alpha)\mathbf{k}}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\mathbf{k}}$ of FeO and CoO become higher than those of MnO and NiO, as shown in the insets of Fig. 3.5. These are attributed to the non-zero MCA constants in FeO and CoO, which are not the case for MnO and NiO (see Table 3.3). Moreover, the frequency gap between $\omega_{(\alpha)\mathbf{k}}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\mathbf{k}}$ for CoO is wider than that for FeO.

Figure 3.6: Magnetic moment precession in α and β modes for (a) MnO and NiO, (b) FeO, and (c) CoO. The right-side figures represent the magnetic moment precession seen from the magnetic easy axis of each TMO. The orthogonal crystallographic directions such as $[111]$, $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$, and $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ are also indicated in the figures. Blue (red) ellipses represent the magnetic moment precession in the α (β) mode.

Table 3.5: Comparison of AFMR frequencies of the present work (at 0 K) and experiments (at low temperatures) in unit of THz. Although experiments of far-infrared absorption spectra in CoO resulted in three frequency peaks [45], only the two distinguishable frequency peaks are listed.

	Present work		Experiments	
	$\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$	$\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$	$\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$	$\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$
MnO	0.84	0.00	0.82 [42]	0.05[43]
FeO	3.45	2.92	4.59 [44]	0.75 [44]
CoO	4.96	3.71	7.74 [45]	6.63 [45]
			9.67 [46]	4.83 [46]
NiO	1.19	0.00	1.28 [47]	0.14 [47]

3.5.2 AFMR frequencies

In Table 3.5, the calculated AFMR frequencies, which correspond to $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$, are compared with experiment results. For the MnO and NiO, whose $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ are zero, the calculated $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$'s are 0.75 and 1.19 THz, respectively, quantitatively consistent with those of experiments [41, 42, 47]. The $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$'s are zero, while small values were reported experimentally. For the FeO and CoO, whose the $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ are not negligible, the α (β) mode is underestimated (overestimated) in FeO and both modes are underestimated in CoO.

Next, the influence of magnetic parameters, particularly MCA- and MDI-related parameters, on the AFMR frequencies is discussed. The MnO and NiO, where the magnetic anisotropy is dominated by the MDI, and the FeO and CoO, where the magnetic anisotropy is dominated by the MCA are separately discussed.

MnO and NiO

The magnetic moment precession trajectory of the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ is shown in Fig. 3.6(a), in which the the semi-major axis of the precession trajectory for α mode coincides with [111]. Since the μ_{TM} parameterizes the strength of MDI-induced magnetic anisotropy between $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ and [111], the dynamics of magnetic moments in the α mode is sensitive to the change of μ_{TM} . On the other hand, the magnetic moment precession trajectory of the $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ is also shown in Fig. 3.6(a), where the semi-major axis of β mode coincides with $[\bar{1}10]$. In an undistorted rock-salt structure MnO and NiO, the MDI energy are degenerate within the (111) plane, which implies no magnetic anisotropy from the MDI energy observed between $[\bar{1}\bar{1}2]$ and $[\bar{1}10]$ directions. Therefore, the AFMR frequencies in the β mode has zero frequency due to no magnetic anisotropy to break continuous rotational symmetry within the (111) plane from the MDI, and this is called as a Goldstone mode (gapless magnon frequency relative to zero frequency)

In the real samples of MnO and NiO, however, they suffer from rhombohedral distortion during the magnetic phase transition from paramagnetic to AFM-II phase [39, 40, 153, 158, 159]. The rhombohedral distortion [40] is introduced in the AFMR frequencies calculations, and the results are given in Table 3.6. The μ_{TM} and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ is assumed to

Table 3.6: First-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants, $J_{(1)}^p$ and $J_{(1)}^{ap}$, MCA constant $K^{\text{MCA},y}$, and calculated AFMR frequencies, $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$, under the rhombohedral distortion.

	$(J_{(1)}^p, J_{(1)}^{ap})$ (meV)	$K^{\text{MCA},y}$ (meV)	Present work with distortion	
			$\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ (THz)	$\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ (THz)
MnO	(1.81, 2.30)	0.00	0.84	0.03
NiO	(-0.20, -0.18)	5×10^{-4}	1.19	0.11

not change under the distortion. According to Ref. [158], the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ contribution can be decomposed into $J_{(1)}^p$ and $J_{(1)}^{ap}$, where $J_{(1)}^p$ represents parallel coupling between the sites on the same (111) plane, and $J_{(1)}^{ap}$ represents anti-parallel coupling between the sites on the adjacent (111) plane. For these calculations, the $J_{(1)}^p$ and $J_{(1)}^{ap}$ are taken from Refs. [140, 160]. The $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ results in 0.03 THz for MnO and 0.11 THz for NiO, as shown in Table 3.6, due to distortion effect that breaks the degeneracy of the MDI energy between $[11\bar{2}]$ and $[\bar{1}10]$. In other words, the rhombohedral distortion breaks the continuous rotational symmetry within the (111) plane, which allows finite AFMR frequencies/gapped magnon frequency to appear. One can see that the $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ differs by an order of magnitude between MnO and NiO in both calculations (Table 3.6) and experiments (Table 3.5): The distortion affects the \mathbf{r}_{ij} in the MDI spin Hamiltonian of the MnO and NiO, and additionally the $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ in the NiO. Note that the value of $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ is negligibly changed by the distortion effect in NiO, while a reduction of $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ is apparent in MnO.

FeO and CoO

In contrast to the MnO and NiO, the FeO and CoO exhibit non-zero MCA contributions (see $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ in Table 3.3), and hence the magnetic anisotropy in these materials is given by a competition between MCA and MDI terms. The dependence of magnon frequency gap, as well as the magnitude of magnon frequencies, in FeO and CoO can be explained by considering magnetic anisotropy energy, E^{MA} , induced by the MCA and MDI, since the magnon frequencies ($\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$) are proportional to energy terms containing $(S_i^y)^2$ and $(S_i^z)^2$ in the E^{MA} [161]. The E^{MA} is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^{\text{MA}} &= \sum_i K_i^{\text{MA},x} (S_i^x)^2 + K_i^{\text{MA},y} (S_i^y)^2, \\
 &\approx \sum_i (K_i^{\text{MA},y} - K_i^{\text{MA},x}) (S_i^y)^2 - K_i^{\text{MA},x} (S_i^z)^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

and the contribution of the MDI and MCA to the total magnetic anisotropy is written as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_i^{\text{MA},x} &= K_i^{\text{MCA},x} + K_i^{\text{MDI},x}, \\
 K_i^{\text{MA},y} &= K_i^{\text{MCA},y} + K_i^{\text{MDI},y}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

In the last line of Eq. (3.7), the first term opens the frequency gap between $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$, and the second term shifts in frequency for both $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ [161, 162]. The MDI energy of the FeO and CoO in \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} directions were also calculated, as shown

by Table 3.4. Since the $K_i^{\text{MA},y} - K_i^{\text{MA},x}$ in the CoO is larger than that in the FeO, the magnon frequency gap of CoO is wider than that of FeO.

In the FeO, the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ in the present calculations are underestimated and overestimated, respectively, compared to those in the experiments, as shown in the Table 3.5. Based on the magnetic moment precession trajectories of the α and β mode in Fig. 3.6(b), the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ depends on the magnetic anisotropy $K_i^{\text{MA},y}$, while the $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ depends on the magnetic anisotropy $K_i^{\text{MA},x}$. To reproduce the experimental value of $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ in FeO, the $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ is needed to increase up to around 3.19 meV, while the $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ is needed to decrease down to around 0.01 meV for FeO. Using these values of $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},x}$, the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ is enhanced to 4.50 THz, while the $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ is reduced to 0.79 THz.

In the CoO, both the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ in the present calculations are underestimated, compared to those in experiments, as seen in Table 3.5. From the magnetic moment precession trajectories of the α and β mode of CoO in Fig. 3.6(c), the $K_i^{\text{MA},y}$ ($K_i^{\text{MA},x}$) determines the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ ($\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$). The experimental values of $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ can be obtained by using the $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ as large as 3.73 and 3.04 meV, respectively, which results in the $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$ being 7.58 and 6.82 THz, respectively.

The $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ and $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ in the present work include the contribution of lattice distortion by Jahn-Teller effect, while the significance of this Jahn-Teller effect is very sensitive to the choice of Hubbard parameter U in GGA+ U approximation. A different choice of U tends to promote the stretching or contraction along [001] for FeO and CoO, both of which lower the site symmetry around Fe and Co cations in the system, and thereby altering the $K^{\text{MCA},x}$ associated with $\omega_{(\beta)\Gamma}$, as well as $K^{\text{MCA},y}$ associated with $\omega_{(\alpha)\Gamma}$. Additional comments on difficulties to obtain a quantitative agreement with experiments are also given as follow. The FeO in the experiment [44] is a non-stoichiometric sample (Fe_{1-x}O with $x = 0.07$), which could have different magnetic anisotropy strength from that of stoichiometric one due to a reduced symmetry. An inclusion of orbital moment in the MDI does not reproduce the experimental results, since the orbital moment is small (for instance, $0.12 \mu_B$ for Fe in FeO [40]). Rather, the treatment of SOC in the single spin states of Holstein-Primakoff transformation is more important. The SOC gives rise not only to the anisotropic field acting on the total spin, but also to spin-splitting, as indicated by the explicit form of SOC $\lambda \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{S}$ [46], where λ is an SOC strength that depends on the TM cations. The magnitude of the splitting, represented by the λ , can reach up to 12.0 meV for CoO case [46]. According to Ref. [46], the inclusion of spin-splitting effects in second quantization method successfully fits the magnon dispersion from inelastic neutron scattering in CoO, which is not taken into account in the present study, since it requires total angular momentum quantum numbers as basis in Eq. (2.145), (2.151), and (2.152). The inclusion of total angular momentum quantum number for magnon operators leads to the generalized linear spin-wave theory, called flavor-wave theory [163–165].

3.6 Concluding Remarks

In this chapter, the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions, MCA induced by SOC, and MDIs on the Néel temperatures and AFMR frequencies 3d TMOs is investigated. Additionally, the Néel temperatures and the AFMR frequencies for the 3d TMOs are employed to benchmark the developed magnetic force theorem and linear spin-wave theory. The isotropic spin-exchange interactions of all 3d TMOs successfully capture the experimentally observed Néel temperatures, confirming the validity the magnetic force theorem in this work. The experimentally observed AFMR frequencies of MnO and NiO are successfully captured by the linear spin-wave theory. The systematic analysis clarified that, for the MnO and NiO which have the in-plane magnetic easy axis within (111), the $\omega_{(\alpha)\mathbf{k}}$ is predominantly influenced by the MDIs, while rhombohedral distortion effect is necessary to describe the $\omega_{(\beta)\mathbf{k}}$, and both $\omega_{(\alpha)\mathbf{k}}$ and $\omega_{(\beta)\mathbf{k}}$ are in quantitative agreement with the experiment results. On the other hand, the experimentally observed AFMR frequencies of FeO and CoO are not well captured by the linear spin-wave theory in this present work. In highly anisotropic FeO and CoO, the ω_α and ω_β are determined by the \mathbf{x} - and \mathbf{y} -components of the MCA constants, respectively. However, quantitative discrepancies remain for ω_α and ω_β of FeO and CoO, which are attributed to a difficulty in the incorporation of SOC-induced spin-splitting in linear spin-wave theory, indicating the need of generalized linear spin-wave theory, i.e., flavor-wave theory which considers multiple spin states rather than a single localized spin state as in linear spin-wave theory.

Chapter 4

Terahertz Topological Magnons in 2D van der Waals CrI₃/As Bilayers

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the FLAPW method and quantum theory of magnons are applied on a two-dimensional (2D) ferromagnetic van der Waals CrI₃/As bilayers to investigate the interplay of isotropic spin-exchange interactions and Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) on THz topological magnons, under symmetries modification from the stacking orders on the As monolayer. This investigation is motivated by the existence of van der Waals interactions that weakly couple a layered structure of CrI₃, thus opening the possibility of electronic state modulation by changing the stacking order between the layers, rather than by introducing impurities, which costs more energy. Experimentally, controls over stacking order in one multi-layer system have been demonstrated by performing mechanical interlayer sliding [86], terahertz light pulse-induced interlayer shear strain [87], and ion intercalation [88]. In particular, it was shown that the terahertz light pulse induces a small interlayer sliding in WTe₂, which drives the system into a metastable electronic topological phase [87].

Terahertz magnon excitation has been directly observed in the monolayer CrI₃ via magneto-Raman spectroscopy [85], where the magnon frequency in the optic mode (4.11 THz) is mainly attributed to the first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange interactions, while that in the acoustic mode (0.07 THz) is linked to the magnetic anisotropy. In both spin-exchange interactions and the magnetic anisotropy, the I atom has two roles, in which the I atom mediates the isotropic spin-exchange interactions between Cr atoms, and the SOC in I atom induces the anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, the so-called Kitaev interactions, resulting in large magnetic anisotropy energy up to 1 meV per unit cell [82, 83, 166]. Additionally, several experimental and theoretical works hinted that the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) drive topological magnon in the CrI₃, in

addition to the first-nearest neighbor Kitaev interactions [167–171].

Attempts to tune magnetic interactions and magnonic properties of the CrI₃ have been demonstrated by placing the CrI₃ onto non-magnetic metal substrate and depositing non-magnetic semi-metal atoms on the CrI₃. In CrI₃/Au(111), the magnetic anisotropy energy is stacking order-dependent and can be enhanced up to 50% [91]. However, a large lattice mismatch between CrI₃ and bulk Au(111) substrate requires a large chemical unit cell of CrI₃, which can lead to magnon mode splitting and enhanced magnon-magnon scattering. In the bilayer system with non-magnetic semi-metallic atom, e.g., As, Sb, or Bi, deposited on monolayer CrI₃, the magnetization of the CrI₃ was used as a knob to control the non-magnetic semi-metals electronic band gap and the electronic topological phase [96]. While the magnetic anisotropy energy and Curie temperature in the CrI₃ are enhanced in the presence of the non-magnetic semi-metallic elements, the effect of the elements on the THz magnon excitation in the CrI₃ remains unaddressed. Additionally, depositing thin layer of semi-metal atoms on the CrI₃ allows keeping similar lattice constant and chemical unit cell of pristine CrI₃, and the stacking orders can be controlled after the deposition on the CrI₃ [86, 96].

4.2 Calculation Model of Monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As Bilayers

Electronic structure calculations based on DFT in the FLAPW framework [172] were performed. GGA+*U* and DFT-D2 correction were employed to treat strongly-correlated electrons in Cr *d* orbitals ($U_{\text{eff}} = 3$ eV) [118, 173] and van der Waals interactions between layers, respectively. Plane wave cut-off $|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}| \leq 7.37 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ was used for plane wave expansion in reciprocal space. Lattice constant of 7.04 Å was obtained from geometry optimization of a free standing monolayer (ML) CrI₃ via Murnaghan equation. The interlayer distance between CrI₃ and As, $t_{\text{CrI}_3\text{-As}}$, was force-optimized with a convergence criterion for atomic force, 0.005 htr/Å in each stacking order. The $15 \times 15 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh was used for Brillouin zone (BZ) sampling that ensures the convergence of the spin-exchange constants. Formation energies per unit area, E_{form} , of each CrI₃/As stacking were calculated by the following equation,

$$E_{\text{form}} = (E_{\text{CrI}_3/\text{As}} - E_{\text{CrI}_3} - E_{\text{As}})/\text{Area}, \quad (4.1)$$

where $E_{\text{CrI}_3/\text{As}}$ is the total energy of a CrI₃/As stacking, and E_{CrI_3} and E_{As} are the total energy of a free-standing ML CrI₃ and As, respectively.

4.2.1 Structure of Monolayer CrI₃

In the monolayer (ML) CrI₃, the primitive unit cell contains two Cr atoms, and each of them is surrounded by six edge-sharing I atoms forming the octahedral crystal field, as shown by Fig. 4.1(a) and 4.1(b) for the top and side-view of a monolayer CrI₃, respectively. In the ideal structure, where the I atoms form a tilted perfect octahedron around the

Cr atom, the Cr atoms belong to the O_h point group symmetry, which splits the Cr d orbitals into doublet and triplet states. In the force-optimized structure, the I atoms are displaced in twisting directions, i.e., the I atoms at the top CrI_3 sublayer are displaced in a counterclockwise direction, while those of I atoms at the bottom CrI_3 sublayer are displaced in a clockwise direction, as shown by red vectors in Fig. 4.1(c). Additionally, there are small compression along the z direction in the optimized structure. The displacements of I atoms induce a trigonal distortion to the perfect octahedron and consequently reduce the perfect octahedron O_h point group symmetry of Cr atoms into D_{3d} point group symmetry.

4.2.2 Multiple Stacking Order of CrI_3/As Bilayers

Six symmetrically distinct stacking orders of CrI_3/As were initially considered, as shown in Fig. 4.2(a)-4.2(f), where $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ CrI_3 unit cell was used, and the triangular lattice As was variably positioned relative to the CrI_3 , labeled as BL1-BL6. Then, the bilayer structures were force-optimized to find the $t_{\text{CrI}_3-\text{As}}$ while keeping the atomic position of the CrI_3 layer fixed.

In terms of the symmetries, the 2D space group symmetry of BL1 is still similar to that of ML, while the point group of two Cr atoms in the unit cell is further reduced to C_{3v} due to that horizontal glide symmetry operation, that maps one I atom from bottom sublayer into that from top sublayer, is lost. The three-fold rotational symmetry around the Cr atoms is broken in the BL3-BL6, while it is preserved in the BL1 and BL2. In addition, the vertical mirror symmetry is also broken in the BL2 and BL6, which results in two Cr atoms in the unit cell having symmetrically inequivalent surroundings. The details of the 2D space group and point group of two Cr atoms in the unit cell are shown in Table 4.1. These symmetrically distinct stacking orders enable us to observe how spin-exchange, magnetic anisotropy energy, and hence magnon propagation are modulated under the symmetry breaking induced by the triangular lattice As.

4.2.3 Formation Energy of CrI_3/As Bilayers

Formation energies per unit area, E_{form} , are calculated for all six stacking orders based on Eq. (4.1). The BL1 has the lowest E_{form} among them, with $E_{\text{Form}} = -45.87 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$, and the E_{form} of five other stacking orders are plotted in Fig. 4.3. The magnitudes of the E_{form} for the six CrI_3/As bilayers range from 40 to 45 $\text{meV}/\text{\AA}^2$, which are stronger than typical van der Waals interactions [174] but weaker than the covalent bond [175]. For comparison, the exfoliation energies in monolayer graphenes and phosphorenes are 32 and 23 $\text{meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ [176]. Then, the stacking orders are grouped based on the direction of the As monolayer shift relative to a fixed CrI_3 layer in the BL1 stacking order, as shown in Fig. 4.3(a). The BL2 and BL6 can be obtained from the BL1 by performing a shift of the As monolayer relative to a fixed CrI_3 layer along $(\bar{2}, 1)$ direction, where the notation of the shift direction is written in lattice vectors $(\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2)$, as seen in Fig. 4.3(b). On the other hand, a shift of the As monolayer along $(\bar{1}, 0)$ gives the BL3, BL4, and BL5. In this work, only the BL1, BL2, and BL6 are discussed, as they correspond to the three stacking

orders with the lowest formation energies. Additionally, the BL1, BL2, and BL6 enable us to simulate the effect of space group and point group symmetry changes on the magnetic interactions and topological magnons.

Figure 4.1: (a) Top and (b) Side view of monolayer CrI_3 , where two Cr atoms have 6 edge-sharing I atoms that form octahedral ligands. Blue, dark green, and light green spheres denote Cr, I at upper CrI_3 sublayer, and I at bottom CrI_3 sublayer, respectively. The translational lattice vectors, \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 , are shown by the blue arrows. (c) Displacements of I atomic position from the ideal structure with perfect octahedral ligands are shown, and the red vectors represent the displacement directions.

Figure 4.2: Six symmetrically distinct stacking order of CrI_3/As bilayers, labeled as (a) BL1, (b) BL2, (c) BL3, (d) BL4, (e) BL5, and (f) BL6, where the As atom position is varied relative to the $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ unit cell of CrI_3 . In (a)-(f), top and side view of each stacking order are presented. In (a)-(f), blue, dark green, light green, and brown spheres denote Cr, I at upper CrI_3 sublayer, I at bottom CrI_3 sublayer, and As atoms, respectively. The interlayer distance between the CrI_3 atom and the As atom is denoted by the $t_{\text{CrI}_3-\text{As}}$.

Table 4.1: The 2D space group and point group in Cr-I octahedron of two Cr atoms in the unit cell of monolayer (ML) and six stacking order of CrI_3/As bilayer. Under the trigonal lattice distortion and addition of the As atom, the O_h point group reduces into some lower point group symmetries. The interlayer distance between the CrI_3 and the As atom for each stacking order is represented by $t_{\text{CrI}_3-\text{As}}$, which is obtained from force optimization.

Stacking order	2D space group	point group	$t_{\text{CrI}_3-\text{As}}$ (Å)
ML	$P31m$	D_{3d}	
BL1	$P31m$	C_{3v}	2.906
BL2	$P3$	C_{3v}	2.910
BL3	$P1m$	C_{3v}	2.910
BL4	$P1m$	C_1	2.963
BL5	$P1m$	C_1	2.646
BL6	$P1$	C_1	2.905

Figure 4.3: (a) Formation energy of six stacking orders bilayers BL1-BL6 per unit area, $E_{\text{form}}/\text{Area}$, in unit of meV/Å² as a function of As atom shift relative to a fixed CrI₃ layer. The two shift vectors, along $(\bar{2}, 1)$ and $(\bar{1}, 0)$, are shown in (b). The stacking orders that are related to BL1 via As monolayer shift along $(\bar{2}, 1)$ direction are denoted by the blue circles and line, while that are related to BL1 via As monolayer shift along $(\bar{1}, 0)$ are denoted by the red triangles and line, where \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 are the primitive lattice vectors.

4.3 Static Magnetism in CrI_3 and CrI_3/As : Magnetic Order and Anisotropy

4.3.1 Isotropic Spin-Exchange Constants of CrI_3/As Bilayers

For the free-standing ML CrI_3 , the isotropic spin-exchange constant is mainly dominated by the first-nearest neighbor and followed by second-nearest neighbor interactions, denoted as $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, respectively, as shown in Fig. 4.4. Our results show a good agreement with previous first-principles calculations results under four-states method [35], total energy mapping [177], and Raman spectroscopy measurement [84], as shown in Table 4.2. The $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ have a negative sign, which implies ferromagnetic (FM) coupling between magnetic moments of Cr atoms is preferable, confirming the ferromagnetism in ML CrI_3 [56, 84]. The dominant FM coupling between Cr atoms ($J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$) satisfies the Goodenough-Kanamori rules [178, 179], in which the nearly 90° super-exchange cation-anion-cation (Cr-I-Cr) stabilizes the ferromagnetic alignment between two nearest Cr atoms.

In the ML CrI_3 , the partial density of states (PDOS), projected along the Cr-I bond direction, is shown in Fig. 4.5(a), and the corresponding energy level is shown in Fig. 4.5(b). One Cr atom, coordinated with six I atoms, forms edge-sharing octahedra which results in the octahedral crystalline electric field (CEF), splitting Cr d orbitals into occupied threefold t_{2g} state and unoccupied twofold e_g state for the majority spin electrons. Ferromagnetic coupling between first-nearest neighbor Cr atoms, indicated by negative $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$, can be explained by Hubbard model [180]. The empty I p states and Cr e_g states above the Fermi level allow electrons from the occupied t_{2g} states of one Cr atom to be excited into e_g states of another Cr atom via I p states, by keeping the electron spin, as shown in Fig. 4.6(a). The unchanged electron spin during virtual hopping results in the favored ferromagnetic coupling between the nearest-neighboring Cr atoms. In real space, one of the electron hopping channel mediated by I atom is from Cr $d_{x^2-y^2}$ $\xleftrightarrow{pd\sigma}$ I $p_{x'}$ $\xleftrightarrow{pd\pi}$ Cr $d_{x'y'}$, as shown in Fig. 4.6(b), where the primes indicate the rotated coordinate axes along the octahedron axes, as shown in Fig. 4.5.

In the presence of the As layer, the first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constant undergoes an enhancement depending on the As atom position relative to CrI_3 layer, as shown in Fig. 4.7(a). The first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants are split into three contributions from each bond, labeled as $J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}$, $J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}$, and $J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}$, as shown in the Fig. 4.7(b)-4.7(d) for stacking order BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. The rotational symmetry breaking, induced by the addition of As layer, reflects in the symmetry between $J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}$, $J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}$, and $J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}$, as shown in Fig. 4.7(b)-4.7(d) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. In the BL1 and BL2, the rotational symmetry around the Cr atom remains similar to that in the ML CrI_3 , as can be seen in Fig. 4.7(b) and 4.7(c), resulting in small uniform enhancements of $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ in all bonds. On the other hand, in the BL6, one of the three $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$'s is enhanced by more than 100% from that of ML CrI_3 , while the other two bonds are relatively unchanged. In this stacking order, the bond that undergoes enhancement of $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ contains an As atom close to an I atom from the bottom CrI_3 sublayer.

In CrI₃/As bilayers, the PDOS of Cr d , I p , and As p states are shown in Fig. 4.8(a)-4.8(c) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. For the BL1 and BL2, the peak around 0.5 eV below Fermi level only consists of I p and As p states, without Cr d states. However, small peak around 0.5 eV below the Fermi level in the BL6 are observed, which consist of Cr d , I p , and As p states. By projecting the Cr d states along the Cr-I bond that has the As atom nearby, the PDOS of Cr t_{2g} and e_g are shown in Fig. 4.8(d)-4.8(f) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. In the BL1 and BL2, the O_h point group is distorted into C_{3v} , which only results in the splitting of t_{2g} states and leaves the e_g states degenerate, as shown in Fig. 4.5(b). Since the t_{2g} states are fully occupied and far below the Fermi level, the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ does not change as significantly as those in the BL6. However, in the BL6, the small peak around 0.5 eV below the Fermi level arises from the degeneracy splitting between $d_{z^2-r^2}$ and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ states, which are unoccupied above the Fermi level in the free-standing ML CrI₃. The degeneracy splitting in the e_g states is mainly attributed to the distorted octahedral CEF in the presence of As atom close to the one of the six edge-sharing I atoms, reducing the symmetry in the D_{3d} point group symmetry operations around the Cr atom into C_1 in the BL6, as shown in right-most energy splitting diagram in Fig. 4.5(b). The small peak around 0.5 eV below the Fermi level lowers the energy requirement for electrons to 'hop' from the t_{2g} states into the e_g states, increasing the probability of electrons hopping from between Cr atoms via the distorted I atom, and consequently increasing the spin-exchange constant. Additionally, for all stacking orders, the interaction between As p and I p orbitals reduces the CEF that acts on Cr d , which lowers the energy levels of Cr e_g due to the reduced Coulomb repulsion.

Figure 4.4: The isotropic spin-exchange constants for the monolayer CrI_3 , J_{ij}^{ex} in meV, as a function of interaction distance r_{ij} in Å. The first- and second-nearest neighbor isotropic spin-exchange constants are indicated by $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, respectively. The negative (positive) sign of the J_{ij}^{ex} corresponds to the ferromagnetic (antiferromagnetic) alignment between a pair of spins.

Table 4.2: First- and second-nearest neighbors spin-exchange constants, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$, in unit of meV, obtained in the present work, density functional theory (DFT) calculations based on projector augmented wave (PAW) under local density approximation (LDA) [166] and generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [177] with different Hubbard correction U_{eff} and experiment of Raman spectroscopy [84].

	$J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$	$J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$
Present work	-2.41	-0.44
Theory (PAW+LDA+four-state method ($U_{\text{eff}} = 0.5$ eV)) [166]	-2.46	
Theory (PAW+GGA+four-state method ($U_{\text{eff}} = 4$ eV)) [177]	-2.56	-0.64
Experiment (Raman spectroscopy) [84]	-2.73	

Figure 4.5: (a) Partial density of states (PDOS) of Cr d states of a free-standing monolayer CrI_3 , where the Cr-I bonds are projected into the orthogonal axes of an octahedron, denoted as $\{x', y', z'\}$. Red and blue shaded areas represent e_g and t_{2g} states, respectively. (b) The orbital splitting of d states in the CrI_3 , under the O_h , D_{3d} , C_{3v} , and C_1 point group symmetries.

Figure 4.6: Electron hopping between two Cr atoms mediated by an I atom in (a) energy diagram and (b) the corresponding hopping in the orbital hybridization representation. In (b), one of possible route for electron hopping between two Cr atoms are shown, which is (i) Cr $d_{x'y^2}$ - $d_{x'y'}$ or (ii) Cr $d_{3x^2-r^2}$ - $d_{x'y'}$ orbitals, and both channels mediated by I $p_{x'}$ orbitals via $pd\sigma$ and $pd\pi$ bonds and

Figure 4.7: (a) First-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants decomposed into three first-nearest neighbor bonds, a , b , and c in meV, colored in red, green, and blue, respectively. The horizontal dashed line in (a) represents the $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ of monolayer CrI_3 . Three first-nearest neighboring Cr-Cr bonds for stacking order (b) BL1, (c) BL2, and (d) BL6, where blue, dark green, light green, and brown spheres represent Cr, I from bottom CrI_3 sublayer, I from upper CrI_3 sublayer, and As atoms. The red, green and blue arrows represents a , b , and c bonds.

Figure 4.8: Partial density of states (PDOS) of Cr d states, I p states, and As p states in three CrI_3/As stacking orders, (a) BL1, (b) BL2, and (c) BL6. In (a)-(c) figures, red, green, and blue shaded areas represent Cr d , I p , and As p states, respectively. PDOS of Cr t_{2g} and e_g states, projected along a Cr-I bond that has As atom nearby, for stacking order (d) BL1, (e) BL2, and (f) BL6. In (d)-(f), red dashed and dotted lines represent Cr $d_{z^2-r^2}$ and $d_{x^2-y^2}$, respectively, while the PDOS of t_{2g} states are negligible in this energy range.

4.3.2 Anisotropic Spin-Exchange Constants of CrI₃/As Bilayers

Symmetry Analysis of Anisotropic Spin-Exchange Constants

The generalized spin-exchange tensors, $\overleftrightarrow{J}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_l(\tau')}$, are divided into two parts: symmetric and anti-symmetric Dzyloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) parts. The spin Hamiltonian is expressed as the sum of the diagonalized symmetric and the anti-symmetric parts, as given by,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta}^{\{x,y,z\}} \sum_{l,l',\tau,\tau'} \left(J_{\mathbf{R}_l+\tau,\mathbf{R}_{l'}+\tau'}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta} + \epsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma} D_{\mathbf{R}_l+\tau,\mathbf{R}_{l'}+\tau'}^\gamma \right) \times S_\tau^\alpha S_{\tau'}^\beta. \quad (4.2)$$

For the sake of simplicity, the site notation in the symmetric parts and DMIs is changed into $J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$ and $\mathbf{D}_{ij} = (D_{ij}^x, D_{ij}^y, D_{ij}^z)$, respectively. Note that, the magnon dispersion of ML, BL1, BL2, and BL6 in the main text was calculated using every element of generalized spin-exchange interaction tensors up to farther interactions distance ($|r_{ij}| \leq 52.92 \text{ \AA}$).

There are six first-nearest neighbor (1nn) spin-exchange interactions with different vectors, which connect two different Cr sub-lattices in the unit cell (labeled as Cr₁ and Cr₂ in Fig. 4.1(a)). Consequently, six 1nn spin-exchange interactions can be symmetrically represented by three 1nn spin-exchange interactions, i.e., the (1nn) Cr₁-Cr₂ in the Table 4.3-4.6. Furthermore, if the three 1nn spin-exchange interactions are symmetrically related by three-fold rotational symmetry around the z axis, they can be represented by one 1nn spin-exchange interactions, i.e., the first row of (1nn) Cr₁-Cr₂ in the Table 4.3-4.5 for ML, BL1, and BL2 stacking orders. This rotational symmetry relation is given by,

$$\overleftrightarrow{J}_{i'l'}^{(\text{sym})} = \mathbf{R}_z(120^\circ) \overleftrightarrow{J}_{ij}^{(\text{sym})} (\mathbf{R}_z(120^\circ))^\dagger, \quad (4.3)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_z(\theta)$ is the rotation transformation matrix along z axis by angle θ .

There are twelve second-nearest neighbor (2nn) spin-exchange interactions in total, which connect two same Cr sub-lattices separated by integer primitive translational vector, which means that there are two sets of six 2nn spin-exchange interactions, labeled as (2nn) Cr₁-Cr₁ and (2nn) Cr₂-Cr₂ in the Table 4.3-4.6. If the stacking order has vertical mirror symmetry that maps one Cr sub-lattice to another Cr sub-lattice, two sets of six 2nn spin-exchange interactions can be symmetrically represented by one of the two sets, and this applies for the ML and BL1 stacking order, as shown by the (2nn) Cr₁-Cr₁ of Table 4.3 and 4.4 for the ML and BL1 stacking order. However, for the BL2 and BL6 case where the stacking orders have no vertical mirror symmetry, two sets of six 2nn spin-exchange interactions are symmetrically distinct, as shown in Table 4.5 and 4.6. Furthermore, if the stacking order has three-fold rotational symmetry, the six 2nn spin-exchange interactions can be symmetrically represented by two 2nn spin-exchange interactions, e.g., the first two rows of (2nn) Cr₁-Cr₁ in Table 4.3- 4.5 for the ML, BL1, and BL2.

The DMIs, \mathbf{D}_{ij} , are calculated from the generalized spin-exchange tensors and given

by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{ij}^z &= \frac{1}{2} \left(J_{ij}^{xy} - J_{ij}^{yx} \right), \\
 D_{ij}^y &= \frac{1}{2} \left(J_{ij}^{zx} - J_{ij}^{xz} \right), \\
 D_{ij}^x &= \frac{1}{2} \left(J_{ij}^{yz} - J_{ij}^{zy} \right),
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

The DMIs of ML, BL1, BL2, and BL6 are shown in Table 4.7 up to 2nn. In each 1nn and 2nn sets, the \mathbf{D}_{ij} 's are also symmetrically related, which depends on the rotational, vertical mirror symmetry, and which Cr atoms are connected by the spin-exchange interactions, as thoroughly discussed in previous paragraphs.

Table 4.3: The symmetric spin-exchange interactions, $J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, of the ML CrI_3 within the first- and second-nearest neighbors (denoted 1nn and 2nn) in the unit of meV. The vector of each 1nn and 2nn is also shown in the unit of Å. The subscript i and j in $\text{Cr}_i\text{-Cr}_j$ denotes the Cr sub-lattices that involves in the spin-exchange interactions. The single-ion anisotropy (SIA) constants for Cr_1 and Cr_2 are also shown, which is indicated by $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = (0.00, 0.00, 0.00)$.

		$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)(\text{Å})$	$J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, with $\alpha, \beta \in \{x, y, z\}$ (meV)					
			xx	xy	xz	yy	yz	zz
SIA	Cr_1	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.00	0.00
SIA	Cr_2	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.00	0.00
(1nn)	$\text{Cr}_1\text{-Cr}_2$	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	0.61	-0.69	-3.01	-0.39	-2.82
		(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	-0.61	0.69	-3.01	-0.39	-2.82
		(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.36	0.00	0.00	-1.95	0.79	-2.82
(1nn)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{-Cr}_1$	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	0.61	-0.69	-3.01	-0.39	-2.82
		(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	-0.61	0.69	-3.01	-0.39	-2.82
		(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.36	0.00	0.00	-1.95	0.79	-2.82
(2nn)	$\text{Cr}_1\text{-Cr}_1$	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	-0.05	0.06	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
		(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	-0.05	0.06	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
		(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
		(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
(2nn)	$\text{Cr}_2\text{-Cr}_2$	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	-0.05	0.06	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
		(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	-0.05	0.06	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
		(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
		(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37

Table 4.4: The symmetric spin-exchange interactions, $J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, of the BL1 stacking order within the first- and second-nearest neighbors (denoted 1nn and 2nn) in the unit of meV. All notations are identical to the Table 4.3.

	$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)(\text{\AA})$	$J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, with $\alpha, \beta \in \{x, y, z\}$ (meV)					
		xx	xy	xz	yy	yz	zz
SIA Cr ₁	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.00	0.00
SIA Cr ₂	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.00	0.00
(1nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₂	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	0.61	-0.69	-3.01	-0.40	-2.82
	(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.31	-0.61	0.69	-3.01	-0.40	-2.82
	(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.36	0.00	0.00	-1.95	0.79	-2.82
(1nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₁	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.30	0.61	-0.69	-3.01	-0.40	-2.82
	(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.31	-0.61	0.69	-3.01	-0.40	-2.82
	(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.36	0.00	0.00	-1.95	0.79	-2.82
(2nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₁	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.05	0.07	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.05	0.07	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
(2nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₂	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.05	0.07	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.05	0.07	-0.45	-0.03	-0.37
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.39	0.05	-0.06	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.07	-0.37

Table 4.5: The symmetric spin-exchange interactions, $J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, of the BL2 stacking order within the first- and second-nearest neighbors (denoted 1nn and 2nn) in the unit of meV. All notations are identical to the Table 4.3.

	$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)(\text{\AA})$	$J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, with $\alpha, \beta \in \{x, y, z\}$ (meV)					
		xx	xy	xz	yy	yz	zz
SIA Cr ₁	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.00
SIA Cr ₂	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.13	0.00	0.00
(1nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₂	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.33	0.67	-0.63	-2.97	-0.40	-2.86
	(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.23	-0.61	0.66	-3.08	-0.35	-2.86
	(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.39	-0.06	-0.03	-1.91	0.74	-2.86
(1nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₁	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-2.33	0.67	-0.63	-2.97	-0.40	-2.86
	(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-2.23	-0.61	0.66	-3.08	-0.35	-2.86
	(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-3.39	-0.06	-0.03	-1.91	0.74	-2.86
(2nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₁	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.45	-0.07	0.09	-0.53	-0.05	-0.43
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.45	-0.07	0.09	-0.53	-0.05	-0.43
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.45	0.07	-0.09	-0.54	-0.05	-0.43
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.45	0.07	-0.09	-0.54	-0.05	-0.43
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.57	0.01	0.00	-0.41	0.10	-0.43
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.57	0.01	0.00	-0.41	0.10	-0.43
(2nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₂	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.33	-0.02	0.03	-0.36	-0.01	-0.28
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.33	-0.02	0.03	-0.36	-0.01	-0.28
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.33	0.02	-0.03	-0.36	-0.02	-0.28
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.33	0.02	-0.03	-0.36	-0.02	-0.28
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.37	0.00	0.00	-0.32	0.03	-0.28
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.37	0.00	0.00	-0.32	0.03	-0.28

Table 4.6: The symmetric spin-exchange interactions, $J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, of the BL6 stacking order within the first- and second-nearest neighbors (denoted 1nn and 2nn) in the unit of meV. All notations are identical to the Table 4.3.

		$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)(\text{\AA})$	$J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})\alpha\beta}$, with $\alpha, \beta \in \{x, y, z\}$ (meV)					
			xx	xy	xz	yy	yz	zz
SIA	Cr ₁	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.38	0.04	0.02	0.27	0.00	0.00
SIA	Cr ₂	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	0.12	0.06	-0.02	0.21	0.03	0.00
(1nn)	Cr ₁ -Cr ₂	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-1.86	0.53	-0.65	-2.57	-0.31	-2.35
		(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-4.30	-0.61	0.63	-5.05	-0.37	-4.93
		(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-2.99	-0.01	0.01	-1.98	0.56	-2.56
(1nn)	Cr ₂ -Cr ₁	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	-1.86	0.53	-0.65	-2.57	-0.31	-2.35
		(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	-4.30	-0.61	0.63	-5.05	-0.37	-4.93
		(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	-2.99	-0.01	0.01	-1.98	0.56	-2.56
(2nn)	Cr ₁ -Cr ₁	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.07	0.07	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.40	-0.07	0.07	-0.46	-0.04	-0.37
		(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.42	0.03	-0.10	-0.53	-0.02	-0.37
		(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.42	0.03	-0.10	-0.53	-0.02	-0.37
		(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.51	-0.01	-0.01	-0.45	0.08	-0.38
		(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.51	-0.01	-0.01	-0.45	0.08	-0.38
(2nn)	Cr ₂ -Cr ₂	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.38	-0.04	0.04	-0.43	-0.02	-0.37
		(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.38	-0.04	0.04	-0.43	-0.02	-0.37
		(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	-0.17	0.00	-0.03	-0.18	0.00	-0.14
		(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	-0.17	0.00	-0.03	-0.18	0.00	-0.14
		(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	-0.41	-0.01	-0.02	-0.34	0.06	-0.29
		(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	-0.41	-0.01	-0.02	-0.34	0.06	-0.29

Table 4.7: The Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs), $\mathbf{D}_{ij} = (D_{ij}^x, D_{ij}^y, D_{ij}^z)$, of ML, BL1, BL2, and BL6 stacking orders within the first- and second-nearest neighbors (in meV). All notations are identical to the Table 4.3.

	$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)$ (Å)	$(D_{ij}^x, D_{ij}^y, D_{ij}^z)$ (meV)			
		ML	BL1	BL2	BL6
(1nn) Cr1-Cr2	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.12, 0.07, -0.04)	(-0.07, -0.15, -0.07)	(-0.02, 0.03, -0.04)
	(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(-0.12, 0.07, -0.04)	(0.17, 0.01, -0.07)	(0.09, 0.21, -0.55)
	(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.00, -0.13, -0.04)	(-0.09, 0.14, -0.07)	(-0.06, 0.16, 0.15)
(1nn) Cr2-Cr1	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(-0.12, -0.07, 0.04)	(0.07, 0.15, 0.07)	(0.02, -0.03, 0.04)
	(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.12, -0.07, 0.04)	(-0.17, 0.00, 0.07)	(-0.09, -0.21, 0.55)
	(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.00, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.13, 0.04)	(0.08, -0.13, 0.07)	(0.06, -0.16, -0.15)
(2nn) Cr1-Cr1	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	(0.08, -0.05, 0.03)	(0.08, -0.03, 0.07)	(0.10, -0.04, 0.05)	(0.09, -0.03, 0.07)
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	(-0.08, 0.05, -0.03)	(-0.08, 0.03, -0.07)	(-0.10, 0.04, -0.05)	(-0.09, 0.03, -0.07)
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	(-0.08, -0.05, 0.03)	(-0.06, -0.05, 0.07)	(-0.09, -0.07, 0.05)	(-0.07, -0.10, 0.10)
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	(0.08, 0.05, -0.03)	(0.06, 0.05, -0.07)	(0.09, 0.07, -0.05)	(0.07, 0.10, -0.10)
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.09, 0.03)	(-0.01, 0.08, 0.07)	(-0.01, 0.11, 0.05)	(-0.03, 0.08, 0.05)
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	(0.00, -0.09, -0.03)	(0.01, -0.08, -0.07)	(0.01, -0.11, -0.05)	(0.03, -0.08, -0.05)
(2nn) Cr2-Cr2	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	(-0.08, 0.05, -0.03)	(-0.06, 0.05, -0.07)	(-0.01, 0.02, 0.02)	(-0.06, 0.05, -0.04)
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	(0.08, -0.05, 0.03)	(0.06, -0.05, 0.07)	(0.01, -0.02, -0.02)	(0.06, -0.05, 0.04)
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	(0.08, 0.05, -0.03)	(0.08, 0.03, -0.07)	(0.01, 0.00, 0.02)	(0.00, 0.02, -0.01)
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	(-0.08, -0.05, 0.03)	(-0.08, -0.03, 0.07)	(-0.01, 0.00, -0.02)	(0.00, -0.02, 0.01)
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	(0.00, -0.09, -0.03)	(-0.01, -0.08, -0.07)	(-0.01, -0.01, 0.02)	(-0.02, -0.06, -0.07)
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	(0.00, 0.09, 0.03)	(0.01, 0.08, 0.07)	(0.01, 0.01, -0.02)	(0.02, 0.06, 0.07)

Role of Anisotropic Spin-Exchange Interactions in Magnetic Anisotropy Energy

Typically, the magnetic anisotropy energy is calculated as the difference between sum of Kohn-Sham energies under SOC effect in the in-plane direction and out-of-plane directions. While it gives information of magnetic anisotropy origin in terms of energy levels of atomic orbitals, in the case of magnetic atoms having weak SOC in the vicinity of strong SOC non-magnetic atoms, this method does not give direct insights about the origin of magnetic anisotropy in real space, which is beneficial for the purpose of engineering the magnetic properties. In this work, the magnetic anisotropy energy is calculated based on the sum of bond-dependent anisotropic spin-exchange constants, which enables real space bond analysis. Specifically, the magnetic anisotropy energy is defined as the magnetic energy difference between in-plane and out-of-plane direction of the film in terms of the diagonal elements of the spin-exchange tensors in Eq. (2.117), which is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta E^x &= E(90^\circ, 0^\circ) - E(0^\circ, 0^\circ) \\ &= \sum_{ij} \left(J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})xx} - J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})zz} \right) S_i S_j = \sum_{ij} \Delta E_{ij}^x, \\ \Delta E^y &= E(90^\circ, 90^\circ) - E(0^\circ, 0^\circ) \\ &= \sum_{ij} \left(J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})yy} - J_{ij}^{(\text{sym})zz} \right) S_i S_j = \sum_{ij} \Delta E_{ij}^y,\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

where two in-plane directions, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , are indicated by Fig. 4.2, and $S_i = 3/2$. For the ML CrI_3 and CrI_3/As bilayers, the ΔE_{ij}^x and ΔE_{ij}^y at distance $r_{ij} = 0$ corresponds to the contribution from the single-ion anisotropy of the individual Cr atom, while at finite distance $r_{ij} \neq 0$, the ΔE_{ij} corresponds to the contribution of the I atoms that mediated the Cr-Cr pair.

The magnetic anisotropy energies of a free-standing ML CrI_3 from the present work and other theoretical references are compared in the Table 4.8, which gives a good agreement between them in terms of sign and magnitude, and confirms the out-of-plane magnetic easy axis. To elucidate the origin of the magnetic anisotropy energy in the ML CrI_3 , the contribution of spin-pair interaction separated by distance r_{ij} to the magnetic anisotropy, ΔE_{ij} , are plotted in Fig. 4.9(a). The first-nearest neighbor Cr-Cr interactions dominantly give rise to the magnetic anisotropy energy, followed by the second-nearest neighbor interactions and single-ion anisotropy of the Cr atom. However, the second-nearest neighbor interactions give rise to a negative contribution to the magnetic anisotropy energy, in contrast to the first-nearest neighbor interactions and single-ion anisotropy. The large contribution of the first-nearest neighbor interactions to the magnetic anisotropy energy is mainly attributed to the Kitaev interactions in the 90° superexchange hopping between the Cr-I-Cr, where the strong SOC effect of I p states creates different energy hopping costs between the Cr-Cr pairs, depending on the magnetization directions [79, 82, 83, 166].

In the presence of the As monolayer, the magnetic anisotropy energies, ΔE^x and ΔE^y , undergo weakening depending on the symmetry of the stacking orders, and are shown in Fig. 4.10, and the ΔE^u in the BL6 becomes negative, which implies the the change of

magnetic easy axis from the out-of-plane \mathbf{z} direction into the in-plane \mathbf{y} direction. The magnetic anisotropy energies as a function of interaction distances for BL1, BL2, and BL6 are plotted in Fig. 4.9(b)-4.9(d), respectively. The change of magnetic anisotropy energy in bilayer from that in ML is mainly attributed to the change of first- and second-nearest neighbor interactions contributions, while the single-ion anisotropy contribution is relatively unchanged in all stacking orders (~ 0.5 meV), as seen in Fig. 4.9(b)-4.9(d) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. The first-nearest neighbor interactions contribution remains dominant in the BL1 and BL2 (above 1 meV), while the magnitude of the second-nearest neighbor interactions contribution increases to nearly 1 meV, resulting in the reduced magnetic anisotropy energy from that of ML, as seen in Fig. 4.9(b) and 4.9(c). On the other hand, in the BL6, the increase of the second-nearest neighbor interactions contributions (around 1 meV) and the decrease of the first-nearest neighbor interactions contributions magnitude (to around 0.5 meV) result in negative ΔE^y and changing the magnetic easy axis into \mathbf{y} direction, as seen in Fig. 4.9(d).

Table 4.8: Magnetic anisotropy energies, ΔE^x and ΔE^y , in the unit of meV/u.c., obtained in the present work and other density functional theory (DFT) calculations based on projector augmented wave (PAW) under local density approximation (LDA) and generalized gradient approximation (GGA) different Hubbard correction U_{eff} .

	ΔE^x	ΔE^y
Present work	1.35	1.35
PAW+LDA ($U_{\text{eff}} = 0.5$ eV) [166]	1.11	1.11
PAW+GGA ($U_{\text{eff}} = 2.6$ eV) [181]	1.55	1.55
PAW+GGA ($U_{\text{eff}} = 3.0$ eV) [173]	1.41	1.41

Figure 4.9: Contribution of Cr-Cr interaction separated with distance r_{ij} , in the unit of Å, to the magnetic anisotropy energy, ΔE_{ij}^x and ΔE_{ij}^y , for (a) ML, (b) BL1, (c) BL2, and (d) BL6 in the unit of meV. Red squares and blue triangles represent the magnetic anisotropy energy contribution from the Cr-Cr pair, ΔE_{ij}^x and ΔE_{ij}^y , respectively. Blue and red dashed lines correspond to the total magnetic anisotropy energy, which is obtained by summing contributions from all Cr-Cr pairs.

Figure 4.10: The magnetic anisotropy energy from the anisotropic spin-exchange constants, ΔE^x and ΔE^y , of three stacking orders BL1, BL2, and BL6 in the unit of meV. The dashed line represents ΔE^x and ΔE^y of the monolayer CrI_3 . The ΔE^x and ΔE^y is colored in red and blue bars, respectively.

Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya Interactions

Off-diagonal elements of spin-exchange tensors in Eq. (2.117) contain the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs), which are the key magnetic interactions that drives topological magnons in magnetic materials. The DMI vectors are related to the off-diagonal spin-exchange tensors, which are given Eq. (4.4). The magnitude of DMI vectors for each spin pair is defined as,

$$|D_{ij}| = \sqrt{(D_{ij}^x)^2 + (D_{ij}^y)^2 + (D_{ij}^z)^2}. \quad (4.6)$$

Additionally, the DMI that is parallel to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\parallel} , and DMI that is perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\perp} , are calculated, which are defined as,

$$D_{ij}^{\parallel} = \begin{cases} |D_{ij}^z| & \text{for ML, BL1, and BL2,} \\ |D_{ij}^y| & \text{for BL6,} \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

$$D_{ij}^{\perp} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{(D_{ij}^x)^2 + (D_{ij}^y)^2} & \text{for ML, BL1, and BL2,} \\ \sqrt{(D_{ij}^x)^2 + (D_{ij}^z)^2} & \text{BL6.} \end{cases}$$

The D_{ij}^{\parallel} enters the second order magnon Hamiltonian, $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$, and modifies the magnon frequencies and wave-function. Physically, the D_{ij}^{\parallel} couples the transversal component of oscillating magnetization, e.g., \mathbf{x} with \mathbf{y} component of magnetization for magnetic easy axis along \mathbf{z} direction. On the other hand, the D_{ij}^{\perp} couples the transversal component of oscillating magnetization with the quantized component of oscillating magnetization, e.g., \mathbf{x}/\mathbf{y} with \mathbf{z} component of magnetization for magnetic easy axis along \mathbf{z} direction. If the D_{ij}^{\perp} is larger than the isotropic spin-exchange constants, D_{ij}^{\perp} induces a non-collinear spin canting configuration, while weak D_{ij}^{\perp} induces magnon damping via three-magnon interactions.

Before proceeding into the results for ML CrI₃ and CrI₃/As, the geometric conditions for a finite DMI are briefly presented. The condition of a bond between two magnetic atoms that possesses finite DMIs has been discussed extensively by Moriya [182]. In general, the DMIs exist in magnetic solids with SOC, where the two magnetic atoms have broken inversion symmetry at the center of the bond. For two magnetic atoms 1 and 2 at position i and j , respectively, and the point bisecting the straight line ij is given by x , the DMIs, $\mathbf{D}_{ij} (D_{ij}^x, D_{ij}^y, D_{ij}^z)$, between two magnetic atoms are given by,

- (1) if the inversion center between two magnetic atoms and ligands around the bond is located at x , the DMIs

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} = 0, \quad (4.8)$$

- (2) if a mirror plane perpendicular to ij passes through the x ,

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} \parallel \text{mirror plane or } \mathbf{D}_{ij} \perp ij, \quad (4.9)$$

(3) if a mirror plane including the i and j ,

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} \perp \text{mirror plane}, \quad (4.10)$$

(4) if a two-fold rotation axis is perpendicular to ij passes through x ,

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} \perp \text{two-fold axis}, \quad (4.11)$$

(5) if there is an n -fold axis ($n \geq 2$) along the ij ,

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij} \parallel ij. \quad (4.12)$$

The DMIs in the ML CrI₃ are shown in Fig. 4.11(a), where the first-nearest neighbor DMIs, $|D_{(1)}|$, vanish, while the second-nearest neighbor DMIs, $|D_{(2)}|$, have finite magnitude, which is around 0.1 meV. The finite $|D_{(2)}|$ is mainly composed of $D_{(2)}^\perp$ [Fig. 4.11(i)], while the $D_{(2)}^\parallel$ has a magnitude of around 0.04 meV [Fig. 4.11(e)], which is quite small compared to other magnetic interactions. The existence of I atoms already fulfill the requirement of the SOC for the DMI, but the requirement of having broken inversion symmetry at the center of the bond depends on the geometry of the bond. The bond between two first- and second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms mediated by I atoms are shown in Fig. 4.12(a, b) and (c, d), respectively. The first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms form two 90° super-exchange paths each mediated by one I atom, and the inversion symmetry at the center of Cr-Cr bond is preserved, as shown in Fig. 4.12(a) and 4.12(b) for the side and top-view. This geometry for the two first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms satisfy the condition (1) in Moriya's theory, which results in zero first-nearest neighbor DMIs $|D_{(1)}|$. On the other hand, the second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms form a super-exchange path mediated by two consecutive I atoms, and this bond satisfy the condition (4) in Moriya's theory, where the two-fold rotation axis is indicated by the red arrow in Fig. 4.12(d). This results in $|D_{(2)}|$ along \mathbf{z} direction and Cr-Cr bond, confirming the finite values of $D_{(2)}^\parallel$ and $D_{(2)}^\perp$, respectively.

In the CrI₃/As bilayers, the first-nearest neighbor DMIs $|D_{(1)}|$ increases to more than 0.1 meV, while the second-nearest neighbor DMIs $|D_{(2)}|$ increases slightly around 0.1 meV, as shown by Fig. 4.11(b)-4.11(d) for BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. The increase of $|D_{(1)}|$ are mainly attributed to the increase of the $D_{(1)}^\perp$ by more than 0.1 meV, as shown in Fig. 4.11(j)-4.11(l) for BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively, while the increase of $D_{(1)}^\parallel$ are less than 0.1 meV, as shown as shown in Fig. 4.11(f)-4.11(h). On the other hand, the increase of $D_{(2)}^\parallel$ are observed from 0.04 meV in ML to 0.07 meV in BL1, 0.05 meV in BL2, and 0.1 meV in BL6, but these enhancements are smaller than the $D_{(2)}^\perp$ which is around 0.1 meV.

The magnetic ground states of each CrI₃/As stacking order are assumed to be collinear ferromagnetic, based on the comparison between the $D_{(1)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $D_{(2)}^\perp/J_{(2)}^{\text{ex}}$ in the present work and those in previous magnetic ground state calculations. Previous Monte Carlo

simulations on the honeycomb Janus monolayer CrI₃ showed that $D_{(1)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ larger than 0.15 results in non-collinear spin textures as magnetic ground state [93], and Luttinger-Tisza calculations demonstrated that $D_{(2)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ less than 0.69 results in collinear ferromagnetic as the magnetic ground state [90, 183, 184]. In the BL1, BL2, and BL6, it is found that $D_{(1)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ are all less than 0.15, and $D_{(2)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ are all less than 0.05, which justifies our assumption that the magnetic ground state remains collinear ferromagnetic. The details of the $D_{(1)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ and $D_{(2)}^\perp/J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$ of BL1, BL2, and BL6 are given in Table 4.9.

In the BL1, BL2, and BL6, the inversion symmetry at the center of Cr-Cr bond is broken, and finite DMI in the first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms appears and points along the normal vector of the red plane in Fig. 4.12(b) according to condition (3) in Moriya's theory [182], which results in finite $D_{(1)}^\parallel$ and $D_{(1)}^\perp$ due to the red plane being tilted relative to the global coordinate axes. To understand the origin of the increase of first-nearest neighbor DMIs $|D_{(1)}|$, the difference between charge density of two I atoms that mediate two first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms are calculated, and the average between the three first-nearest neighbor bonds are defined by,

$$\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)} = \frac{|n_{I_3} - n_{I_6}| + |n_{I_2} - n_{I_5}| + |n_{I_1} - n_{I_4}|}{3}, \quad (4.13)$$

where the I_i with $i=1, \dots, 6$ are shown in Fig. 4.1(a). The average charge density difference between two I atoms in each first-nearest neighbor bond, $\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)}$, are summarized in the Table 4.10. From BL1 to BL6, the $\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)}$ increases, which correspond to the increasing trend of $|D_{(1)}|$ between BL1, BL2, and BL6, as shown in Fig. 4.11(b)-4.11(d). The finite $\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)}$ is attributed to the interfacial charge transfer from the electrons in the As monolayer to the CrI₃ layer, which then redistributed across the layer. This mechanism is indicated by the decreasing charge density of As atoms δn_{As} , as shown in the Table 4.10, which is defined as the charge density of the As atom in the bilayer CrI₃/As subtracted by that in the free-standing ML As, $n_{\text{As, BLx}} - n_{\text{As, ML}}$.

The increase of $|D^{(2)}|$ can also be traced by calculating the difference between charge density of two I atoms that mediate two second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms in series, and take the average between all second-nearest neighbor bonds, as defined by

$$\Delta\bar{n}_{(2)} = \frac{|n_{I_2} - n_{I_4}| + |n_{I_1} - n_{I_6}| + |n_{I_3} - n_{I_5}| + |n_{I_3} - n_{I_4}| + |n_{I_2} - n_{I_6}| + |n_{I_1} - n_{I_5}|}{6}. \quad (4.14)$$

The $\Delta\bar{n}_{(2)}$ are summarized in the Table 4.10, and the increasing trend of $\Delta\bar{n}_{(2)}$ from BL1 to BL6 are also shown, which also due to the interfacial charge transfer from the As monolayer to the CrI₃ layer.

Figure 4.11: The magnitude of Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs), $|D_{ij}|$, in unit of meV as a function of interactions distance r_{ij} in unit of \AA for the (a) monolayer (ML) CrI_3 , (b) BL1, (c) BL2, and (d) BL6 CrI_3/As bilayers. The DMIs component parallel to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\parallel} , for the (e) ML, (f) BL1, (g) BL2, and (h) BL6 CrI_3/As bilayers. The DMIs component perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\perp} , for the (i) ML, (j) BL1, (k) BL2, and (l) BL6 CrI_3/As bilayers. In all figures, the first- and second-nearest neighbor DMI are denoted by subscript (1) and (2), respectively.

Table 4.9: The ratio between DMIs perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis and first-nearest neighbor isotropic spin-exchange interactions, $D_{ij}^\perp/|J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}|$. All notations are identical to the Table 4.3.

	$(r_{ij}^x, r_{ij}^y, r_{ij}^z)$ (Å)	$D_{(ij)}^\perp/ \bar{J}_{(1)}^{\text{ex}} $ (meV)			
		ML	BL1	BL2	BL6
(1nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₂	(-2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.02
	(-2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.12
	(4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.06
(1nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₁	(2.03, -3.52, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.02
	(2.03, 3.52, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.12
	(-4.06, 0.00, 0.00)	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.06
(2nn) Cr ₁ -Cr ₁	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.02
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.02
(2nn) Cr ₂ -Cr ₂	(6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	3.41×10^{-3}
	(-6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	3.41×10^{-3}
	(-6.10, -3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02
	(6.10, 3.52, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02
	(0.00, 7.04, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02
	(0.00, -7.04, 0.00)	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02

Table 4.10: The average charge density difference between two I atoms in each first- and second-nearest neighbor bond, $\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)}$ and $\Delta\bar{n}_{(2)}$, and the change of As atom charge density under stacking with the CrI_3 , δn_{As} , in the unit of e/bohr^3 .

	ML	BL1	BL2	BL6
$\Delta\bar{n}_{(1)} (\times 10^{-3})$	0.00	1.21	1.29	7.86
$\Delta\bar{n}_{(2)} (\times 10^{-3})$	0.00	1.21	1.29	10.58
$\delta n_{\text{As}} (\times 10^{-2})$		-1.47	-0.79	-1.48

Figure 4.12: The first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms from two super-exchange paths each mediated by one I atom, as viewed from (a) side and (b) top. The second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms mediated by two consecutive I atoms, as viewed from (c) side and (d) top. In (a)-(d), blue, dark green, and light green, denote Cr, I at bottom CrI_3 sublayer, and I at top CrI_3 sublayer, respectively. The black circle represents the inversion point in each bond. Red plane in (b) represents a plane that contains the first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms with the two mediating I atoms. Red vector in (d) represent the two-fold rotation axis that leaves the Cr-I-I-Cr unchanged.

4.4 Dynamic Magnetism in CrI₃ and CrI₃/As: Topological Magnon

4.4.1 Magnon Dispersion in Monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As Bilayers

Monolayer CrI₃

Using the spin-exchange constants obtained via magnetic force theorem, the magnon dispersion of a ML CrI₃ are calculated and shown in Fig. 4.13(a) for two magnon modes, optic (red line) and acoustic (blue line) modes for higher and lower frequency modes. At Γ , the optic mode represents a uniform magnetic moment precession where two first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms have a 180° phase difference, while the acoustic mode represents a uniform magnetic moment precession where all Cr atoms precession are in-phase, as seen in Fig. 4.14(a) and 4.14(b) for acoustic and optic mode, respectively. In the optic mode, the magnon frequencies are mainly determined by the first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants due to the anti-parallel alignment between first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms from the 180° precession phase difference, while, in the acoustic mode, the magnon frequencies are mainly determined by the magnetic anisotropy energy. Magnon frequencies at Γ , which correspond to the FMR frequencies or Goldstone mode, were found to be 5.15 THz for the optic mode and 0.21 THz for the acoustic mode, which are in agreement with the results of magneto-Raman spectroscopy (4.11 and 0.08 THz) [85]. Had the magnetic anisotropy energy been assumed by a single-ion anisotropy term of Cr atom in the spin Hamiltonian, the acoustic FMR frequency is overestimated by more than 0.5 THz.

At \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' , a magnon frequency gap between optic and acoustic modes is open under the anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, and our calculation results in 0.218 THz of frequency gap. The magnetic moment precession at the \mathbf{K} between first-nearest neighboring Cr atoms are shown in Fig. 4.14(c) and 4.14(d), and the energy of these magnetic moment configuration in the isotropic case are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{acoustic},\mathbf{K}}^{(1),\text{ex}} &= \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}| - |J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}| + \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}| = 0, \\ E_{\text{optic},\mathbf{K}}^{(1),\text{ex}} &= -\frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}| + |J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}| - \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}| = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

and the rotational symmetry between three first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants has been taken into account. This implies that the two types of magnetic moment precession are degenerate at the \mathbf{K} , as confirmed by the magnon dispersion in the dotted lines in Fig. 4.13(a). Under the first-nearest neighbor DMIs, the energy of magnetic moment configuration in Fig. 4.14(c) and 4.14(d) are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{acoustic},\mathbf{K}}^{(1),\text{DMI}} &= -D_{(1)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(1)}^{\parallel} (0) - D_{(1)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) = 0, \\ E_{\text{optic},\mathbf{K}}^{(1),\text{DMI}} &= -D_{(1)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(1)}^{\parallel} (0) - D_{(1)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

which implies that $D_{(1)}^{\perp}$ does not lift the degeneracy at the \mathbf{K} . On the other hand, under

the second-nearest neighbor DMIs, the energy of magnetic moment configuration in Fig. 4.14(g) and 4.14(h) are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\text{acoustic},\mathbf{K}}^{(2),\text{DMI}} &= -D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) \\
 &\quad + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) = -3\sqrt{3}D_{(2)}^{\parallel}, \\
 E_{\text{optic},\mathbf{K}}^{(2),\text{DMI}} &= -D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) \\
 &\quad + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) - D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) + D_{(2)}^{\parallel} \left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3} \right) = 3\sqrt{3}D_{(2)}^{\parallel},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.17}$$

and this results in the frequency gap opening by $6\sqrt{3}D_{(2)}^{\parallel}$.

At \mathbf{M} , the optic and acoustic modes represent magnetization precession shown in Fig. 4.14(e) and 4.14(f), where the energy of these configurations is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\text{acoustic},\mathbf{M}}^{(1),\text{ex}} &= -\frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}| - \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}| + \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}| = -\frac{1}{2}|J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}|, \\
 E_{\text{optic},\mathbf{M}}^{(1),\text{ex}} &= \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}| + \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}| - \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}| = \frac{1}{2}|J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}|,
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.18}$$

and the rotational symmetry between three first-nearest neighbor spin-exchange constants has been taken into account. This implies that the gap between two magnon modes in the \mathbf{M} has symmetry origin, rather than anisotropic origin as in the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' .

Bilayers CrI₃/As

The presence of the As monolayer modifies the magnon dispersions, and this is shown in Fig. 4.13(b)-4.13(d) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. The magnon frequency gap is open at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' in the BL1, BL2, and BL6. To check whether the magnon frequency gap opening arise from symmetry-breaking or the anisotropic effects, the magnon dispersions with solely isotropic spin-exchange constants are plotted, as shown by the dotted lines in Fig. 4.13(b)- 4.13(d) for the BL1, BL2, and BL6, respectively. In the BL1, the optic and acoustic modes at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' has a much larger frequency gap by almost 50% than that in ML, which is mainly due to the enhanced $D_{(2)}^{\parallel}$ by almost twice from that of ML. Therefore the frequency gap opening at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' in the BL1 is mainly driven by the anisotropic origin, which is similar to what occurs in ML. In the BL2 and BL6, the magnon dispersions with solely isotropic spin-exchange interactions exhibit gap opening, which confirms the symmetry-breaking origin of the gap opening. In particular, this is mainly due to that two Cr sub-lattices in the unit cell of BL2 and BL6 are no longer connected by any symmetry operation due to the broken vertical mirror symmetry, which leads to the degeneracy lifting at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' .

Furthermore, magnon dispersion of acoustic and optic modes in the BL6 is observed to have extrema around \mathbf{M} , as shown in Fig. 4.13(d). The dispersion around \mathbf{M} can be explained by evaluating the Eq. (4.18), where $|J_{(1),a}^{\text{ex}}| = |J_{(1),b}^{\text{ex}}| = J$ and $|J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}| \approx 2J$. In this case, the $E_{\text{acoustic},\mathbf{M}}$ increases from $-\frac{1}{2}J$ to 0, while the the $E_{\text{optic},\mathbf{M}}$ decreases from

$\frac{1}{2}J$ to 0, resulting in the disappearance of frequency gap at \mathbf{M} under broken rotational symmetry solely. However, the additional broken vertical mirror symmetry between two Cr sub-lattices, as discussed in the previous paragraph, re-opens the frequency gap at \mathbf{M} , and the combination with broken rotational symmetry results in optic and acoustic mode extrema at \mathbf{M} , respectively. Additionally, the extrema only occurs at two out of six the \mathbf{M} at the BZ, as indicated by two crosses in the Fig. 4.13(e) due to the broken rotational symmetry, while the other four \mathbf{M} 's of BZ have dispersion similar to those of ML, BL1, and BL2.

4.4.2 Magnon Berry Curvature in Monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As Bilayers

To investigate the topological properties of magnon in the ML CrI₃ and multiple CrI₃/As stacking orders, the magnon Berry curvature of each of the magnon modes is calculated and mathematically given by,

$$\Omega_{n,\mathbf{k}}^{\text{xy}} = 2\text{Im} \sum_{m \neq n} \frac{\langle n | \partial_{k_x} \mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} | m \rangle \langle m | \partial_{k_y} \mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}} | n \rangle}{(\hbar\omega_{n,\mathbf{k}} - \hbar\omega_{m,\mathbf{k}})^2}, \quad (4.19)$$

where $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbf{k}}$ is the second-order magnon Hamiltonian (Eq. (2.160)) from Holstein-Primakoff transformation, $|n\rangle$ is the n mode magnon wave-function from Bogoliubov transformation and given by Eq. (2.165), and $\omega_{n,\mathbf{k}}$ is the magnon frequencies of n mode at wave-vector \mathbf{k} .

Magnon Berry curvatures of the ML CrI₃ are shown in Fig. 4.15(a) and 4.15(b) for the acoustic and optic mode, respectively. Both the acoustic and optic mode Berry curvature peaks mainly reside at the corner of the BZ, and, in the case of the ML CrI₃, the magnon Berry curvature peak has three-fold rotational and inversion (roto-inversion) symmetry around the Γ . The integration of the acoustic and optic mode magnon Berry curvature results in non-zero values, which confirms the topologically non-trivial phase of ML CrI₃. Furthermore, the BL1 also exhibits similar magnon Berry curvature to the ML CrI₃ due to similar magnetic structure symmetry, as shown in Fig. 4.15(b) and 4.15(f) for the optic and acoustic modes. In the BL2, the acoustic and optic mode magnon Berry curvatures exhibit broken inversion symmetry while retaining the three-fold rotational symmetry, which results in the alternating sign of Berry curvature at the corner of the BZ, as shown in Fig. 4.15(c) and 4.15(g) for optic and acoustic modes, respectively. Consequently, the integration of the Berry curvature across the BZ results in zero values, indicating a topologically trivial phase. In the BL6, the acoustic and optic mode magnon Berry curvatures exhibit broken three-fold rotational and inversion symmetry, and the peaks of the Berry curvature mainly resides at around the middle of a BZ side, as shown in Fig. 4.15(d) and 4.15(h). For each magnon mode, there are two opposite magnon Berry curvature peaks around the \mathbf{M} , and the integration across the BZ results in zero values, which indicates a topologically trivial phase. Although the integration of the Berry curvature across the BZ results in zero values in the BL2 and BL6, if the integration is restricted to around the valley of magnon dispersion, which is \mathbf{K}/\mathbf{K}' for the BL2 or \mathbf{M} for

the BL6, the integration yields to non-zero values, resulting the so-called magnon valley [185–187].

Figure 4.13: Magnon dispersion, $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, of (a) ML CrI_3 , bilayer CrI_3/As (b) BL1, (c) BL2, and (d) BL6 in THz. The dotted line represents the magnon dispersion obtained by only isotropic spin-exchange constants. The red and blue lines represent the optic and acoustic modes, respectively. (e) The Brillouin zone (BZ) of ML and bilayer CrI_3/As with high-symmetry points in the BZ, Γ , \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{K}' , and \mathbf{M} . Two red crosses indicate the extrema of optic (acoustic) mode magnon dispersions in the BL6.

Figure 4.14: Illustration of magnetization precession of (a) acoustic and (b) optic modes at Γ , where two distinct Cr sub-lattices have 180° phase difference and in-phase uniform precession, respectively. Top view of magnetization precession of (c) acoustic and (d) optic mode between first-nearest neighboring (1nn) Cr atoms at \mathbf{K} . Top view of magnetization precession of (e) acoustic and (f) optic mode between 1nn Cr atoms at \mathbf{M} . Top view of magnetization precession of (g) acoustic and (h) optic mode between second-nearest neighboring (2nn) Cr atoms at \mathbf{K} . In (c)-(f), $\Delta\varphi_i$, where i is an index for bond, represents the phase difference between each of the first-nearest neighbor magnetic moment and magnetic moment of central atom. The (+) and (-) symbols in (g) and (h) represent the sign of $D_{(2)}^{\parallel}$.

Figure 4.15: Magnon Berry curvature, $\Omega_{n,\mathbf{k}}^{xy}$, of (a, e) ML CrI_3 , bilayer CrI_3/As (b, f) BL1, (c, g) BL2, and (d, h) BL6 stacking orders. The left-side figures (a-d) correspond to the Berry curvature of the optic mode, while the right-side figures (e-h) correspond to the Berry curvature of the acoustic mode. The dotted line in each figure represents the Brillouin zone, and the high-symmetry points Γ , K , M , K' are also indicated in each figure.

4.4.3 Magnons in Quasi-One-Dimensional Nanoribbon Geometry of Monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As Bilayers: LSWT Limit

The topological magnon phase implies the existence of localized magnon edge states that close the bulk magnon gap, and this is called bulk-boundary correspondence. To confirm the existence of magnon edge states, magnon dispersions of ML CrI₃ and bilayers CrI₃/As in a quasi-1D nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination are investigated, as shown in Fig. 4.16(a). The contribution of three Cr atoms to the magnon states is resolved, where two Cr atoms are located at the opposite edges of the nanoribbon, and one Cr is located at the middle of nanoribbon, as indicated by blue, red, and green spheres in Fig. 4.16(a) respectively. Furthermore, in the BL6 stacking order, two possible nanoribbon geometries can be made due to the broken rotational symmetry, as shown in Fig. 4.16(b)-4.16(d). Taking the first-nearest neighbor bond c , with $J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}$ being significantly enhanced, as the reference direction, one possible geometry has periodicity completely perpendicular to the bond c (labeled as BL6(\perp)), while another possible geometry has periodicity parallel to the bond c (labeled as BL6(\parallel)).

Band Folding Analysis

Before proceeding to the calculation results of magnon in 1D nanoribbon geometry, it is convenient to introduce band folding analysis, where the analysis of magnon dispersion in 2D geometry can be used again to analyze magnon dispersion in 1D nanoribbon geometry. The band folding basically tells us that the reduction of physical dimension in real space due to broken translational symmetry in certain direction leads to the band dispersion in reciprocal space being projected into certain reduced Brillouin zone. This is schematically shown in Fig. 4.17. In the ML and BL1, the symmetrically related Dirac points at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' in 2D BZ are projected onto $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ in 1D BZ, as shown in Fig. 4.17(a), and hence the magnon dispersion extrema at $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ are expected. In the BL2, the Dirac points at \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' in 2D BZ are no longer symmetrically connected due to broken inversion symmetry, and these Dirac points are projected onto $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ in 1D BZ, as shown by blue and red circles in Fig. 4.17(b), respectively. In the BL6 with periodicity perpendicular to the bond c , BL6(\perp), the magnon dispersion extrema in 2D BZ is located at \mathbf{M} , which is projected onto the $\bar{\Gamma}$ in the 1D BZ, as shown in Fig. 4.17(c). On the other hand, in the BL6 with periodicity parallel to the bond c , BL6(\parallel), the magnon dispersion extrema in 2D BZ is projected onto the $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ in the 1D BZ, as shown in Fig. 4.17(d).

Magnon Dispersion in Nanoribbon Geometry

In the case of ML CrI₃, the magnon dispersion is shown in Fig. 4.18(b), and the two localized edge states, which consist of only the Cr atom at the edges, are seen between 4.00 and 4.25 THz and cross at $\bar{\Gamma}$ point. Additionally, the two localized edge states also exhibit chirality upon mirroring to both $\bar{\Gamma}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$, which implies that magnons at the two edges propagate in opposite directions and confirms the topologically non-trivial phase of

ML CrI_3 . In the BL1 stacking order, the magnon dispersion is shown in Fig. 4.18(c), which has similar properties to those of the ML CrI_3 due to the similar space group symmetry, while the frequency range of localized chiral edge states is from 4.00 to 4.75 THz.

In the BL2 stacking order, magnon dispersion is shown in Fig. 4.18(d), and the two localized edge states have frequency ranges from 4.00 to 4.75 THz, which is wider than those in ML CrI_3 . The higher frequency edge states (blue line) are composed of only edge Cr atoms represented by the blue spheres in Fig. 4.18(a), while the lower frequency states (red line) are composed of only those at the opposite edge, and hence the chirality in these edge states is lost. Although the chirality of the magnon edge states is lost, the edge states satisfy $\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \neq \omega_{-\mathbf{k}}$ as a result of broken vertical mirror symmetry between two Cr atoms in the unit cell, which manifest in different magnon occupation numbers and magnon group velocities between two counterpropagating magnons at one edge.

In the BL6(\perp) stacking order, gapped magnon dispersion without localized edge states are observed and shown in Fig. 4.18(d). The reason for the localized edge states are not observed in Fig. 4.18(d) is due to that the $J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}$ connects the Cr atoms at the edge to those inside the nanoribbon, and this results in stronger hybridization between the Cr at the edge and those inside the nanoribbon than the hybridization between only the Cr atoms at the edges that supports localized edge states. This can be seen in two magnon states at frequency around 4.5 and 5.0 THz at $\bar{\Gamma}$ in Fig. 4.18(d), which are composed of both edge Cr atoms and Cr atoms inside the nanoribbon. On the other hand, in the BL6(\parallel), the localized edge states exist in the magnon dispersion of the BL6(\parallel), as shown in Fig. 4.18(e), and the magnon dispersion exhibit extrema at $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ which reflect the magnon dispersion extrema in the 2D geometry as discussed in terms of band folding analysis.

We note that the closing of the gapped bulk states by two localized edge states in the magnon dispersion of 1D nanoribbon BL2 and BL6 and the \mathbf{k} -dependence of the localized edge states are attributed to accidental origins rather than the symmetry origins at the edges of the nanoribbons. Particularly, we compared the magnon dispersion of 1D nanoribbon BL2 with that of $\text{CrI}_3/\text{MoTe}_2$ and $\text{CrI}_3/\text{HfS}_2$ in Ref. [188], where the 2D space group is identical to that of BL2, in which the vertical mirror symmetry between nearest neighboring Cr atoms is broken. In the Ref. [188], the broken vertical mirror symmetry between two Cr sub-lattices in the unit cell of the $\text{CrI}_3/\text{MoTe}_2$ and $\text{CrI}_3/\text{HfS}_2$ enters the magnon Hamiltonian only via two distinct single-ion anisotropy (SIA) terms, which results in the two opposite nanoribbon edges being composed of Cr atoms with distinct SIA terms. Consequently, the opening of the bulk gap with flat edge states connecting the valley at $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ is observed in the magnon dispersion of 1D nanoribbon $\text{CrI}_3/\text{MoTe}_2$ and $\text{CrI}_3/\text{HfS}_2$. In contrast, the broken vertical mirror symmetry in the BL2 in the present work enters the magnon Hamiltonian additionally via second-nearest neighbor spin-exchange interactions being distinct in magnitudes at two opposite edges of the nanoribbons, which gives rise to the \mathbf{k} dependence of magnon edge states.

Figure 4.16: (a) Quasi-one-dimensional (1D) nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination and width of 20 unit cells of honeycomb lattice. Two Cr atoms at the opposite edges are represented by blue and red spheres, while a Cr atom at the middle of the nanoribbon is represented by green spheres. White and black spheres represent two symmetrically distinct Cr atoms in the 2D unit cell. (b) Two different nanoribbon geometries can be made for BL6 stacking orders, where periodicity is (c) perpendicular or (d) parallel to the first-nearest neighbor bond c (the significantly enhanced $J_{(1),c}^{\text{ex}}$) as indicated by blue ellipses.

Figure 4.17: Illustration of 2D Brillouin zone folding onto 1D Brillouin zone in nanoribbon of (a) ML, BL1, (b) BL2, (c) BL6(\perp), and (d) BL6(\parallel). The magnon dispersion extrema, such as Dirac points, are labeled by colored circles, and different colors represent symmetrically different magnon dispersion extrema.

Figure 4.18: Magnon dispersion of (a) ML CrI_3 , bilayer CrI_3/As (b) BL1, and (c) BL2 in quasi-one-dimensional (1D) nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination and width of 20 unit cells of honeycomb lattice. Magnon dispersion of the BL6 stacking order, where periodicity is (d) perpendicular and (e) parallel to the bond c , as indicated by Fig. 4.16(c) and 4.16(d), respectively. In (a)-(e) red, green, and blue lines correspond to the contribution of the Cr atom indicated by red, green, and blue spheres in Fig. 4.16(a), respectively, to magnon dispersion.

4.4.4 Magnon Renormalization and Magnon Damping in Nanoribbon Monolayer CrI₃ and CrI₃/As Bilayers

In the previous section, the magnon dispersion for both ML CrI₃ and CrI₃/As bilayer in multiple stacking orders without taking into account the scattering between the magnons has been obtained. In this section, the magnon frequencies correction (renormalization) and the damping of 1D nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination of ML CrI₃ and CrI₃/As bilayers (Fig. 4.16) are calculated by self-consistently solving the Dyson equation in Eq. (2.189)-(2.190) under three-magnon interactions shown in Fig. 2.11(b). In the magnon dispersion, the magnon damping, $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$, is represented by the linewidth around the magnon frequencies, and narrow linewidth of the edge states compared to the magnon frequency gap from the bulk states is highly desired, which implies sharp and separable absorption peak from the bulk frequency response in the magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Magnon dispersion of the ML CrI₃ under three-magnon interactions are shown in Fig. 4.19(a), in which the linewidths and the corrected magnon frequencies of the edge states are shown by the red shaded areas and red dashed lines, respectively. Under three-magnon interactions, the two edge states overlap with each other at $\bar{\Gamma}$ - \bar{K} and \bar{K}' - $\bar{\Gamma}$, which implies large linewidth of the edge states, and the broadest linewidth occurs at the wave-vector indicated by k^* in Fig. 4.19(a). Additionally, the magnon frequencies of the edge states are strongly corrected around the wave-vector k^* in Fig. 4.19(a). To understand the origin of the broad linewidth and large correction to the edge states, analysis based on the imaginary part of Eq. (2.190) with Lorentzian factors in the summation are performed. The Lorentzian factor translates into a 'kinematic condition' [33, 135, 184], where the three-magnon interactions, that damp and corrects the magnons frequencies, occurs strongly when the momentum and energy conservation of three magnons are satisfied,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} &= \mathbf{q} + (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}), \\ \omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}} &= \omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

The left-hand side of energy conservation condition corresponds to the one magnon state, i.e., the magnon dispersion in LSWT limit, while the right-hand side of energy conservation condition corresponds to the two-magnon state which forms a continuum rather than a discrete value as in one magnon state [32]. If the magnon dispersion in LSWT limit crosses with two-magnon states continuum, damping channel of three-magnon interactions exist which results in large energy correction and large magnon damping. The two-magnon density of states (2mDOS) are calculated based on the following expression,

$$D(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = \sum_{n,l} \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \delta(\omega - \omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}), \quad (4.21)$$

and plotted as superimposed with the magnon dispersion in LSWT limit in Fig. 4.19(e). Large density of 2mDOS is clearly seen around the wave-vector k^* , and the crossing

between large density of 2mDOS and magnon dispersion in LSWT limit occurs at this wave-vector, which satisfies the momentum and energy conservation conditions and consequently allow the chiral edge states to decay leading to broad linewidth (large damping) and strong energy correction. Furthermore, the large density of 2mDOS around the k^* originates mainly from the two-magnon state that is composed of manifold degenerate magnon states at $q^* \approx \bar{\mathbf{M}}$, indicated by a square shape, and magnon states at lowest frequency magnon states at the wave-vector $k^* - q^*$ indicated by the a triangle shape in 4.19(i).

The magnon dispersion of BL1 nanoribbon in Fig. 4.19(b) shows that the two edge states (red shaded areas) are well separated compared to those of ML, and the broadest linewidth and large correction occur at the wave-vector slightly shifted toward $\bar{\Gamma}$ and higher frequencies around 4.5 THz. This is due to the crossing between magnon dispersion in LSWT limit and 2mDOS occurs at much higher frequencies and slightly smaller wave-vectors, as shown in Fig. 4.19(f). This is also shown in Fig. 4.20(a) and 4.20(b), where the peaks of $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the upper and lower magnon edge states of BL1 nanoribbon (solid lines) are shifted toward $\bar{\Gamma}$ and slightly lowered from that of ML nanoribbon (dashed lines).

In the BL2 nanoribbon, where the chirality is lost due to the broken vertical mirror symmetry between two Cr atoms, the magnon dispersion shows that the two edge states (red shaded areas) are largely separated compared to those of ML and BL1, as seen in Fig. 4.19(c). Additionally, counter-propagating magnon edge states undergo different damping, i.e., $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}} \neq \Gamma_{-\mathbf{k}}$, while retaining the trend of damping as a function of wave-vector \mathbf{k} , and this is clearly shown by solid line in the Fig. 4.20(c) and 4.20(d). This results implies that, although the chirality is lost under broken vertical mirror symmetry, and one edges allows magnons to propagate in opposite directions, the DMI interactions in the edge of BL2 nanoribbon give different damping for the oppositely propagating magnons. In particular, two second-nearest neighboring Cr atoms at one edge of the nanoribbon are related to each other via real-space local inversion symmetry operation, and the second-nearest neighbor DMIs break that symmetry operation due to the anti-symmetric nature of DMIs. The breaking of the real-space inversion symmetry manifests in the high-order magnon Hamiltonian, i.e., $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, via the $D_{(2)}^\perp$, where the $D_{(2)}^\perp$ in the $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ lowers the probability scattering in one bond direction while increases the probability scattering in the opposite bond direction at the nanoribbon edge. In this way, unidirectional magnon edge states can be artificially generated in the BL2 via three-magnon interactions, in contrast to the symmetrically protected unidirectional magnon edge states in the ML and BL1 stacking order.

In the BL6(∥) nanoribbon, the magnon dispersion exhibits the non-chiral magnon edge states at wave-vectors $\bar{\mathbf{K}}-\bar{\mathbf{M}}-\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ being more separated than the magnon edge states at wave-vectors $\bar{\Gamma}-\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ in ML, BL1, and BL2, which is shown in Fig. 4.19(d). Figure 4.20(e) and 4.20(f) show how small magnon damping peak of the edge states of BL6(∥) (solid line) at $\bar{\mathbf{K}}-\bar{\mathbf{M}}-\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ compared to that of ML (dashed line) at $\bar{\Gamma}-\bar{\mathbf{K}}$. The counter-propagating magnon edge states also undergo different damping, as in the BL2 case. The smaller edge states in the BL6(∥) at wave-vectors $\bar{\mathbf{K}}-\bar{\mathbf{M}}-\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ is mainly attributed to the change of

kinematic condition in three-magnon interactions. The 2mDOS of the BL6(\parallel) at wave-vectors $\bar{\mathbf{K}}\text{-}\bar{\mathbf{M}}\text{-}\bar{\mathbf{K}}'$ in Fig. 4.19(h) shows no large density around the magnon edge states (red solid line), which is due to the lifted degeneracy at $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ in the magnon dispersion in LSWT limit from the broken rotational symmetry, as discussed in section 4.4.1. This small 2mDOS in the BL6(\parallel) results in a few magnon damping channel that only slightly broadens the magnon linewidth, compared to the ML, BL1, and BL2.

Figure 4.19: Magnon dispersion of 1D nanoribbon with zig-zag termination in Fig. 4.16 for (a) ML CrI_3 , (b) BL1, (c) BL2, and (d) BL6(\parallel) bilayers stacking orders under three-magnon interactions. Red color represents the magnon edge states. Shaded areas represent the linewidth of magnon dispersion due to damping from three-magnon interactions, $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$. The two-magnon density of states, $D(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$, superimposed with the magnon dispersion in LSWT limit for (e) ML, (f) BL1, (g) BL2, and (h) BL6(\parallel). (i) The origin of $D(\mathbf{k}, \omega \approx 4 \text{ THz})$ (see the text). In all figures, k^* represents the wave-vector where crossing between $D(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$ and $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the edge states occurs.

Figure 4.20: Magnon damping, $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$, of (a,b) BL1, (c,d) BL2, and (e,f) BL6(\parallel) nanoribbon, as a function of wave-vectors. The top figures correspond to the magnon damping from higher frequency edge states, while the bottom figures correspond to the magnon damping from lower frequency edge states. In all figures dashed lines represent the $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the ML nanoribbon, while the solid lines represent the $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the corresponding bilayer stacking orders.

4.5 Concluding Remarks

In this chapter, the developed magnetic force theorem and linear spin-wave theory with many-body Green's function are applied to investigate the interplay between isotropic spin-exchange interactions and DMIs on topological THz magnon in the 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayers in multiple stacking orders. Three symmetrically distinct stacking orders of CrI₃/As bilayers are chosen to simulate the effect of symmetry modifications on the static magnetism, i.e., isotropic spin-exchange interactions, DMIs, and topological magnons.

The isotropic spin-exchange interactions of CrI₃/As undergo enhancements from 16% to more than 100% due to the reduced crystalline electric field, that splits the e_g and t_{2g} states of Cr d orbitals, and the splitting of e_g states near the Fermi level. The non-local origin of magnetic anisotropy in CrI₃ is confirmed, in which the origin of large magnetic anisotropy in this system arises from first- and second-nearest neighbor anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, rather than the local single-ion anisotropy from the individual Cr atom. Furthermore, the modulation of DMIs in the CrI₃/As bilayers are discussed, where the interfacial charge transfer from the As atom to the I atom breaks the inversion symmetry of Cr-Cr bond.

Using the isotropic and anisotropic spin-exchange interactions, the magnon dispersion in 2D and quasi-1D nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination were investigated, and the topological properties of magnon were confirmed in the magnon Berry curvature and the existence of localized magnon edge states. It is found that the presence of As monolayer also modulates both the localized magnon edge states frequencies and magnon damping. Although the chirality of magnon edge states is lost in several stacking orders with reduced symmetry, two counter-propagating edge states magnons undergo different magnon damping, mainly due to finite second-nearest neighbor DMIs that are perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In this work, the interplay between magnetic interactions on THz magnon dynamics in bulk antiferromagnetic insulators TMOs and thin-film vdW ferromagnetic insulator CrI₃/As bilayers are theoretically investigated. Derivation and the implementation of generalized magnetic force theorem (MFT) on the FLAPW framework allow one to extract the generalized spin-exchange constants directly from one-electron energies and wavefunctions of Kohn-Sham equations. Using these generalized spin-exchange constants, the magnon dispersion of antiferromagnetic insulators TMOs and ferromagnetic insulators heterostructures CrI₃ in THz regimes were mainly evaluated via LSWT, and the interplay between the magnetic interactions in the topological magnon dispersion were analyzed.

In Chapter 3, the Néel temperatures and THz AFMR frequencies of two magnon modes in the TMOs (MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO) were evaluated to benchmark the developed MFT and LSWT. The isotropic spin-exchange interactions successfully describes the experimentally observed Néel temperatures of all bulk TMOs, confirming the validity of the MFT developed in this work. On the other hand, only the AFMR frequencies of MnO and NiO are successfully captured by the LSWT, while those of FeO and CoO are not well captured in the present work. In the case of the FeO and CoO, the SOC has only been introduced phenomenologically via the MCA, while, the SOC also couples spin and orbital degree of freedom and creates multiple spin states. The treatment of multiple spin states may require the general LSWT, i.e., flavor-wave theory, to fully capture the experimentally observed results.

In Chapter 4, the interplay between magnetic interactions on topological magnonic properties in 2D vdW CrI₃/As bilayers were evaluated, in which three symmetrically distinct stacking orders were employed. Modulation of isotropic spin-exchange and DMIs were observed due to the change of the electronic states of Cr *d* orbitals under the site symmetry breaking induced by the As substrate and interfacial charge transfer from the As substrate to the I atoms, respectively. The ratio between isotropic spin-exchange and DMIs reach around 12%, which implies the magnetic ground state of the the CrI₃ layer remains collinear under the addition of As substrate. The topological magnon properties were evaluated via magnon Berry curvature and the existence of chiral magnon edge states in 1D nanoribbon geometry. The addition of As substrate slightly lowers the chiral magnon

edge states damping, and in the case where chirality of magnon edge states is lost, two counter-propagating magnon edge states undergo different damping, mainly due to the second-nearest neighbor DMIs at the edge of the nanoribbon.

In this dissertation, the effects of magnetic interactions on THz magnon excitation in antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic insulators were systematically studied by means of MFT and LSWT. In conclusion, the findings in this work gives insights on how magnetic interactions, driven from the electronic states of the magnetic atoms and the ligands in the vicinity, affect the magnon frequencies. Particularly, the long wave-length limit magnon frequencies in the bulk system can be engineered by applying lattice distortion which changes the magnetic anisotropy from either MDIs or MCA from the SOC. On the other hand, short wave-length limit magnon frequencies in the thin film can be tailored by modifying the electronic and spin states of the TM cation and the ligand in its vicinity, which alters the spin-exchange interactions between TM cations. For instance, by stacking the CrI₃ with a ferroelectric substrate, modulation of interlayer magnetic interactions by perpendicular electric field was demonstrated, which stems from strong interlayer spin-charge interactions [189]. Additionally, by twisting double bilayers of CrI₃, electric-field switchable multiple spin-textures were demonstrated, which stems from the electric-field tunable interlayer isotropic spin-exchange interactions, and this property may enable controllable non-trivial topological magnon phases via electric-field [190].

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List of Publications

1. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Role of Magnetic Dipole-Dipole Interaction on Magnon in NiO
Journal of the Physical Society of Japan, **92**, 084703, (2023)
2. K. Nawa, A. Gumarilang, T. Moriyama, and K. Nakamura
Tuning of exchange constants and magnetic anisotropy for terahertz antiferromagnetic resonance frequencies in cation-doped NiO
Physical Review Applied, **21**, 034040, (2024)
3. M. Arifin, E. Suharyadi, A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Enhanced Sensitivity of Magneto-Optical Surface Plasmon Resonance in the FeCu Superlattices
Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **2696**, 012007, (2024)
4. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Magnon dispersion and terahertz antiferromagnetic resonance frequencies in 3d transition-metal monoxide
Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials, **610**, 172499, (2024)
5. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Tensor representation of four-magnon interactions Hamiltonian and magnon decay rate suppression by magnetic dipolar interactions in the antiferromagnetic insulator NiO
Physical Review B, **113**, 024411, (2026)
6. A. Gumarilang and K. Nakamura
Tailoring spin-exchange interactions and topological magnons in 2D ferromagnetic van der Waals CrI₃/As bilayer via multiple stacking orders: A first-principles study
Physical Review Materials, **10**, 024407, (2026).

List of Presentations

International Conferences

1. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura, Investigation of Magnon Hybridization in NiO with Fe Impurity by First-Principles Calculation
The 11th International Symposium of Metallic Multilayers, 2023, (Seoul)
2. K. Nawa, A. Gumarilang, T. Moriyama, and K. Nakamura
Controllable THz Antiferromagnetic Resonance Frequencies in NiO by Cation Doping: First-Principles Study
The 25th International Colloquium on Magnetic Films and Surfaces, 2024, (Perugia, Italy)
3. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Four-Magnon Interactions and Gilbert Damping in Antiferromagnetic Insulators NiO
The 5th International Symposium on Advanced Magnetic Materials and Applications, 2024, (Quang Binh, Vietnam)
4. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Temperature and Magnon Wave-Vector Dependence of Gilbert Damping Processes for Two Magnon Modes in Antiferromagnetic NiO
The International Conference on Solid State Devices and Materials, 2024, (Himeji, Hyogo)
5. A. Gumarilang and K. Nakamura
Tailoring Magnon Dirac Gap in 2D van der Waals CrI₃/As Bilayers: First-Principles Study
The 26th Asian Workshop on First-Principles Electronic Structure Calculations, 2025, (Tsukuba, Ibaraki)
6. K. Kobayashi, A. Gumarilang, and K. Nakamura
First-Principles Study of Magnon in Altermagnet: Hexagonal FeS
The 26th Asian Workshop on First-Principles Electronic Structure Calculations, 2025, (Tsukuba, Ibaraki)

Domestic Conferences and Seminars

1. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Unveiling Antiferromagnetic Resonance Frequencies of $3d$ Transition-Metal Monoxides via Landau-Lifshitz Equation
The 84th Japan Society of Applied Physics Autumn Meeting, 2023, (Kumamoto)
2. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Theoretical Analysis of Magnetic Damping by Four-Magnon Interactions for NiO from Tensor Representation of Second Quantization
The 71st Japan Society of Applied Physics Spring Meeting, 2024, (Setagaya, Tokyo)
3. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Magnetic Damping Calculation Based on Four-Magnon Interactions
The 3rd Workshop on ‘Progress and Harmony of First-Principles Calculation and Machine Learning’, 2024, (Suita, Osaka)
4. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Effects of Magnon Spin-Polarization of Magnon Lifetime in Antiferromagnetic Insulator NiO
The 85th Japan Society of Applied Physics Autumn Meeting, 2024, (Bandaijima, Niigata)
5. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Ferromagnetic Resonance Frequencies of CrI₃ Monolayer Under Triangular Lattice As substrate: a First-Principles Study
IEEE Magnetic Society Nagoya Chapter Young Researcher Meeting, 2025, (Tsu, Mie)
6. K. Kobayashi, A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Ab-initio study of magnon in L10 Mn-based antiferromagnets
The 72nd Japan Society of Applied Physics Spring Meeting, 2025, (Tokyo)
7. A. Gumarilang, K. Nawa, and K. Nakamura
Tailoring THz Magnon Frequencies in Multiple CrI₃/As Stacking Orders via Exchange Interactions: A First-Principles Study
OSAKA-SYMMML Workshop 2025, (Nakanoshima, Osaka)
8. A. Gumarilang and K. Nakamura
Engineering THz Magnon Frequencies in 2D Ferromagnetic vdW CrI₃/As Bilayer: A First-Principles Study
The 86th Japan Society of Applied Physics Autumn Meeting, 2025, (Nagoya, Aichi)

9. K. Kobayashi, A. Gumarilang, and K. Nakamura
Ab-initio study of magnon in altermagnet Hexagonal FeS
The 86th Japan Society of Applied Physics Autumn Meeting, 2025, (Nagoya,
Aichi)

*"When a complex system is far from equilibrium,
small islands of coherence in a sea of chaos have the capacity
to shift the entire system to a higher order."*

ILYA PRIGOGINE

Nobel Laureates in Chemistry for Non-Equilibrium Thermodynamics